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Quantifying Terrestrial Ecosystem Functions
to Improve Bioretention Design

By

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Abstract

The broad motivation for this research endeavor is to investigate how water resources engineers and other planning and design professionals working in urban environments can promote improved functioning of terrestrial ecosystems. A worldwide decline in biodiversity and ecosystem functions is ongoing, and some drivers of this decline are specific to urban areas. The decisions of engineers working in urban environments therefore can influence this decline. Engineers designing bioretention basins for management of surface runoff typically have not considered implications of their design configurations, plant choices, and management decisions on terrestrial ecosystem structure and function. This project aimed to bridge a gap and connect existing knowledge from the fields of engineering and ecology to bring ecosystem function into engineering decision making. Specifically, from this existing knowledge base, this study aimed to identify planning and design criteria to improve terrestrial ecological functions in and around bioretention basins, while never losing sight of core water quantity and quality management objectives. A key measure identified is the ability of bioretention basins and their urban surroundings to provide host plants for the larvae of native butterflies and moths. This single measure can serve as a proxy for a range of desirable ecosystem functions.

The research approach employed novel uses of existing data and methods while also developing new data and methods to meet the overarching goal of integrating ecosystem function into stormwater infrastructure design. Throughout this work, over 175 relevant multi-disciplinary publications are highlighted, identified using a combination of structured keyword searches and traditional literature review methods. Existing data on plant taxa for bioretention listed in disparate sources (design manuals, government databases, data posted by researchers and non-profit organizations) were standardized and connected based on common fields, resulting in a

searchable data set covering over 700 plant species. Performance of 18 alternative bioretention designs over 20 years was explored using continuous numerical simulations conducted in both Hydrus-1D and EPA SWMM5. Results were quantitatively compared between these models and validated to long-term field data. The ability of over 50 global circulation models (GCMs) to accurately match precipitation benchmarks was explored, and results were developed into an approach for selecting GCM ensembles for future water resources applications including bioretention basins. This work also extended a previously reported method of adjusting historical precipitation time series to also reflect projected changes in consecutive dry days. Quantitative spatial metrics of habitat connectivity used in ecology and conservation science were explored in a watershed-scale bioretention planning and policy context.

The research posed four research questions with implications for engineering practice. First (RQ1.1), to increase measures of ecological performance at the site scale, is it necessary to accept decreases in traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures? Results indicate that design configurations and plant choices exist in many cases that can achieve the traditional engineering objectives of limiting surface outflow and effluent pollutant loads while at the same time increasing potential biodiversity at the site scale. Because some plants that promote greater biodiversity are adversely impacted by longer durations of saturated soils, design choices need to limit the duration of surface ponding to provide a balance between traditional and ecological objectives. Second (RQ1.2), under projected end-of-century rainfall and temperature conditions, will it be necessary to accept decreases in additional traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures compared to the results of RQ 1.1? The research results did not indicate an increase in these tradeoffs. However, results indicated that drought tolerant plant taxa are already required under present conditions and will continue to

be required in the future. Third (RQ1.3), what subset of traditional and ecological performance measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that will provide actionable information to a professional bioretention designer seeking to rank design alternatives? Recommended measures include annual groundwater recharge volume, surface outflow volume, peak flow reduction, a plant diversity index, and a butterfly diversity index. Fourth (RQ2), what subset of habitat connectivity measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that can provide actionable information to decision makers with influence over bioretention placement and land use policy? Recommendations include the total habitat area and the distribution of distances between neighboring pairs of suitable habitat patches in the larger landscape.

In addition to answering the formal research questions, this research project has produced novel data sets and recommended procedures of use to practicing water resource engineers and researchers. First, the research identifies a body of publicly accessible data from multiple disciplines that can inform choices between alternative plans, designs, and policies. Second, a newly compiled data set of plant species listed in five bioretention design manuals published in the U.S. Northeast and Midwest regions is presented. Practitioners can filter and sort this data by many different variables, including the ability of plants to serve as butterfly larval hosts. More quantitative methods are demonstrated for analyzing plant species' tolerance to soil moisture conditions based on time patterns of water level, water inflow and outflow, and temperature. Third, a method is suggested for practitioners to select and analyze an ensemble of global circulation models to inform design choices. Fourth, quantitative methods are suggested that professionals can consider when comparing the habitat connectivity implications of plans and policies affecting bioretention locations. Finally, the document recommends future research topics at the site and watershed scales.

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation and Research Questions

The broad motivation for this research endeavor is to investigate how water resources engineers and other planning and design professionals working in urban environments can promote improved functioning of terrestrial ecosystems. A worldwide decline in biodiversity and ecosystem functions is ongoing, and some drivers of this decline are specific to urban areas. The decisions of engineers working in urban environments therefore can influence this decline. Throughout this document, I identify and discuss specific criteria engineers can consider to improve terrestrial ecosystem functions alongside objectives typical of urban stormwater management in the United States today. One critical decision I discuss that impacts ecosystem functions in and around bioretention basins is plant choice. In addition to plant choice, I discuss a range of performance measures quantifying both traditional and ecological performance measures, including the ability of the plants selected to host the larvae of butterfly and moth taxa present in urban environments. For any ecological criteria engineers adopt to be effective, they need to inform practical design decisions made by professionals and project stakeholders. They need to consider projected climate conditions through the end of the functional life span of any new infrastructure being implemented. Finally, they need to consider how the surrounding urban landscape and watershed can constrain or complement the ecosystem functions being provided. Outcomes of this research project include answers to four formal research questions designed to advance engineering practice and spur further research in pursuit of these objectives.

Research Question 1.1: To increase measures of ecological performance at the site scale, is it necessary to accept decreases in traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures? Research Question 1.1 is answered in Chapter 4.

Research Question 1.2: Under projected end-of-century rainfall and temperature conditions, will it be necessary to accept decreases in additional traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures compared to the results of Research Question 1.1? An answer to Research Question 1.2 is provided in Chapter 5.

Research Questions 1.1 and 1.2 link to null hypotheses that can be tested using formal statistical methods. The primary intended audience for the resulting information is engineering researchers. These results also may inform the construction of indices used in Research Question 1.3. Under Research Question 1.3, the intention is to demonstrate how a subset of the site-scale performance measures can be combined to inform an iterative design process typical of engineering practice. A typical design process starts with a single design concept and refines it iteratively. Sometimes, a design process may include a feasibility study phase that considers a small number of alternatives. Methods for Research Question 1.3 are not based on a traditional hypothesis testing framework but rather on concepts from decision science and strategies for addressing the historical theory-practice gap in engineering.

Research Question 1.3: What subset of traditional and ecological performance measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that will provide actionable information to a professional bioretention designer seeking to rank design alternatives? Research Question 1.3 is answered in Chapter 4.

Research Question 2: What subset of habitat connectivity measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that can provide actionable information to decision makers with influence over bioretention placement and land use policy? The purpose of Research Question 2 is to survey information in the literature informing whether connectivity measures may be able to provide actionable information to professionals with some influence over bioretention siting

decisions at the watershed scale. The intended audience for Research Question 2 includes municipal green infrastructure program managers, integrated water utility managers, professionals in government agencies with land use planning authority, and potentially large institutional land owners. Research Question 2 is answered in Chapter 6.

1.2 Products to Inform Water Resources Engineering Practice

In addition to answering the formal research questions presented in Section 1.1, this research project has produced knowledge and products of immediate use both to academic researchers and to water resources engineers in professional practice. The literature review presented in Chapter 2 surveys suggestions made to date on designing bioretention and other green stormwater installations to promote terrestrial ecosystem function. Chapter 2 includes a list and discussion identifying a range of open data available to researchers and practitioners interested in incorporating terrestrial ecosystem functional objectives into their work. Finally, Chapter 2 concludes with a list and detailed discussion of potential future research topics at the intersection of water resources engineering and ecology.

Chapter 3 provides a description and analysis of a new compilation of plant taxa incorporated in a range of published government and industry bioretention design guidelines. This information will be of immediate use to planning and design practitioners in the U.S. Mid-Atlantic and Midwest regions. It will expand the range of plant choices professionals currently consulting a single source of design guidelines may consider. Practitioners will be able to filter and sort the data set by variables such as geographic range, native status, and tolerance (as stated by the manuals) to extremes of wet conditions, dry conditions, and loads of deicing salts.

Chapter 4 presents a planning and design decision framework, and results are demonstrated with example specific performance measures for practitioners to consider incorporating into the framework. These performance measures address both traditional

engineering performance objectives and terrestrial ecological function objectives. The suggested measures can be derived from simulated or observed time series of water level or temperature using models and methods familiar to many practicing engineers, and these measures can be combined with other measures deemed important by the practitioner.

Chapter 5 suggests a specific procedure for choosing global circulation model ensembles to inform planning and design decisions in urban water resources systems under projected climate change conditions. Criteria considered in the suggested procedure can be weighted in relation to the objectives of a specific urban water resources engineering project. Chapter 5 also explores an experimental procedure for adjusting observed precipitation time series to represent future conditions. This procedure produces time series that capture temporal patterns and variation in precipitation at time scales relevant to urban water planning and engineering projects.

Chapter 6 gathers information from the literature on landscape/watershed scale habitat connectivity indices that may be relevant to green stormwater infrastructure installations. While many publications include qualitative discussions of this topic, a practical quantitative approach to consider habitat connectivity in urban water resources engineering design has yet to be proposed. This chapter begins to fill this gap between theory and practice, and it proposes future research others may choose to undertake to make further progress in this endeavor.

CHAPTER 2. Literature Review: *Lepidoptera* Abundance and Diversity as a Quantitative Measure of Ecosystem Function in Bioretention Design

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 Objective

The primary objective of this chapter is to propose *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity that can be supported by a given stormwater management bioretention basin as a quantitative measure to guide design choices. While designers can consider a range of other indicator taxa, there are many reasons to focus on *Lepidoptera*. This single measure can be considered a proxy for an important set of terrestrial ecosystem functions and for biodiversity as described in Section 2.1.2. Employing this measure therefore will provide engineers with the ability to consider terrestrial ecosystem functions explicitly in the design process. Engineers designing bioretention basins for management of surface runoff are asked to consider many objectives simultaneously. However, they typically do not consider implications of their design, plant choices, and management decisions on terrestrial ecosystem structure and function (e.g., Cook et al., 2023; Prudencio and Null, 2018). A foundation of knowledge to evaluate design decisions in light of ecosystem function exists in the fields of engineering and ecology, but historically there has been a gap in knowledge sharing and collaboration between these disciplines. There is a need to bridge this gap as engineers seek to advance bioretention designs that meet an increasingly wide range of objectives while never losing sight of core water quantity and water quality management objectives.

2.1.2 Definitions

To begin bridging the gap between the disciplines of engineering and ecology, I will employ a definition of the term “ecosystem function” that is recognizable to both disciplines and intended for application within the narrow domain of bioretention design. I herein define

“function” as work performed by a designed system (such as a bioretention basin receiving urban surface runoff) where the work has been identified as desirable in the judgment of the system’s design team. This definition is logically consistent with definitions of the term “ecosystem service” commonly employed by ecologists (Costanza, 1997; Jax, 2005), and it is also appropriate to serve as a basis for engineering design. In ecology, value judgments or comparison to a suitable reference state may be employed to determine what work will be considered desirable from a human perspective (e.g., Jax, 2005). When a system is designed by engineers, desired functions of the system typically are determined by a project owner or stakeholders and stated explicitly at commencement of the planning and design process (e.g., Yoe and Orth, 1996). Engineers then apply scientific principles to choose the components and structure of a system (including soil characteristics and plants, where relevant) expected to achieve the desired functions while considering external conditions acting on the defined boundaries of the system (Beyers and Odum, 1993). There is an opportunity to either expand the design team beyond engineers or to equip engineers with understandable and usable metrics to design more inclusively.

In the context of this chapter, specific bioretention system functions to be considered will be (1) hydrologic regulation, (2) production, or facilitation of energy and carbon flows between trophic levels (i.e., “up the food chain”), (3) nutrient retention, and (4) habitat provision. Pollination and nectar provision will be mentioned, but a detailed treatment of these functions will be considered outside the scope of this study. The term “biodiversity” will be considered a description of the characteristics or ordered biological components of the system (Chao et al., 2014; Pavoine and Bonsall, 2011), analogous to engineering system characteristics such as soil

properties or hydraulic structure configuration. I will not attempt to value functions performed in financial units.

2.1.3 Organization

To provide context for introduction of ecological design criteria, Section 2.2 briefly summarizes the historical background and policy framework for urban stormwater management design in the United States. The focus is on bioretention, an umbrella term for a range of commonly employed nature-based solutions incorporating soil, water, and plants at ground level. I describe the expanding number of performance objectives that stormwater management planners and designers are asked to consider in parallel. These expanding objectives now include voluntary consideration of terrestrial ecosystem functional objectives such as providing habitat and nutrition for a diverse range of plant and animal life and facilitating the flow of nutrients and energy between trophic levels in the ecosystem. In Section 2.3, I briefly summarize global trends of insect decline, making a case that the decisions of planners and engineers working in urban environments are important because they can either contribute to these negative trends or potentially contribute to their mitigation.

In Section 2.4, I explain why bioretention basins are typically nutrient-enriched ecosystems and why this enrichment may place limits on biodiversity that can be achieved in these systems. Nutrient retention is often an explicit design objective for bioretention basins to protect downstream aquatic ecosystems, and the presence of nutrients in bioretention basins is therefore a constraint that engineers must consider when setting objectives for terrestrial ecosystem functions. In Section 2.5, I make a case that an important terrestrial ecosystem objective for practicing stormwater designers is to create or restore functioning food chains incorporating multiple trophic levels in and around bioretention basins. Insect herbivores, and specifically the insect order *Lepidoptera*, including butterflies and moths, are identified as an

important “missing link” that can transfer energy and matter from bioretention plants to vertebrates, creating functional ecological communities in the urban landscape (Narango et al., 2020). In Section 2.6, I demonstrate that although no data making direct links between *Lepidoptera* and bioretention basins are currently available, data required to make quantitative use of *Lepidoptera* in bioretention design are extensive and widely available due to the popularity of butterflies among both professional and citizen scientists. In Section 2.7 I present results of a literature review to demonstrate that the quantitative use of *Lepidoptera* in this context has never before been reported in published literature, indicating a gap in existing knowledge. This literature review was conducted in three phases, including a first phase based on a structured keyword search. A description of the literature review methodology is included in Section 2.7.1 and Figure 2.1. Finally, in Section 2.8 I propose a research agenda aimed at connecting and exploiting available data across disciplines while also developing new knowledge to inform a design decision framework. This new framework will be of use to professional bioretention planners and designers who wish to consider terrestrial ecosystem objectives in practice.

2.2 A Brief History of Multiple-Objective Urban Stormwater Management Design in the United States

Water resource engineers practicing in the urban environment typically are required to balance a range of performance objectives simultaneously. Urbanization profoundly alters the hydrologic characteristics of watersheds by converting permeable surfaces (soil, vegetation) to sealed impermeable materials including pavement and buildings. Prior to approximately the 1970s in the United States, water management efforts in urbanized and urbanizing areas typically focused on mitigating risks to human life and property posed by increased flood peaks (Debo and Reese, 2002). With the advent of the Clean Water Act in the 1970s, governments at all levels

began to pay more attention to protection of aquatic ecosystems by limiting pollutant loads to surface waters (Davis et al., 2022). By the 1990s, some state and local programs included measures to prevent erosive flows from damaging the structure of downstream aquatic ecosystems, such as stream banks, channels, and substrates needed by aquatic organisms (e.g., Prince George's County, 2000). Gradually, many jurisdictions adopted objectives of mimicking a pre-development water balance, taking into account the various fates of surface runoff including groundwater recharge, stream baseflow replenishment, surface runoff, and evapotranspiration (National Academy of Sciences, 2009; Davis et al., 2022). In the U.S. context, all of these objectives typically are mandated by federal, state, and municipal regulations.

Mandates to consider the hydrologic cycle and biogeochemical cycles within stormwater management facilities require stormwater engineers to be familiar with the dynamics of soil-water-plant systems and to apply this understanding to inform design choices. Qualitative advice on soil composition and plants appropriate for stormwater management facilities is tabulated in guidance for public infrastructure design and private building/zoning code requirements at the state and municipal level (e.g., Center for Watershed Protection and Maryland Department of the Environment, 2009; Philadelphia Water Department, 2020; Shaw and Schmidt, 2003; also see detailed discussion in Chapter 3). More recently, quantitative research is beginning to shed light on specific plant species and plant characteristics that enhance pollutant removal in stormwater management systems, thereby helping protect downstream aquatic ecosystems (e.g., Payne et al., 2018). Evidence supports an increase in hydraulic conductivity, permeability, and pollutant removal in systems with plants compared to systems with no plants. This improved performance can be linked to the presence and characteristics of roots (Dagenais et al., 2018).

With an understanding of plants' role in stormwater design, in addition to the dynamics of water and soil, a natural progression is for engineers and other urban design professionals to consider the impacts of the systems they are designing on terrestrial habitat and biodiversity more broadly, both at the site scale and at the landscape/watershed scale. Most engineering disciplines have not traditionally focused on biodiversity, but choices made by engineers affect the characteristics of the built environment and therefore the extent and quality of habitat for plants and animals in developed areas (Prudencio and Null, 2018). In the U.S. stormwater management policy context, explicit consideration of terrestrial ecosystem functions is voluntary. While a range of policy measures might be considered in the future to enhance terrestrial ecosystems, my intention in this chapter is to propose voluntary measures for interested designers and stakeholders to consider.

This chapter will focus on bioretention systems, and I am using this term to refer to a range of common configuration options for urban nature-based solutions incorporating intermittent surface ponding, soil, plants, and hydraulic outflow controls. Related terms found in the literature include rain gardens, stormwater planters, bioinfiltration, biofiltration, bioswales, and vegetated swales (e.g., see Prudencio and Null, 2018 and Cook et al., 2023 for broader discussions of green stormwater infrastructure terms).

2.3 Engineers Have an Ability and Responsibility to Influence Insect Decline

A large body of evidence indicates that wild plants and animals are disappearing around the world. While ecologists are likely familiar with this evidence, many practicing engineers and other design professionals may be less familiar. The purpose of this section is to briefly summarize key evidence for the engineering audience and to convince engineers that they have an ability to mitigate several drivers of insect decline. Engineers have an ability to influence insect decline because they make daily decisions about the built environment and infrastructure

of cities, including collaborating with landscape architects and other professionals on plant choices for stormwater management practices. These decisions in turn affect habitat and resources available to insects. This section is not intended to provide a comprehensive overview or critical analysis of the global biodiversity decline issue. More comprehensive analyses have been provided by other sources including those cited in this section.

Trends of widespread population declines and elevated extinction risks are being observed in insects on multiple continents. Forister et al. (2019) stated that “insects are experiencing a multicontinental crisis that is apparent as reductions in abundance, diversity, and biomass”. The magnitude and severity of the trend is such that it has been described as an “insect apocalypse” (Goulson, 2021). Sharp declines in *Lepidoptera* species (butterflies, skippers, and moths) have been documented on multiple continents. In the United Kingdom, Warren et al. (2021) reported 8% of species extinct and a 50% decline in overall abundance since 1976, while in the Netherlands the corresponding figures were 20% of species extinct and a 50% decline in abundance. In Belgium, Warren et al. (2021) reported 29% of species extinct and a 30% decline in abundance between 1992 and 2007. In the U.S. State of Ohio, Wepprich et al. (2019) studied 21 years of data on 81 butterfly species, reporting a cumulative 33% reduction in abundance over this period and three times as many species experiencing declines as increases. Across the United States, the non-profit organization NatureServe has classified 16% of butterfly and skipper species and 20% of moth species as being at risk of extinction (NatureServe, 2023). There is a lively scientific debate about data collection methods and potential biases in the literature discussing these insect declines, and a comprehensive survey of this debate is beyond the scope of the current dissertation aimed at an audience of engineers and other urban design professionals. Nonetheless, there is a widespread view among scientists that declines in numbers

of species and in abundance of many common species are occurring and need to be addressed (Wagner et al., 2021b).

A range of contributing causes of species declines has been identified. While there is debate about the relative importance of the contributing factors, a loose consensus has emerged that principal drivers of insect decline are land use change including habitat loss (e.g., Habel et al., 2019), urbanization (Concepcion et al., 2023), climate change (Halsch et al., 2012; Harvey et al., 2023), agricultural practices (Raven and Wagner, 2021) including neonicotinoid insecticides (van Deynze et al., 2024; Janousek et al., 2023), introduced species (Wagner et al., 2021b; Yoon and Read, 2016), and pollution, with excess nitrogen loads being a particularly impactful form of pollution (e.g., Forister et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2021b).

While explicit links between insect decline and bioretention are unavailable in the literature, a group of identified stressors leading to insect decline tends to co-occur in densely populated urban and suburban areas, where choices of water resource engineers and other urban design professionals can be particularly impactful. This group of stressors includes conversion of forests and other natural habitats to residential, commercial, and industrial land uses which drastically alter historical hydrology (National Academy of Sciences, 2009), fragment and pollute remaining habitat, and reduce the availability of host plants and nectar sources (e.g., Fenoglio et al. 2021). Exotic species, fertilizers, and pesticides are introduced in urban environments through landscaping practices, while urban heat island effects, sound pollution and light pollution in urban areas also can have impacts on insects and other wildlife (Wagner et al., 2021b). Of particular concern, combustion of fossil fuels to meet energy demand in urban areas is a key source of atmospheric nitrogen deposited across rural, urban, and aquatic environments (Vitousek et al., 1997), and excess nitrogen loads have been linked to reduced abundance and

diversity of organisms at multiple trophic levels, including plants (Bobbink et al., 2010) and animals (Betzholtz et al., 2013; Nijssen et al., 2017; Poyry et al., 2017).

Climate change is impacting insects and is expected to be an increasingly important driver of insect declines in the future (Harvey et al., 2023). Along with increasing average air temperatures, insects will be impacted by changes in the severity and frequency of extreme heat and cold periods, fires, storms, floods and drought conditions (Wagner et al., 2021b). Decisions of engineers and other urban design professionals have potential to exacerbate or mitigate these stressors.

Declines in insect abundance and diversity are concerning in their own right, and because of the key position of insects in the trophic hierarchy, they are an indicator of the decline of ecosystem functions more broadly. In the urban environment, human-driven changes in historical land use, land cover, hydrology, and pollutant loads are drivers of insect declines and ecosystem function declines more generally, although the relative contribution of each of these drivers has not been established. Engineered stormwater management systems are intended to mitigate environmental impacts in urban areas, and therefore their design and locations can be expected to affect insects. However, the impacts of these systems on insects have not been established and this gap in knowledge warrants further investigation. The remainder of this chapter discusses ways in which the choices of engineers and other urban design professionals can play a role in mitigating species declines.

2.4 Nutrient Enrichment May Constrain Biodiversity that can be Achieved in Bioretention Basins

One function of a stormwater control such as bioretention is to intercept, concentrate, and retain nitrogen and other nutrients in runoff from the surrounding land area. This nutrient retention function protects downstream aquatic ecosystems by preventing a portion of nutrients

in surface runoff from reaching them. A bioretention basin can be thought of as an engineered terrestrial ecosystem that is intentionally nutrient enriched by design, in contrast to a natural ecosystem where undesired nutrient enrichment typically indicates management objectives have not been met. While this nutrient enrichment is intentional, it may require acceptance of tradeoffs between localized diversity of the engineered terrestrial ecosystem (e.g., a bioretention basin and its urbanized watershed) and diversity of downstream aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems the engineered system is intended to protect. As documented in Section 2.7, available literature does not address implications of nutrient enrichment on *Lepidoptera* in bioretention basins. Rather, these implications can be inferred from literature discussing other types of ecosystems and from engineering literature on nitrogen dynamics in bioretention basins. It is reasonable to infer that because nutrient enrichment limits biodiversity in a range of ecosystems, it will also limit biodiversity in bioretention basins. If engineers wish to increase ecosystem function in design, it may be necessary to identify plant taxa that are able to persist and compete in a nutrient-enriched environment, while ensuring that these taxa are able to support a diverse range of insects, including *Lepidoptera*.

When an ecosystem, such as a bioretention basin, receives an excess of a particular resource such as a nutrient load, it tends to organize itself to make maximum use of that resource by prioritizing development of components able to process that excess. All other things being equal, a system with a regular inflow of excess nutrients, a eutrophic system, will tend to be less diverse because a few species that are best able to process the nutrients will out-compete others. Such a eutrophic ecosystem is able to organize itself to make maximum use of available energy and resources with a relatively simple structure (low diversity, low complexity, and low information content) (Giannetti et al., 2019; Odum, 1988). This state can be a desired outcome in

engineered systems because the localized low-diversity, high-productivity system is able to process wastes produced by human activity and thereby allow higher diversity, lower productivity systems to exist downstream (Beyers and Odum, 1993).

Bioretention basins receiving urban runoff can be expected to be nutrient-enriched ecosystems when compared to similarly sized soil-water-plant ecosystems not receiving urban runoff. The engineering literature on nutrients in urban stormwater provides evidence that bioretention basins receive large nutrient inputs on a unit-area basis relative to other ecosystems of similar size. Bioretention systems typically receive runoff from an urbanized drainage area that is on the order of 5 to 25 times the area of the bioretention basin surface footprint itself (e.g., Chaves et al., 2024). Nitrogen loads in urban stormwater are introduced by multiple sources. When mobilized by runoff, nitrogen loads from atmospheric deposition can explain a portion of elevated nutrient concentrations entering the bioretention surface footprint relative to concentrations deposited on an equivalent land area not receiving concentrated runoff (Yang and Toor, 2016). Other sources introduce nutrients to urban runoff including soil erosion, fertilizers, organic material from lawns and gardens, and pet waste (Jani et al., 2020). Sources, loads, and concentrations of pollutants in urban runoff have been extensively studied (e.g., Burton and Pitt, 2001).

Calculations presented in Table 2.1 demonstrate that nutrient enriched conditions should be expected in bioretention basins receiving urban surface runoff. These calculations are derived from data available in the engineering literature. Using an event mean concentration of 1.95 mg/L total nitrogen reported in the National Stormwater Quality Database (Pitt et al., 2018), if a bioretention facility were to receive approximately 1,000 mm of runoff in a year from a highly impervious drainage area (typical of southeast Pennsylvania) at a ratio of 5-15 units of drainage

area per unit of bioretention surface area, the total nitrogen load reaching the facility would be on the order of 100-300 kg N/yr per hectare of bioretention surface area (Table 2.1, right-most column). This load is within the order of magnitude intentionally applied to the land surface in intensive agricultural operations (e.g., Kurze et al., 2018), confirming that bioretention basins receiving urban runoff can be expected to be nutrient-enriched ecosystems relative to similarly sized soil-water-plant ecosystems experiencing minimal human impacts.

Table 2.1. Calculated Nitrogen Loads to the Surface Area of a Bioretention Basin

Drainage Area: Bioretention Surface Area (ratio, including bioretention surface area)	TKN (kg N/ha)	Ammonia (kg N/ha)	Nitrate- Nitrite (kg N/ha)	Total Nitrogen (calculated) (kg N/ha)
5	68.0	16.4	29.3	97.3
10	136	32.8	58.6	195
15	204	49.1	88.0	292

2.5 *Lepidoptera* Diversity as a Potential Proxy for Terrestrial Ecosystem Function in Bioretention Design

I recommend that engineers strongly consider potential *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity as quantitative design criteria indicative of terrestrial ecosystem functions in bioretention basins. I do not claim that *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity are the single best or only indicator that should be considered for all bioretention designs. Rather, if a design team has time and resources to consider only one ecological indicator, I suggest they give due consideration to *Lepidoptera* for the following reasons. First, the presence and diversity of *Lepidoptera* indicates that critical functions are occurring in the urban ecosystem, such as pollination and energy transfer from plants to higher trophic levels (Section 2.5.1). Second, *Lepidoptera* have been proposed by a range of authors as reliable indicators of fluctuations and trends in ecosystem functions such as changes in productivity and habitat provisioning (Sections

2.5.2 through 2.5.5). Finally, *Lepidoptera* have been studied extensively and relevant data sets are readily available to researchers and practitioners (Section 2.6).

2.5.1 Ecological Functions of *Lepidoptera*

Lepidoptera perform critical functions within ecosystems. As herbivores in the larval stage, they represent biomass linking primary producers (plants) to higher trophic levels including a majority of all birds, bats, and freshwater fish (Forister et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2021a). Narango et al. (2020) report that caterpillars transfer more energy from plants to other animals than all other herbivores combined. Illustrating the importance of this transfer, observed declines in insects and insectivorous birds have been closely linked (Tallamy and Shriver, 2021). As pollinators in the adult stage, *Lepidoptera* support the reproduction of flowering plants, and their declines have been linked to declines in overall flower and nectar plant abundance (Wallisdevries et al., 2012). While *Lepidoptera* themselves may be less economically important pollinators of agricultural crops than other insects such as bees and wasps, their loss may be an indicator of loss of pollinators more generally and therefore be predictive of economic impacts (Oliver et al., 2015). Ultimately, herbivory and pollination are linked functions because the same plant species can interact with both herbivores and pollinators (Sauve et al., 2015). Because *Lepidoptera* perform these critical functions within ecosystems, their abundance and diversity can serve as indicators of the ability of the ecosystem as a whole to provide desired functions.

2.5.2 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecosystem Condition

Invertebrates are considered by some researchers to be more powerful indicators of biodiversity than vertebrates or vascular plants because they have high abundance and diversity, are sensitive to perturbation, and play significant roles in ecosystems (Kazemi et al., 2009a). *Lepidoptera* in particular have been identified as suitable proxies for study of ecosystem functions and services because they are present in many different ecosystems and are considered

indicators for many groups of terrestrial insects which together make up a large fraction of biodiversity (Settele et al., 2008). In addition, species cover a range of productivity, their ecological functions are well known, and their short life cycles enable scientists to easily observe their responses to changing conditions (WallisDeVries and van Swaay, 2017). Observed changes in their abundance and diversity can be interpreted as proxies for the responses of ecosystems to fluctuations in environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, water availability) over shorter time scales, trends in environmental conditions due to climate change over longer time scales, land use change, habitat fragmentation, and nutrient enrichment. Land use change, climate change, and nitrogen deposition have been identified as key drivers of biodiversity loss in general (Klop et al., 2015).

2.5.3 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Environmental Change, including Temperature and Available Moisture

Projected impacts of climate change in temperate regions include warmer, wetter winters; hotter, dryer summers; and greater inter-annual hydrologic variability (Prudencio and Null, 2018). Butterflies are often regarded as benefiting from warmth, but extreme hot and dry periods can decrease populations through heat stress to larvae and impacts to host plants. For example, Oliver et al. (2015) documented the effect of an extreme drought event on butterfly populations in England in 1995. With an understanding of population collapse and recovery in response to this individual event, the authors were able to draw conclusions about long-term drought impacts to butterfly populations as events of the studied magnitude are projected to become more frequent in the future. For the six drought-sensitive butterfly species studied, the authors concluded that the probability of the species persisting until mid-century is “around zero” in the absence of emissions reductions (i.e., under CMIP5 scenario RCP8.5) and adaptation measures creating and preserving habitat with suitable environmental conditions (Oliver et al., 2015).

2.5.4 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Land Use Change, Habitat Fragmentation, and Climate Change Impacts

Ecological functions of species facing fragmentation and climate change depend on availability of functionally connected habitats and ability of the species to disperse quickly enough to track these changes (Stevens et al., 2010). Without conscious policy to limit negative impacts, urbanization results in the loss and fragmentation of preferred habitat for butterflies, including loss of resources such as larval host and nectar source plants (Fenoglio et al., 2021). The sizes, configurations, and locations of bioretention basins and other stormwater management features potentially can play a role in limiting both habitat loss and fragmentation. Butterfly species have varying abilities to adapt to fragmentation, and some are examples of edge species with dispersal rates sufficient for their populations to persist as a landscape becomes increasingly fragmented (Baguette et al., 2003). Butterflies are considered ideal for study of spatial habitat fragmentation because their specialization makes their habitats easy to map in heterogenous landscapes and because their life history characteristics are well documented. In fact, dispersal is best documented in butterflies out of all animal groups (Baguette and Mennechez, 2004; Stevens et al., 2010).

Taking action to limit habitat fragmentation is a potential strategy to help organisms adapt to climate change. For example, in their projection of butterfly population responses to heat and drought events, Oliver et al. (2015) considered the extent to which mitigating habitat loss and fragmentation may be able to offset climate change impacts. For the six drought-sensitive butterfly species studied by Oliver et al. (2015), the authors determined that measures to reduce habitat loss and fragmentation could increase the probability of local persistence by mid-century from near zero to 6-42% under CMIP5 scenario RCP8.5. However, they concluded that

emissions reductions would also be needed to increase the probability of persistence to greater than 50%.

2.5.5 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecological Response to Nutrient Enrichment

There is no literature available specifically addressing nutrient enrichment, bioretention basins, and *Lepidoptera* (as discussed in Section 2.7). One can infer some potential effects of nutrient enrichment on *Lepidoptera* in bioretention basins by reviewing literature describing impacts on *Lepidoptera* in other ecosystems. Several authors provide evidence that *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity are useful indicators of nutrient enrichment impacts in ecosystems (Bobbink et al., 2010; Klop et al., 2015; Pöyry et al., 2017; WallisDeVries and Swaay, 2017). The principle of reduced diversity in nutrient-enriched environments begins in the soil (Poyry et al., 2017) before propagating upward through trophic levels to plants (Bobbink et al., 2010) and then to insect herbivores (Klop et al., 2015; Poyry et al., 2017; WallisDeVries and van Swaay, 2017). Interactions between nitrogen and butterfly and moth species in engineered stormwater control measures specifically have not been studied. However, a number of studies have examined the impacts of agricultural and atmospheric deposition of reactive nitrogen on plant and insect communities in Europe, and some parallels can be drawn regarding the introduction of nitrogen in stormwater to engineered ecosystems. Pöyry et al. (2017) studied the movement of nitrogen from atmospheric deposition on soil to plants and then to 1,064 northern European butterfly and moth species. Nitrogen content in plant leaves is thought to be a limiting factor for the growth of insect herbivores. The authors found that nitrogen enrichment in the soil reduces plant, butterfly, and moth diversity by favoring species adapted to nitrogen-rich environments (Pöyry et al., 2017). Specific *Lepidoptera* traits were found to predict success of dominant butterflies and moths, including a positive relationship between foliar nitrogen content and insect body size, the ability to disperse widely, multivoltinism (producing multiple broods per breeding

season), and being either dietary generalists or specialists in consumption of plants that benefit from higher-nitrogen conditions. Similarly, WallisDeVries and van Swaay (2017) and Klop et al. (2015) report that by favoring some plant species over others, nitrogen deposition in natural ecosystems reduces overall plant diversity and may increase insect biomass while decreasing insect diversity as measured by species richness. One identified mechanism by which nutrient enrichment decreases *Lepidoptera* diversity is micro-climatic cooling in the spring, when a dense plant canopy can prevent temperature-sensitive caterpillars from absorbing sufficient solar radiation and reaching optimal body temperatures (Klop et al., 2015). The available literature makes a strong case that *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity are useful indicators of how mass and energy flows in ecosystems react to nutrient enrichment and other environmental changes. Section 2.6 will discuss a range of existing data that can help researchers quantify these ecosystem functions using *Lepidoptera*.

2.6 Available and Relevant Data for Analysis of *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecosystem Functions

The literature does not provide evidence or examples directly linking *Lepidoptera* to ecosystem functions in bioretention basins (Figure 2.1). In Section 8, I will propose a research agenda to begin developing this data. However, a substantial amount of relevant information is available on plants recommended for bioretention, on *Lepidoptera* larval host plants and habitat preferences, and on *Lepidoptera* dispersal. Conditions affecting plants and *Lepidoptera* can in turn be related to more general information on environmental conditions such as land use and land cover, hydrology, and water quality. This information exists in databases maintained by engineering practitioners, agricultural scientists, entomologists, spatial analysts, and other specialists. However, data on these topics, collected and maintained by these separate disciplines, has never before been connected to answer the research questions posed in this study in an urban

stormwater management context. Types of relevant data that can be connected to improve bioretention design are summarized in Table 2.2. Linking plant information in engineering bioretention design manuals to horticultural information provided by agricultural extension services also can be useful.

Recommendations on plants suitable for bioretention are available in design manuals and guidelines produced by state and municipal agencies and from stormwater utilities. The information in these manuals can be combined with information available in U.S. federal government databases such as the National Wetland Plant List (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 2020) and USDA PLANTS (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022) database, to provide extensive information on the geographic occurrence and environmental tolerance ranges of plants. Links between *Lepidoptera* and the presence of specific larval host plants that support them are well documented and accessible in public databases (Narango et al., 2020; Robinson et al., 2023). The HOSTS database combines information on caterpillar host plants from approximately 1,600 published and manuscript sources covering approximately 22,000 *Lepidoptera* species internationally, with locations identified at the country level (Robinson et al., 2023). Narango et al. (2020) used over 3,600 published sources, including HOSTS and the Biota of North America Program (Kartesz, 2015), to characterize all plant genera known to occur and all *Lepidoptera* species known to feed on at least one of the plant species in 83 counties across the United States. For Lancaster County, Pennsylvania, for example, the data set indicates 521 plant genera and 2,070 *Lepidoptera* taxa present in the county. Table 2.3 lists ten examples of bioretention plants serving as host plants for a range of *Lepidoptera* species (Narango, 2020). I chose these examples to illustrate the wide range in the number of *Lepidoptera* species supported by different native plants, from more than 500 to 0.

Data on *Lepidoptera* habitat and resource preferences is also available. The related concepts of “habitat” and “resource patch” can be distinguished by spatial scale. A resource patch such as a concentration of larval host plants can be delineated at the localized spatial scale, while habitat can be defined as the aggregation of all resources at the landscape or regional scale which collectively support an organism throughout its life cycle (Baguette and Mennechez, 2004). Characterizing habitat at the landscape scale is useful because dispersal processes operate and are well documented at this scale (Stevens et al., 2010). Detailed information on larval host plants at the localized scale is not often available in urban environments, while information on land cover is widely available and can be linked logically to the habitat concept. For *Lepidoptera*, Butterflies and Moths of North America (2023) is one source describing habitat preferences. With this information, researchers can make qualitative links between spatially explicit land use/land cover information and the potential presence of specific butterfly and moth species in the landscape. The National Land Cover Database (Dewitz, 2024) provides 30 m resolution land cover information throughout the United States, and more detailed information often is available from state, municipal and regional planning agencies and from researchers. For example, high-resolution land cover information for the Chesapeake Bay and Delaware Bay watersheds in the U.S. Mid-Atlantic region is available from the University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory (2016).

Table 2.2. Types and Example Sources of Readily Available Data that can be Connected to Improve Bioretention Design

Data Type	Example Sources
Plants suitable for bioretention	Center for Watershed Protection and Maryland Department of the Environment, 2009; Credit Valley Conservation Authority, 2010; Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District, 2012; Philadelphia Water Department, 2020; Prince George's County, 2007; Shaw and Schmidt, 2003
Plant characteristics and geographic occurrence	National Wetland Plant List, 2020; USDA PLANTS database; Biota of North America Program (Kartesz, 2015); TRY database
<i>Lepidoptera</i> larval host plants	Narango et al., 2020; Robinson et al., 2023
<i>Lepidoptera</i> characteristics and habitat preferences	Butterflies and Moths of North America, 2023
<i>Lepidoptera</i> dispersal	Stevens et al., 2010
<i>Lepidoptera</i> population trends	NatureServe, 2023; Pelton et al., 2019; UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme, 2021; Wallis de Vries et al., 2012; Wepprich, 2019
<i>Lepidoptera</i> geographic occurrence	Global Biodiversity Information Facility; iNaturalist; museum collections
Land cover	National Land Cover Database; University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory, 2016
Hydrography	National Hydrography Database; National Wetlands Inventory
Bioretention water quantity and quality	International Stormwater BMP Database
Untreated stormwater quality	Nationwide Urban Runoff Program; National Stormwater Quality Database

Table 2.3. Ten Example Bioretention Plant Species Serving as *Lepidoptera* Larval Hosts in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania (Derived from Narango, 2020)

Host Plant Scientific Name	Host Plant Genus	Host Plant Common Name	<i>Lepidoptera</i> Species Supported
<i>Quercus bicolor</i>	Quercus	swamp white oak	511
<i>Viburnum lentago</i>	Viburnum	Nannyberry	114
<i>Ilex verticillata</i>	Ilex	common winterberry	43
<i>Panicum virgatum</i>	Panicum	Switchgrass	25
<i>Iris versicolor</i>	Iris	harlequin blueflag	14
<i>Asclepias incarnata</i>	Asclepias	swamp milkweed	13
<i>Lilium superbum</i>	Lilium	turk's-cap lily	9
<i>Onoclea sensibilis</i>	Onoclea	sensitive fern	5
<i>Oclemena nemoralis</i>	Oclemena	bog aster	1
<i>Echinacea purpurea</i>	Echinacea	eastern purple coneflower	0

Ecologists have published information classifying butterfly species based on ecological characteristics or processes they participate in. These characteristics can be related to the

likelihood of a particular species persisting in a given location under a given set of environmental conditions or a given change in environmental conditions, such as those brought about when a bioretention basin is added to the landscape. A simple approach to classifying species describes them as specialists or generalists in terms of habitat and food source preferences (Townsend et al., 2008). In an example of a more elaborate classification, WallisDeVries (2014) provided data on characteristics of 145 butterfly species from Northwestern Europe, grouping 16 characteristics into four components: spatial distribution and reproductive capacity (area occupied, tendency to range outside preferred habitat, individual size, potential egg production), climate conditions (moisture and temperature tolerance), generation time (growth rate of larvae, number of broods per year, overwintering ability, ability to enter diapause or a suspended developmental state), and resource specialization (territorial behavior, food and nectar plant specialization, preferred location for egg laying). For example, *Lepidoptera* that co-evolved with plants under nitrogen-limited conditions will tend to have slower larval growth rates, fewer generations per year, and less flexibility in overwintering and diapause, putting them at a disadvantage in a higher-nitrogen environment. Species with the opposite set of functional traits (e.g., faster larval growth rates) will have a competitive advantage (WallisDeVries, 2014).

Extensive data sets on butterfly spatial occurrence are readily available. Extensive, long-term data sets have been collected in Europe including the UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme (2021) and the Dutch Butterfly Monitoring Scheme (Wallisdevries et al., 2012). In recent years, there have been substantial advances in the organization and accessibility of high-quality occurrence data in repositories such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, a portal aggregating multiple databases including iNaturalist (e.g., “Pennsylvania Butterfly Species

Occurrence Data Set”, 2023). Butterflies are charismatic, and because they are popular with the public, a large body of occurrence data is readily available from citizen scientists. With appropriate consideration of uncertainty, this data can supplement high quality data collected by scientists under controlled conditions, such as occurrence data documented in museum collections.

Information on bioretention water quality and quantity and on the characteristics of urban stormwater allows engineers to evaluate pollutant loads entering and leaving bioretention basins, including nitrogen loads. The Nationwide Urban Runoff Program first provided high-quality research data on pollutant loads in untreated urban stormwater in the United States, and more recently the National Stormwater Quality Database has greatly expanded this evidence by incorporating sample results submitted as part of regulatory permitting requirements. The International Stormwater BMP Database is a repository for data on concentrations of nitrogen and other constituents leaving bioretention basins through surface flow. From these large data sets, engineers can estimate the proportion of pollutant loads that are flowing through bioretention basins by surface pathways. Relevant to the goals of the current study, engineers can now estimate the proportion of nitrogen reaching groundwater, accumulating in bioretention soil, and being assimilated into plant tissues where it is ultimately available to insect herbivores. Combining these estimates with the ecological data sets mentioned throughout Section 6, it is possible to evaluate potential tradeoffs between ecosystem functional objectives (for example, maximizing *Lepidoptera* diversity) and traditional engineering objectives such as reducing nitrogen loads reaching downstream aquatic ecosystems.

2.7 Gaps in the Engineering Literature on Bioretention and *Lepidoptera*

2.7.1 Literature Review Phase 1: Results of a Structured Literature Search on *Lepidoptera* and Bioretention Basins Illustrating a Gap in the Literature

To determine whether the combination of *Lepidoptera* and stormwater bioretention basins has been studied in the past, a systematic keyword-based literature review was conducted in line with the workflow recommended by the PRISMA 2020 protocol (Page et al., 2021). For this first phase of the literature review, Figure 2.1 lists the research database queried and all search terms employed. Some records matching search terms were excluded for one or more of three reasons. First, some records were clearly irrelevant and returned only because the name of an author contained a search string. Second, some records were excluded because the only systems discussed were dissimilar to bioretention basins (e.g., a pollinator garden with no stormwater inflow). Third, many records were excluded because they focused exclusively on agricultural pests, invasive species, or pesticides and were otherwise irrelevant to the topic of *Lepidoptera* and bioretention basins. The keyword search identified 62 unique records mentioning keywords related to butterflies or moths in engineered stormwater control measures or constructed wetlands. After examination of these records, only four were determined to be relevant to the current research topic (Figure 2.1). Bolques et al. (2010) and McCrary and Buechter (2017) are conference papers making qualitative statements without providing supporting evidence. Kim (2018) reports results of a field survey of plants and animals (including three species of *Lepidoptera*) following installation of a rain garden in Illinois, USA. Kazemi et al. (2009a) provides quantitative results and analysis for insects in stormwater bioswales in Melbourne, Australia. The study focuses on ground-dwelling insects but does include some limited data on the occurrence of *Lepidoptera*. In conclusion, this first phase of the literature review, the structured keyword search phase, revealed a near-total gap in literature presenting information

relevant to the topic of promoting *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity in bioretention design (Figure 2.1). Only one published study (Kazemi et al., 2009a) contained quantitative information relevant to the topic. After identifying this gap, two additional literature review phases were conducted using broader methodology as discussed in Sections 2.7.2 and 2.7.3.

Figure 2.1. Results of Systematic Review of Web of Science Database Conducted on May 4, 2024.

2.7.2 Literature Review Phase 2: Studies of Terrestrial Arthropods in the Melbourne Area by Kazemi et al. (2009-2011) Including Generalized Habitat Design Recommendations

The second and third phases of the literature review employed more traditional methods of literature review rather than the structured keyword search methods discussed in Section 2.7.1. In these phases, additional relevant publications were identified through references cited in publications identified during the first phase of the literature review (Figure 2.1), through a forward citation database (Google Scholar), and through recommendations of subject matter experts. In addition to Kazemi et al. (2009a), the second phase of the literature review identified two additional studies published by the same research group, Kazemi et al. (2009b) and Kazemi

et al. (2011). While these three studies did not focus on *Lepidoptera*, they provided data and recommendations on the intersection of bioretention-type stormwater control design and presence of a range of terrestrial arthropods, including a small number of *Lepidoptera*. While these studies are geographically limited and it has not been established whether their findings are broadly applicable, I summarize their findings below as they represent the most relevant information available in the very limited literature on insects in bioretention basins.

The first of the three related studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2009a) identified the presence and depth of leaf litter as an important factor in explaining arthropod biodiversity in bioretention compared to lawn areas used as controls and suggested that leaf litter not be removed during maintenance. In general, Kazemi et al. (2009a) hypothesized that the lesser degree of human disturbance in bioretention basins compared to lawns may partially explain biodiversity differences. They concluded that frequent disturbance such as mowing is likely associated with decreased biodiversity. The study identified the presence of gravel in bioretention basins as a positive factor for biodiversity. Drawing on past studies of natural ecosystems, they hypothesized that presence of rocks and stones may provide habitat heterogeneity, shelter, and suitable microhabitats for some invertebrates. The second of the three studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2009b) suggested that additional factors explaining greater invertebrate biodiversity in bioretention systems include a larger number of plant taxa and sizes and shapes that create larger interior habitats to provide shelter from the surrounding landscape.

The third of the three studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2011) studied the importance of 11 habitat factors influencing invertebrate biodiversity in nine bioswales and nine corresponding “gardenbed-like” or “lawn-like” sites. They concluded that important factors correlated to greater invertebrate diversity included mid-stratum vegetation (bushes, shrubs) coverage, number of

flowering plants, pH, and slope characteristics. The importance of shrubs is consistent with findings by other researchers including Noemí Mazía et al. (2006) who reported that mid-stratum vegetation can act as a keystone structure sheltering invertebrates. Flowering plants support species depending on nectar. Finally, the authors found a relationship between greater lateral slope (from the edge to middle of the system) and measured invertebrate diversity. They suggested that the effect of slope on water ponding and soil moisture creates a range of stable microclimates within the bioswale which species are able to take advantage of. They further suggested that these stable microclimates may increase resilience of species to climate extremes prevailing in the surrounding landscape outside the bioswale, including extreme solar radiation, wind, and evaporation. These three studies are the only ones available that provide empirical evidence specific to design of bioretention basins to support invertebrates. They are briefly referenced in Pille and Säumel (2021), one of four broad review and synthesis papers that will be discussed in Section 2.7.3.

2.7.3 Literature Review Phase 3: Relevant Content in Recent Broad Review and Synthesis Studies on Green Stormwater Infrastructure and Urban Ecosystems

To further confirm that the combined study of *Lepidoptera* and bioretention has not been reported in the literature, four recent reviews and one published data set were examined, each intended to synthesize a broad range of literature on urban green infrastructure and ecosystem functions or services (Table 2.4). These review and synthesis publications were identified through references cited in publications identified during the first two phases of the literature review (described in Sections 2.7.1 and 2.7.2), through a forward citation database (Google Scholar), and through recommendations of subject matter experts. Prudencio and Null (2018) and Pille and Säumel (2021) focused specifically on stormwater control measures, while Filazzola et al. (2019) and a related data set (Filazzola et al., 2018) surveyed a wider range of

urban green infrastructure including some stormwater control measures. Veerkamp et al. (2021) reviewed a broad range of urban green infrastructure types and a selected set of ecosystem services including stormwater regulation and pollination. Because these studies are broad, not all information is directly relevant to *Lepidoptera* and bioretention basins. Table 2.4 illustrates the proportion of relevant information by quantifying the total number of studies included in each review and synthesis publication, the number referring both to urban stormwater control facilities (of any type) and to habitat, the number referring both to bioretention and to insect habitat, and the number referring both to bioretention and to *Lepidoptera*. As these criteria are narrowed from left to right in Table 2.4, the number of relevant studies decreases until in the right-most column of the table, the three relevant studies represented are the three studies already discussed in Section 2.7.2. Of the four review and synthesis papers and one related data set, only Pille and Säumel (2021) mentioned studies covering both *Lepidoptera* and bioretention. The analysis of these review and synthesis studies therefore confirms the earlier finding that the existing peer reviewed literature on *Lepidoptera* and bioretention represents a gap other than these three studies.

Table 2.4. Recent Review and Synthesis Studies of Green Infrastructure, Stormwater Control Measures, Biodiversity, and Insects

Review	SCM Terms Included ¹	Number of Studies Reviewed			
		Total	Referring to SCMs and Habitat ²	Referring to Bioretention and Insect Habitat ³	Referring to Bioretention and <i>Lepidoptera</i>
Pille and Saumel, 2021	swales, ponds, rain gardens, green roofs, green walls, permeable pavement	830	140	3	3
Filazzola et al., 2018	bioswales, green roofs, retention ponds	85	25	4	0
Filazzola et al., 2019	green roofs, wetland detention basins, vegetated roadsides/bioswales	1,883	59	0	0
Prudencio and Null, 2018	stormwater harvesting, stormwater capture, green roofs, basins, wells, rain barrels, wetlands, ponds, permeable pavement, permeable surfaces, pervious pavement, pervious surfaces, rain gardens, tree boxes, swales, r-tanks, underground vaults	170	48	0	0
Veerkamp et al., 2021	green roofs, rain gardens, vegetated swales, permeable surfaces, constructed wetlands, ponds	850	N/A	N/A	N/A

N/A indicates that the structure of Veerkamp et al. 2021 does not allow categorization of the studies reviewed in the same way as the other review and synthesis papers.

¹Includes references to urban stormwater control measures (SCMs).

²Includes references to urban SCMs and habitat or biodiversity.

³Includes references to surface vegetated SCMs classified as bioretention or pseudonyms. Includes references to habitat or biodiversity. Includes references to terrestrial insects, arthropods, invertebrates, or pollinators. Papers referring only to aquatic species or mosquitoes are excluded.

While these review and synthesis studies did not identify any additional studies covering both bioretention and *Lepidoptera*, they drew some conclusions relevant to the design of stormwater control measures for the terrestrial ecological functions of interest. For example, the review and synthesis studies suggest that habitat and biodiversity implications of stormwater control measures have been underrepresented in the research literature relative to studies of other types of urban green infrastructure. Filazzola et al. (2019) performed a meta-analysis of

published data on a range of urban green infrastructure in relation to biodiversity, covering wetland detention basins and lumping together vegetated roadsides and bioswales. The authors concluded that “[t]he effects of GI [green infrastructure] on biodiversity have been rarely quantified.” Prudencio and Null (2018) suggested that “[g]reen stormwater infrastructure could focus on biodiversity as an umbrella goal for resiliency of several ecosystem services in the urban setting.” They found that many papers referred to ecosystem services but less than 40% quantified them. Veerkamp et al. (2021), considering pollination as a proxy for biodiversity, concurred that most studies to date have focused on non-stormwater features such as parks and gardens.

A common conclusion of the review articles is that the literature on habitat and stormwater control measures most comprehensively reports on green roofs and on stormwater management ponds and related structures such as retention basins with permanent pools. Pille and Säumel (2021) focused specifically on the intersection of stormwater control measures, habitat, and biodiversity. The authors found that 85% of the studies screened provided information for ponds and green roofs, while other stormwater control measures including bioretention were under-represented.

An additional trend identified by the review articles is that ecosystem functions and services are often mentioned in the literature in qualitative terms or in calls for further research, but these are rarely quantified. Butterflies, insects, and pollinators are often mentioned in papers in qualitative terms. Other types of insects have been quantitatively studied. For example, the search revealed studies specific to dragonflies and damselflies in stormwater ponds (Perron and Pick, 2020) and studies specific to mosquitoes (e.g., Hanford et al., 2019).

Filazzola et al. (2019) examined data from 33 published studies pairing green roofs, green walls, wetland detention basins, vegetated roadsides/bioswales, and yards/gardens with conventional infrastructure counterparts and natural systems. The authors concluded that some types of green infrastructure (green roofs and roadside bioswales but not wetland detention basins or urban gardens) were found to improve biodiversity over conventional counterparts in the urban environment, and in some cases were comparable to natural (non-engineered) ecosystems. The authors acknowledged that the non-engineered ecosystems studied tended to be urban remnants of larger ecosystems that existed historically and may have retained less function than less urban, less human-impacted counterparts. The paper recommended further research with experimental design frameworks that include negative controls (conventionally designed urban infrastructure), positive controls, (“natural” or non-engineered ecosystems), replication, and sufficient sample sizes to draw formal statistical inferences.

The review and synthesis articles identify a trend in the literature calling for further research on the role stormwater management measures have in fostering habitat connectivity at the landscape scale. For example, Pille and Säumel (2021) recommended increasing the number and density of stormwater control measures designed specifically to support biodiversity to increase the overall quality and connectivity of urban green infrastructure. They also recommend focusing these efforts specifically on identified corridors for animal movement. A frequent recommendation for further study found is to consider not only the local scale of individual stormwater or green infrastructure facilities, but also their larger landscape context including the distribution of resources spatially and the ability of organisms to move and disperse between habitat areas (e.g., Kremen et al., 2007). Researchers (e.g., McDermott et al., 2017) also suggest that mitigating habitat fragmentation effects may be a way to reduce downward pressure on

species populations caused by gradual increases in mean temperature and by increases in the frequency and severity of extreme climate events. The review and synthesis studies identify recent research on green roofs, insects, and habitat connectivity at a landscape scale in urban areas (Brenneisen, 2006; Gonsalves et al., 2022; Wooster et al., 2022). Some research methods employed in these studies may be transferrable to bioretention studies.

Table 2.5 summarizes planning, design, and maintenance recommendations found in existing literature. Recommendations include increasing the number and density of bioretention basins designed to enhance biodiversity within the landscape, siting basins to reduce landscape-scale fragmentation and enhance animal movement, incorporating physical features that create heterogeneous habitat and moisture conditions within basins, maximizing plant diversity and flowering plants, and minimizing human disturbance. Many of these recommendations are general and qualitative in nature, and they likely exhibit geographic bias since they are derived from a small set of studies. In Section 2.8, I propose a research agenda to build on this limited base of existing knowledge.

Table 2.5. Summary of Planning and Design Recommendations in the Literature to Provide Habitat and Increase Biodiversity of Insects in Bioretention Basins

Source	Category	Recommendation
Pille and Saumel, 2021	Planning/Siting	Increase number and density of stormwater controls designed to enhance biodiversity.
Kremen et al., 2007; Pille and Saumel, 2021	Planning/Siting	Place stormwater controls designed to enhance biodiversity within identified animal movement corridors.
McDermott et al., 2017	Planning/Siting	Place stormwater controls to help mitigate habitat fragmentation at the landscape scale.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Design	Incorporate gravel, rocks, and stones.
Kazemi et al., 2009b, 2011; Noemi Mazia, 2006	Design	Maximize the number of plant taxa and flowering plants. Include mid-stratum vegetation (bushes, shrubs).
Kazemi et al., 2009b	Design	Configure size and shape to maximize interior habitat.
Kazemi et al., 2011	Design	Configure slope to create a gradient of moisture conditions.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Maintenance	Do not remove leaf litter.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Maintenance	Minimize mowing and other forms of disturbance.

2.8 Conclusions: An Agenda for Engineering Research and Action

I have suggested a relatively simple framework for improving ecological outcomes of engineering designs based on plant choice and *Lepidoptera* larvae supported by those plants. Specifically, designers can choose plant species that are both suitable for environmental conditions and that serve as larval hosts for a diversity of *Lepidoptera* species. A simple metric that can be maximized in design is the total number of *Lepidoptera* species reported in the literature (e.g., Narango, 2020; Robinson et al., 2023) to be supported by the specific plant taxa selected in the relevant geographic region. Since terrestrial ecosystem function has in most cases not been considered at all in typical engineering bioretention design practice, I believe simply choosing larval host plants for *Lepidoptera* that are suitable for environmental conditions will immediately improve outcomes compared to current practice.

I acknowledge that this proposed approach does have a number of limitations including a current lack of evidence directly linking *Lepidoptera* and bioretention basins, geographic bias, and the potential difficulty of prioritizing ecological objectives in multiple-objective engineering practice. My proposed approach does not consider all the complex temporal and spatial ecosystem dynamics that occur in bioretention basins. Development of additional metrics is a recommendation for future research as discussed throughout this section. There are many more questions that can be explored at the intersection of bioretention engineering and ecology. Drawing from this detailed literature review, I propose a series of questions for future research. While further research will certainly improve scientific understanding, an overarching question is whether considering additional ecological complexity within bioretention basins will improve engineering design decisions leading to more desirable outcomes. For new research to improve ecosystem functional outcomes of bioretention designs, research findings must inform bioretention engineering practice. This section therefore concludes with some ideas for applying

research outcomes to the professional practice of bioretention design. Table 2.6 summarizes the recommendations for future research and applications to professional practice. These recommendations are discussed in detail throughout the remainder of Section 2.8.

Table 2.6. Recommendations for Future Research and Applications to Professional Practice

Section	Category	Topic	Question or Recommendation
2.8.1.1	Future Research	Tradeoffs	Does meeting water regulation and pollutant load objectives place limits on ecological functions that can be achieved in and around bioretention basins?
2.8.1.2	Future Research	Microclimates	Can attention to microclimates in design improve ecosystem functions?
2.8.1.3	Future Research	Temporal Dynamics	Is detailed consideration of ecosystem temporal dynamics necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
2.8.1.4	Future Research	Stochastic Processes	Is detailed consideration of stochastic processes affecting species occurrence necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
2.8.1.5	Future Research	Spatiotemporal Dynamics	Is detailed consideration of dispersal, migration, and population dynamics in both space and time necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
2.8.1.6	Future Research	Climate Change	Will climate change degrade ecosystem functions in and around bioretention basins, and can design choices mitigate this degradation?
2.8.1.7	Future Research	Pollination	Can the presence of <i>Lepidoptera</i> host plants serve as an effective proxy for pollination?
2.8.1.8	Future Research	Connectivity	Can bioretention basins serve as part of a larger green infrastructure network to create an urbanized landscape with improved terrestrial ecological functions?
2.8.1.9	Future Research	Watershed Scale	Is a similar scale of bioretention implementation needed to achieve both hydrologic and ecological objectives?
2.8.1.10	Future Research	Ecosystem Services	Does valuing ecosystem functions in financial units improve design decisions and outcomes?
2.8.2.1	Application	Decision Support Tools	Use evidence produced by research to inform decision support tools for bioretention planners and designers, such as plant selection guides.
2.8.2.2	Application	Design Guidelines	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention design guidelines used in professional practice, including guidance on plant selection and habitat design.
2.8.2.3	Application	Standard Plans, Details, Specifications	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention plans, details, and technical specifications used in professional practice.
2.8.2.4	Application	Maintenance Protocols	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention maintenance protocols.
2.8.2.5	Application	Model Codes and Ordinances	Use evidence produced by research to inform codes governing land use and design on private property.
2.8.2.6	Application	Other Policy Options	Consider how evidence produced by research can inform innovative policy options to support urban ecosystem functions and biodiversity.

2.8.1 Key Research Questions

2.8.1.1 Do the hydrologic and biogeochemical conditions necessary to meet traditional engineering performance objectives place limits on habitat provision, biodiversity, and pollination that can be achieved in and around bioretention basins? Put another way, are tradeoffs required between traditional engineering performance objectives and terrestrial ecosystem objectives? Are there specific design choices that can minimize these tradeoffs?

While design professionals may be interested in adding terrestrial ecosystem objectives such as habitat provision to their design frameworks, most projects will continue to have minimum requirements for traditional criteria including peak outflow rate control, groundwater recharge, and export of pollutants to downstream aquatic ecosystems. Many of these design guidelines and regulatory requirements are aimed at protection of human life, property, and integrity of downstream aquatic ecosystems. Meeting these minimum legal requirements typically is not negotiable, and project stakeholders may wish to exceed minimum requirements in some situations. Therefore, a useful outcome of future research will be to better describe and quantify any tradeoffs between maximization of terrestrial ecosystem functions and these traditional water resource engineering objectives. For example, a hypothesis that can be explored by a researcher is whether an increase in the number of *Lepidoptera* species supported across a range of bioretention designs is statistically related to a decrease in the volume of groundwater recharge occurring in the basins over a period of time. This example hypothesis could be explored through numerical simulations of a number of alternative basin designs, through field investigations of implemented systems that differ in configuration, or through a combined simulation and field approach. This chapter has argued that the mix of plants present in a bioretention basin, particularly larval host plants for *Lepidoptera*, is a suitable indicator of potential biodiversity and ecosystem function that can develop in the basin. If critical larval host plants are not able to survive in the basin, this may place an upper limit on potential ecosystem function. Design choices including bioretention system surface area, maximum surface ponding

volume, and engineered soil depth govern the hydroperiod and time pattern of soil moisture in bioretention systems. These patterns place bounds on the range of plants that can be grown in a given system.

Concentrated resource inputs such as nutrients have been shown to result in lower-diversity ecosystems, and a goal of engineered bioretention systems is to intercept and process these excess resources before they reach downstream aquatic ecosystems. Eutrophic conditions in ecosystems have been shown to reduce biodiversity in the soil, among plants, and upward through the food chain to herbivores including *Lepidoptera*. If keystone larval host plants are unable to survive or compete in the nutrient-rich conditions expected in bioretention basins, it is reasonable to expect that this may result in unavoidable tradeoffs between nutrient processing and biodiversity support functions of the systems. An example hypothesis is whether the mass of nutrients retained by a range of bioretention designs is statistically related to the maximum number of *Lepidoptera* species that can be supported by the designs.

The range of plants that can persist in a bioretention basin may be limited by additional factors such as the presence of deicing salts, other toxins, or development and persistence of low-oxygen conditions if unexpected soil or hydraulic conditions lead to prolonged saturation. Further research can explore whether plants that can persist in these conditions are able to also provide habitat, support herbivores, and support pollinators.

2.8.1.2 Can attention to microclimates in design improve ecosystem functions?

Literature sources reviewed suggest that design choices can intentionally create microclimates creating a variety of environmental conditions within a bioretention basin, and that this variety in microclimates can then support greater biodiversity. Examples of these design choices include incorporating a variety of plant sizes (grasses, shrubs, trees); incorporating a variety of flowering plants; including gravel, rocks, and stones; creating larger interior habitats to

provide shelter from extremes of wind, temperature, and solar radiation in the surrounding landscape; creating lateral slopes (from the edge to center of the basin) that provide a gradient of soil moisture conditions; and minimizing disturbance as much as practical to leave leaf litter in place. Empirical testing of these hypotheses can help inform future designs.

2.8.1.3 Is detailed understanding and consideration of ecosystem temporal dynamics necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?

The discussion in this chapter to this point has largely neglected temporal dynamics of urban ecosystems. Plant succession can occur over short time scales, particularly in newly established or disturbed ecosystems like bioretention basins. To some extent, changes in engineered ecosystems such as bioretention basins can be managed by standardized operation and maintenance activities. These activities may include removal of undesirable plant species and replanting or supplementing of desirable ones. Nonetheless, competition and succession processes can be expected to establish trends in the species assemblage present in a given system over time. Arrival and spread of invasive species is another temporal process that will affect species assemblage. Episodic extreme heat, cold, wet weather, drought, and human intervention can further favor species that are more resistant and resilient to disturbances.

Seasonal dynamics are additional examples of temporal dynamics that potentially can be considered in design. One example of a seasonal dynamic is the timing of blooms serving as nectar sources for different species of pollinators over the course of a year. Another example is the timing of insect overwintering relative to increases in heat, light, and predation in the spring (e.g., Stevens et al., 2018). Climate change may tend to result in mismatches between historical seasonal patterns and the timing of animal and plant activity, termed phenological asynchrony. These mismatches may put downward pressure on the populations of some species (Donoso et al., 2016). A final example is the timing of deicing chemical application in colder urbanized

regions, the timing of spring rainfall that tends to flush these substances from soil into groundwater and surface water, and the beginning of the spring growing season for plant species that are sensitive to these chemicals (e.g., Shetty et al., 2020).

2.8.1.4 Is it necessary to account for the probability of dispersal and animal movement, or is a framework based on theoretical carrying capacity sufficient to achieve design outcomes?

The concepts presented in this chapter consider the theoretical carrying capacity of ecosystems under a given set of physical conditions. Chance also plays a role in determining whether organisms that can be supported by the physical conditions in a given basin are actually present in a given place and time. Interdisciplinary collaboration with biologists can design and execute experimental designs to confirm the validity of predictions made on the basis of theoretical carrying capacity. Researchers have suggested that field experimental designs should incorporate positive controls (analogous ecosystems with minimal human disturbance), negative controls (“business as usual” urban designs), replication, and sufficient sample sizes to support formal statistical inferences. A practical objective of this research can be to determine whether accounting for the empirical presence of organisms would change the optimal decisions of design professionals.

2.8.1.5 To what extent is it necessary to consider the complexities of Lepidopteran dispersal processes, migration, and population dynamics in both space and time in order to inform successful design decisions?

Ultimately, spatial habitat connectivity is linked to the temporal processes of organism arrival, dispersal, localized extinction, and other population dynamics. The abundance and distribution of migratory species, such as the monarch butterfly, depend on processes playing out over even larger spatial scales. Interdisciplinary research can explore whether accounting for these dynamics in the engineering design process would improve design decision making or lead

to more desirable design outcomes that encourage butterfly usage. Some initial approaches that may be considered are discussed in Chapter 6.

2.8.1.6 Will climate change further decrease maximum terrestrial ecosystem function that can be achieved in and around bioretention basins? If so, can specific design decisions increase climate change resilience of the bioretention systems and surrounding ecosystems?

An important area of research will be to determine whether conclusions about any tradeoffs between water management, habitat provision and support for greater biodiversity will continue to hold as climate change modifies environmental conditions, potentially moving them outside the range favored by plants and animals currently inhabiting a given geographic area. Climate change also is expected to affect local environmental conditions by modifying the frequency, magnitude, and duration of precipitation and dry periods, leading to changes in the frequency distribution of inundation and soil moisture within the root zone of plants. Climate change is affecting and will continue to affect the frequency of extreme events including heat, cold, storms, fires, and floods. These modified conditions may affect the ability of preferred larval host and nectar source plants to persist, indirectly affecting *Lepidoptera* and organisms at higher trophic levels. Modified conditions such as higher temperatures also may affect *Lepidoptera*, birds, and other species directly. Gradual trends introduced by climate change can further affect the outcome of competition and succession processes over time. It may be necessary to choose plants able to tolerate longer drought periods while still supporting herbivores and pollinators.

2.8.1.7 Can potential Lepidoptera diversity estimated from larval host plants serve as an effective proxy for pollination in the urban ecosystem?

The discussion in this chapter has focused on providing conditions conducive to increasing the abundance and diversity of insect herbivores, with a particular focus on *Lepidoptera*. It was hypothesized that designing to support herbivores will indirectly support

pollinators, including bees. I acknowledge that bees are dominant pollinators of many wild plants and economically important crops. The hypothesis that *Lepidoptera*-based indicators may be an adequate proxy for urban pollination remains to be tested, and research on pollination could complement the research on herbivore functions discussed in this literature review. Documented interactions between insects and specific nectar source plants also could be taken into account more explicitly in future research.

2.8.1.8 Can planners and designers use bioretention basins as part of a larger green infrastructure network to create an urbanized landscape with improved terrestrial ecological functions? How much does location of bioretention basins matter relative to the total habitat area they represent? What spatial metrics best capture city-scale connectivity and how much bioretention needs to be implemented to significantly improve the values of these metrics?

The realized abundance and diversity of *Lepidoptera* and other species at the urban site scale will not be determined in isolation but will depend on the abundance, diversity, and movement of species at the larger city and watershed scales. A future research agenda, initial steps of which are discussed in Chapter 6, can take this interplay of spatial scales into account. Of interest are the interplay between stormwater management elements (including bioretention-like practices, green roofs, ponds, wetlands and detention/retention basins) and other urban green infrastructure elements such as street and landscaping trees (the urban forest); larger parks and institutional landscapes (e.g., education, health care, government campuses); and roadside vegetation. Trees and other large woody plants are ecologically important but not always practical in stormwater management practices in highly urban environments. On the other hand, stormwater management practices may be able to take advantage of the water-rich environment to provide nectar and larval host plant species that would not otherwise be present in the urban environment. A strategy at the larger spatial scale may be able to take advantage of these opportunities afforded by stormwater elements and the biodiversity-supporting power of trees to create an overall landscape that maximizes biological diversity and abundance while also

meeting hydrologic objectives and minimum legal requirements for water resources management.

At an even larger scale, Derby Lewis et al. (2019) and Hall et al. (2017) suggest a role for urban green infrastructure in providing refuges and movement corridors for wildlife surrounded by intensively agricultural landscapes. Future research could further explore the role green stormwater infrastructure specifically can play within such a regional framework.

2.8.1.9 Is the magnitude of bioretention implementation needed to achieve desired urban hydrological and other ecosystem functions at the city scale similar to the magnitude needed at the watershed scale? Do tradeoffs exist at this larger scale or can both sets of objectives be maximized?

To achieve traditional engineering water resources management objectives such as peak flow reduction, hydrologic cycle management, and pollutant load management in urban areas, implementation of management features must achieve a minimum threshold relative to the scale of the watershed. Once an understanding is reached of the scale of green infrastructure implementation required to achieve terrestrial ecosystem function objectives in urban environments, along with an understanding of the required scale and role of green stormwater infrastructure specifically within that larger network, an interesting research endeavor will be to explore whether this threshold is similar to the threshold of implementation required to achieve watershed-scale hydrologic and water quality objectives. Additional discussion relevant to this question is provided in Chapter 6.

2.8.1.10 Does making the connection from ecosystem functions to ecosystem (economic) services improve design outcomes?

This literature review has focused on ecosystem functions of bioretention basins and stopped short of linking these explicitly to ecosystem services, or the benefits that ecosystem functions provide to humans. Some authors in the engineering and planning literature do not clearly distinguish between the terms functions and services, and making this clear distinction is

recommended. For example, the ecosystem services framework considered by Prudencio and Null (2018) included improved water quality, groundwater replenishment, recreation opportunities, “creation of diverse habitats”, ability to “counter impacts from urbanization while also increasing natural capacity to buffer for anticipated climate change”, and carbon sequestration as services. There is much fundamental research that can be conducted on ecosystem functions before they are tied to the economic concept of services, whether or not these services are ultimately valued in currency units. Nonetheless, tying functions to services may open up decision making approaches rooted in economics, such as benefit-cost analysis. These frameworks can be useful to inform policy and design decisions about where to invest limited resources for maximum benefit. It is suggested that engineers involved in this type of research collaborate with economists and other professionals with economic benefits valuation expertise, whether or not these benefits are ultimately valued in currency terms.

2.8.2 Connecting Research and Engineering Practice

Based on the literature review presented in this chapter, a key design criterion recommended as a proxy for terrestrial ecosystem function in bioretention basins is the potential number of *Lepidoptera* species supported in the larval stage by the plant genera selected by the designer. Planners and designers can adjust plant choice to maximize this value, subject to tradeoffs with other design objectives and constraints imposed by site-specific conditions.

This chapter has identified knowledge gaps that can be filled by academic research. For the new knowledge produced to have maximum impact, it needs to be codified in a form useful for professional practice (e.g., Zare et al. 2024). Useful forms include decision support tools and materials for inclusion in the “playbook” for urban infrastructure design. This playbook includes design guidelines for public infrastructure and private development; standard design plans, details, and planting plans; technical specifications for construction; standard operating protocols

for maintenance; and model language for inclusion in municipal codes and ordinances. Incorporation of the knowledge presented in this chapter into each of these design support documents is discussed below.

2.8.2.1 Decision Support Tools

This proposed product is a tool or tools to aid a bioretention designer in comparing alternative design choices in light of a variety of objectives, including terrestrial ecological objectives. A decision support tool can help a designer rank two or more discrete design alternatives to determine if a given alternative is superior, inferior, or statistically indistinguishable from other alternatives using a specified set of performance criteria. Recommended plant taxa and habitat elements relevant to specific objectives should be considered in development of these tools. For example, the designer might choose a bioretention surface area, overflow elevation, and proposed plant palette for a range of designs and receive estimates of annual groundwater recharge volume, nitrogen load prevented from reaching a downstream water body, and *Lepidoptera* species richness. This quantitative information can then aid project stakeholders in choosing between alternative designs in light of their objectives and preferences.

2.8.2.2 Design Guidelines

These guidelines consist of practical language that government entities can consider incorporating into guidelines and regulations for bioretention design on public infrastructure and on private development and redevelopment projects. Large institutional land owners such as education and health care systems, military and other large government facilities have direct control over land use on larger properties and could also consider adopting these guidelines. Design guidelines should describe minimum requirements for site investigation and geotechnical testing, facility sizing, hydraulic structure sizing and configuration, and materials including soil

characteristics, habitat elements, and plant palette. Design guidelines should also describe acceptable calculation methods and minimum documentation requirements.

2.8.2.3 Standard Plans, Details, and Technical Specifications

Standard plan drawings, standard detail drawings, and master technical specifications provide a starting point for designers preparing documents for eventual contractor bids and construction. They provide a means to implement the specifics of bioretention size, configuration, soil, and plants taken from the design guidelines. When adjusted to local conditions in accordance with the design guidelines and the designer's professional judgment, they provide a complete description of the condition that the final, constructed facility must conform to. They provide the legal basis for bidding and award of a construction contract and for the construction management process.

2.8.2.4 Standard Operating Protocols for Maintenance

A standard operating protocol provides a starting point for the bioretention system owner to tailor an appropriate maintenance plan for a given facility and location. This plan should describe the frequency and activities to be taken during routine maintenance, frequency and actions to be taken during inspections, and reactive maintenance activities to be performed in response to inspection results during the facility's functional life span. For example, a maintenance protocol might recommend removal of invasive species and replacement or reseedling of species that support more *Lepidoptera*.

2.8.2.5 Model Code and Ordinance Language

The bioretention design professional working at the site scale will have limited opportunities to affect biodiversity at larger spatial scales. However, professionals involved in land use planning and regulation, zoning code development and enforcement, and municipal stormwater and combined sewage management will have some ability to direct locations of

stormwater management elements on a larger scale by influencing the content of municipal codes and ordinances. Codes set minimum requirements and limits on land use and design of buildings and facilities on private property. Examples of these codes include zoning codes, building codes, and stormwater codes. Zoning codes in particular create the possibility to direct designs with particular features to priority areas or corridors, as discussed in Chapter 6. Local code development ultimately is affected by a mix of technocratic (e.g., public safety, environmental), legal, and political considerations. Codes can support terrestrial ecosystem functions by including landscaping and planting requirements.

2.8.2.6 Other Policy Options

Government entities can consider additional policy options for implementing planning and design guidelines. Examples of potential policies include biodiversity offset requirements, financial incentives for voluntary implementation on private property, and educational initiatives to incorporate best practices in design and in development projects.

2.8.3 Overall Conclusions

I have identified a significant opportunity to close a gap in knowledge and collaboration between the fields of engineering and ecology. By connecting existing knowledge available within these fields and applying the results to engineering design, bioretention basins can be transformed into more functional elements within urban ecosystems while still providing core water quantity and quality management functions. This result has important policy implications for professionals working to find solutions to intertwined water management and ecological challenges facing urban areas.

CHAPTER 3. A New Data Compilation to Support Bioretention Plant Choices in the U.S. Mid-Atlantic and Midwest Region

3.1 Introduction

Until now, engineers and landscape architects have made decisions about which plant taxa to include in bioretention basins primarily based on professional judgment, experience, and guidance available in design manuals published by state and local government agencies within a particular jurisdiction. This approach limits the range of plant species considered to only a subset of the species that have been identified in the wider literature as potentially appropriate for bioretention basins. Because each design manual leaves out some plant taxa, providing data from multiple sources will increase the number of taxa available to be considered by professionals. Characterizing data for individual taxa across multiple manuals likely will increase the accuracy of information about plant characteristics. Considering a wider range of species may identify plant species that are better suited to environmental conditions or contribute more to engineering objectives. Including more plant species in designs will increase biodiversity in the basins themselves and potentially better support pollinators and other wildlife in the surrounding landscape. Finally, increasing diversity and explicitly tailoring plant choices to projected environmental conditions may increase resilience of the systems. The purpose of the framework discussed in this section is not to substitute for experience and professional judgment but to provide professionals with additional information for use in screening and choosing plant species for bioretention.

Bioretention design guidance manuals have been produced by a range of state and municipal government agencies, water utilities, and non-profit organizations. The newly compiled data set includes information on 736 different plant taxa (most lists provide species names, while some provide cultivars). From this point forward, I ignore intraspecific variation

for parsimony. Information in this new data set has been linked to what was previously not available in one place due to spelling variations and use of different plant pseudonyms by different sources. Information in state and local government design manuals also has been linked to two large databases maintained by the U.S. federal government: USDA PLANTS and the National Wetland Plant List. An additional benefit of this compiled data set is its inclusion of a biodiversity indicator (number of butterfly and moth species supported by each plant genus as a larval host) that had yet to be linked to bioretention plant choice. This chapter describes the data set, provides an analysis of its contents, and suggests a procedure for professionals to follow when utilizing it as an aid in design and planning. The database will be employed for analyses discussed in Chapters 4 and 5.

3.2 Data and Methods

3.2.1 Data Sources

The goal of the research process discussed herein is to compile a master list of plant species recommended for bioretention basins located in the United States Mid-Atlantic and Midwest regions, with a particular focus on Pennsylvania. The data sources include government and industry design guidelines, the USDA PLANTS database, the National Wetland Plant List, and supplemental data from the National Gardening Association.

3.2.1.1 Government and Industry Design Guidelines

To identify appropriate data sets as a starting point from which to compile this master list, I first considered plant lists included in the 19 design manuals identified by Dagenais et al. (2018). The objective of Dagenais et al. (2018) was to evaluate scientific evidence for claims made in government agency and industry manuals related to hydraulic, hydrologic, and pollutant removal performance of bioretention systems. My purpose in beginning with the manuals

identified by Dagenais et al. (2018) was to build on the effort they made to identify a set of published information representative of what many design professionals are relying on.

Dagenais et al. (2018) identified publications containing recommended bioretention plant lists for many regions including the United States, Canada, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific. Ten of these publications originated in the United States or in southern Ontario, Canada (Figure 3.1). To further narrow the geographic scope of the present analysis, I limited my consideration to the seven publications originating in the Eastern Temperate Forests Level I Ecoregion, as defined by Omernik (1987, 2014) and later adopted by the Council for Environmental Cooperation (1997). Omernik (1987) described ecoregions as areas that are “relatively homogeneous in their soils, land use, land surface form, and potential natural vegetation”. For example, Omernik (2014) described the Eastern Temperate Forest Level I Ecoregion as a “mesic originally forest-covered region of plains, hills, and low mountains”. Acknowledging that a debate has since developed about the best definition and most appropriate applications of the ecoregion concept, my application of the concept is simply to set a geographic boundary for analysis where plant species recommendations are likely to be relevant. For example, I have used the concept when deciding to include plant recommendations from a manual published in eastern Minnesota in the compilation while excluding recommendations made in a manual published in Nebraska (Figure 3.1).

Since the Eastern Temperate Forests ecoregion includes states in the U.S. Northeast, Midwest, and Southeast regions, these can be considered “relatively homogeneous in their soils, land use, land surface form, and potential natural vegetation” (see discussion above). However, none of the published plant lists incorporated originated in the Southeast region. Many plant species included in the master list are reported to occur in these states (Figure 3.3), and the list is

therefore applicable. However, practitioners utilizing the list in this region should consider cultivars and sub-species specific to the region. Practitioners may also want to consult additional sources originating in the region and listing additional species not included in the list presented here.

Figure 3.1. Publication Location of Selected Bioretention Plant Lists within North America

To further narrow the number of publications considered, I selected a single publication whenever two publication locations were very close to each other geographically. Of the two publications produced by the Minnesota Pollution Control Agency (Shaw and Schmidt, 2003; Minnesota Pollution Control Agency, 2016), I selected Shaw and Schmidt (2003) because it contains more quantitative information than other available design manuals and is frequently cited in the academic and professional literature. Of the two publications based in Maryland (Prince George's County Environmental Services District, 2007; Center for Watershed Protection, 2009), I selected Center for Watershed Protection (2009) because it is more recent

and is currently in effect under the state regulatory framework. Finally, I chose to substitute the draft 2023 Pennsylvania Post-Construction Stormwater Management Manual (PADEP, 2023) for Philadelphia Water Department (2014) because the former manual combines the plant list from the latter with a plant list from the 2006 Pennsylvania Stormwater Best Practices Manual (PADEP, 2006). As of February 2025, Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection (2023) is a draft publication subject to a public notice and revision process.

3.2.1.2 USDA PLANTS Database

The USDA PLANTS database provides information on over 50,000 plant taxa found in North America. For each plant species and some varieties, a scientific name and a unique alphanumeric symbol is provided. Use of these standardized names and symbols helps to reduce ambiguity when linking data between data sets including plant lists in government manuals and in the National Wetland Plant List. USDA PLANTS also provides a taxonomic classification of each plant, geographic range information with citations, status as native or introduced to North America, and morphological characteristics including height at maturity and rooting depth.

USDA PLANTS is not available in a standardized tabular format, and no applied programming interface (API) has been developed for this data set to date. However, the entire database was scraped by a Kaggle user and posted publicly in 2018 (Appolonius, 2018). This scraped data set was the source of USDA PLANTS information utilized for the current study.

3.2.1.3 National Wetland Plant List (2020)

The National Wetland Plant List (NWPL) provides standardized indicator ratings describing the expected frequency with which many plant species are found in wetlands in different regions of the United States. The NWPL itself and the definitions of the indicator categories have been refined multiple times since their initial publication in 1988 (Reed, 1988; Lichvar et al., 2012). The wetland indicator ratings are assigned by regions defined by the U.S

Army Corps of Engineers, and I specified a hierarchy of these regions to choose the most relevant rating when the rating assigned differs between regions intersecting the Eastern Temperate Forests Ecoregion. Additional details of this procedure are explained in Appendix A.

3.2.1.4 *National Gardening Association*

The National Gardening Association maintains a database with information on approximately 800,000 plant species. This database includes a qualitative “Water Preferences” category along with a range of practical horticultural information (e.g., shade tolerance). The database is publicly available and can be manually searched for information about individual plant taxa. The National Gardening Association does not provide an API for the database, and staff from that organization have stated that web scraping is not a permitted use of this data set. I have respected this preference and have manually looked up water use preference information from this data set only for selected plant species where the other sources of drought tolerance information discussed in this chapter are unavailable.

3.2.2 **Standardization of Plant Names**

Scientific names listed in each of the data sources were reduced to a genus and species name. More specifically, some sources included a cultivar or sub-species name, and this information was not considered in matching across databases. Within a given species, practitioners may wish to consider cultivars specifically developed for regional conditions.

To be able to link species across data sets, it was first necessary to standardize the scientific names presented in each of the data sets. I chose to standardize all scientific names to that given in the USDA PLANTS database. For each scientific name, USDA assigns a unique alphanumeric symbol (e.g., “HEGR4” denotes *Helianthus grosseserratus*, common name sawtooth sunflower). I therefore ensured that each plant species is referred to consistently across data sets. USDA PLANTS scientific names were also linked to scientific names listed in the NWPL

whenever possible. Additional details of the procedure followed to standardize these data sources are discussed in Appendix A.

3.2.2.1 Geographical Range

The USDA PLANTS database includes a text field for most listed plant taxa specifying every U.S. state and some Canadian provinces where that plant is known to occur. It also provides a list of reference documents consulted in the development of this information for each plant. Additional details of the procedure followed to process and standardize this information are described in Appendix A.

3.2.2.2 Morphological Traits and Native Status

I also compiled information on plant traits from the design manuals and USDA PLANTS database. Traits included height at maturity, horizontal spread, flowering colors and seasonal timing, growth habit (e.g., woody or herbaceous), and status as native or introduced to the continental United States and Canada. This information was standardized and added to the master dataset using procedures described further in Appendix A.

3.2.2.3 Environmental Tolerance

My data sources contained a variety of information on the environmental tolerance ranges of plant species recommended for bioretention, including ponding (or saturated soil) tolerance, drought tolerance, and salt tolerance. Most of the information is semi-quantitative, for example, rating plant taxa as having low, medium, or high drought tolerance. To standardize and compare information across sources, I have mapped the categories used by each source to scales ranging from 1.0 (least tolerant) to 3.0 (most tolerant). Fractional values were assigned when appropriate, for example 1.5 (medium-low tolerance) and 2.5 (medium-high tolerance).

Ponding (Saturated Soil) Tolerance

Based on the wetland indicator ratings assigned to plant species in the NWPL, it is possible to develop logical expectations about the duration or frequency of saturated soils that can be tolerated. For example, it is reasonable to assume from the verbal description of the “OBL” category (Lichvar et al., 2012) that plant species within this category will be able to tolerate “14 or more consecutive days” of ponding/saturation. Likewise, it is reasonable to assume that species in the “UPL” category will be able to tolerate little to no ponding/saturation because they “almost never occur in standing water or saturated soils” (Lichvar et al., 2012). For plant species with wetland indicator ratings available, these logical relationships have been applied in development of the standardized ponding tolerance rating provided in the newly compiled master plant list (Table 3.1). These standardized ponding tolerance ratings are derived from information in the NWPL for all plant species with a wetland indicator rating (626 out of 736 species).

Table 3.1. Standardized Ratings of Ponding Tolerance Based on NWPL Indicator

Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Upland (UPL)	1
Facultative Upland (FACU)	1
Facultative (FAC)	2
Facultative Wetland (FACW)	3
Obligate (OBL)	3
No Rating (NA)	NA

For plant species with no wetland indicator rating available in the NWPL, the standardized rating reported is the mean of ratings derived from the following variables when available: Anaerobic Tolerance (USDA PLANTS), Inundation Frequency (Shaw and Schmidt, 2003), Inundation Frequency (Maryland), Inundation Tolerance (PADEP), Flood Frequency Tolerance (St. Louis), Hydrologic Zone (Maryland), Hydrologic Zone (PADEP), and Landscape

Zone (Toronto). Detailed tables explaining the mapping of these variables to the standardized three-point scale are provided in Appendix A. Not all plant species have data for all variables.

Drought Tolerance

Drought tolerance is not simply the inverse of ponding tolerance because some plants may have adaptations to both very wet and very dry conditions. Nonetheless, it is reasonable to assume that plant species assigned wetland indicator “OBL” have low drought tolerance since “[w]ith few exceptions, these species (herbaceous or woody) are found in standing water or seasonally saturated soils” (Lichvar et al., 2012). No inferences about drought tolerance have been made for any of the other wetland indicator ratings.

It is reasonable to infer that plants with high salt tolerance will also have high drought tolerance. Saline soils reduce the ability of plant roots to take up water at a given soil moisture potential, and adaptations that allow plants to take up water at lower (more negative) water potentials will often convey an advantage in terms of both salt and drought tolerance (Munns and Tester, 2008). No inferences have been made about whether plant taxa in the “low” and “medium” standardized salt tolerance categories are either drought tolerant or intolerant.

Standardized drought tolerance ratings are calculated using the mean of ratings derived from the wetland indicator rating (“OBL” rating only); salt tolerance (“High” rating only); drought tolerance ratings from PADEP, St. Louis, and Toronto design manuals; and “water use” ratings from USDA PLANTS, whenever at least one of these six ratings is applicable. For taxa without any of this information available, I manually looked up available “water preference” ratings provided by the National Gardening Association and mapped these to the standardized scale. Table 3.2 is an example standardization table mapping codes in the PADEP manual to the standard scale. Full details of the mapping are provided in Appendix A. Using all the sources

discussed, sufficient information was available to assign standardized drought tolerance ratings to 675 of the 736 plant species in the master data set.

Table 3.2. Logic for Assigning Standardized Qualitative Drought Indicator Values Based on Codes Provided in PADEP (2023)

Source Rating	Interpretation	Standardized Rating
"L"	Low Drought Tolerance	1
"N"	Very Low or No Drought Tolerance	1
"No"	Very Low or No Drought Tolerance	1
"M"	Moderate Drought Tolerance	2
"H"	High Drought Tolerance	3
"NA"	No Drought Tolerance Information Provided	NA

Salt Tolerance

Qualitative salt tolerance ratings are provided by all five of the design manuals and by USDA PLANTS. These ratings were standardized on a scale of low (1.0) to high (3.0) and the mean rating was then determined for each species in the database. Table 3.3 provides one example of a standardization table for the Credit Valley Conservation Authority manual.

Additional details of the standardization process are described in Appendix A.

Table 3.3. Logic for Assigning Standardized Qualitative Salt Indicator Values Based on Codes Provided in Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)

Source Rating	Standardized Rating
L	1.0
L-M	1.5
M	2.0
M-H	2.5
H	3.0
NA	NA
unknown	NA

Lepidoptera Host Plant Status

In 2020, Narango et al. published an open-source data set synthesizing a large amount of documentation on the ability of many plant genera to serve as host plants for the larval stages of *Lepidoptera* species (butterflies and moths). Narango et al. (2020) provided this information for selected counties throughout the continental United States. Relevant data for Lancaster County,

Pennsylvania has been joined by genus to the master bioretention plant data set discussed in this chapter, and the full data set published by Narango et al. (2020) is available in the supplemental materials provided with their article.

3.3 Results and Discussion

3.3.1 Geographical Range

The five bioretention design manuals list a total of 736 unique plant species. Each manual lists some species that are unique to that manual, but many species are listed by multiple manuals (Figure 3.2). For example, of the 549 unique plant species listed by the Pennsylvania and Maryland manuals, 126 (23% of the total) are found in both manuals. The southeastern portion of Pennsylvania has a similar climate to Maryland, and it may be appropriate to consider the joint list when picking plant species for designs in either area. However, the publication location of the manuals is not the only information available when choosing species appropriate to a particular region.

Figure 3.2. Overlap Between 736 Unique Bioretention Plant Species Listed in the Five Manuals

Of the 736 unique plant species in the master list, USDA PLANTS provides state-level distribution data for 718. Figure 3.3 illustrates the percentage of these 718 found in each state intersecting the Eastern Temperate Forests Ecoregion. More than 80% of the plant species in the database can be found occurring in New York, Pennsylvania, and Virginia, suggesting the list provides a particularly rich set of choices in these states. In fact, for most states in the Mid-Atlantic and Midwest regions, the list provides a robust set of choices to consider as a starting point. All states contain at least 50% of the species in the master list except for Oklahoma and Florida. For states on the periphery of the Eastern Temperate Forests ecoregion and for the Southeast states specifically, it is recommended that practitioners supplement plant species choices in the list with other regional sources. It is also recommended that practitioners

investigate cultivars within species of interest that are bred specifically for conditions in the region of interest.

Figure 3.3. Percent of Unique Plant Species in the Master List Found in Each U.S. State Intersecting the Eastern Temperate Forests Ecoregion. The difference in geography between Figures 3.1 and 3.3 is that the ecoregion boundary is not shown, and in Figure 3.3 only the states with any portion intersecting the ecoregion are shown. This choice was made because plant distribution information in USDA PLANTS is most readily accessible at the state level.

Because there is substantial overlap between the plant taxa contained in the five manuals and because taxa contained in each manual occur throughout the ecoregion regardless of the manual’s publication location, it is appropriate to create a single master data set containing all the taxa in the manuals which planners and designers can then filter based on geography and other criteria. This master data set can be filtered to include only plant taxa recommended by a particular manual or by a subset of manuals if desired. A user can select species appropriate to

specific environmental conditions that are expected based on design conditions. Other stakeholder/landowner objectives such as ecological functions also can be considered (as discussed later).

3.3.2 Physical Characteristics and Native Status

The master list covers a wide diversity of plants, with the 736 unique species belonging to 110 different plant families (Table 3.4). The species listed are approximately two-thirds herbaceous and one-third woody. Species considered native to North America make up over 90% of the total, providing planners and designers wishing to choose only native species with a wide range of possibilities to consider. Some of the remaining species not classified as native in the list lack information in USDA PLANTS and could warrant further investigation on an individual basis to inform a final determination on their nativity.

Table 3.4. Selected Characteristics of Plant Species in the Master List by Botanical Family

Family	Number of Species	Growth Habit ¹		Native Status ¹	
		Herbaceous	Woody	Native (L48)	Non-Native or Unclassified
Asteraceae	105	101	4	92	13
Poaceae	72	72	0	60	12
Cyperaceae	62	62	0	60	2
Rosaceae	45	7	38	39	6
Ericaceae	36	0	36	33	3
Fagaceae	20	0	20	20	0
Lamiaceae	19	14	5	16	3
Fabaceae	16	10	6	15	1
Salicaceae	16	0	16	16	0
Caprifoliaceae	14	0	14	13	1
Juncaceae	13	13	0	13	0
Betulaceae	12	0	12	12	0
Liliaceae	12	12	0	12	0
Pinaceae	12	0	12	11	1
Campanulaceae	11	11	0	11	0
Ranunculaceae	11	10	1	10	1
Scrophulariaceae	11	11	0	11	0
All Other Families (n<10)	250	147	103	233	17
Total	737	470	267	677	60

¹ Source: USDA PLANTS

3.3.3 Environmental Tolerance

Table 3.5 summarizes the number of plant species falling into each standardized ponding tolerance, drought tolerance, and salt tolerance category grouped by design manual. Conditions that can be expected in a given bioretention design, and therefore the tolerance range of plants that will be appropriate, will vary depending on a number of factors. For example, a larger

watershed area relative to the bioretention footprint will tend to increase unit-area inflow to a basin, increasing the duration of ponding and saturated soil conditions while reducing the length and severity of drought periods. A greater maximum ponding depth, regulated by the overflow elevation set in the basin, will increase the duration of ponding and decrease the duration and severity of dry soil conditions following large storms. Plant species tolerant of ponding may be preferred under these conditions. More permeable soils will tend to decrease ponding and saturated soil durations while increasing the length and severity of drought periods. More drought tolerant species may be preferred under these conditions. Systems located in colder climates and tributary to urban land uses, particularly transportation infrastructure, will tend to receive larger loads of deicing salts. More salt tolerant plants may be preferred under these conditions.

Table 3.5. Summary of Mean Bioretention Plant Tolerance Ratings Derived for Plants Included in Each of the Design Manuals

Source	Species Included	Inundation Tolerance			Drought Tolerance			Salt Tolerance		
		Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High
Shaw and Schmidt	131	20	23	88	62	55	12	71	54	3
PADEP	246	92	55	99	95	102	48	147	72	10
Maryland	429	105	95	229	162	151	58	354	62	13
St. Louis	96	40	34	22	16	43	37	73	23	0
Toronto	224	82	40	80	48	112	64	78	123	18

Note: Columns do not add to the total number of unique species because some species are included in multiple sources. The sum of low, moderate, and high ratings may not add to the total number of species for a given source because tolerance information is not available for all species and categories.

Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5 provide an illustration of the variation and uncertainty in the qualitative drought and salt tolerance ratings derived from information in the manuals. The ponding tolerance ratings are not depicted in this format because they exhibit less variation. This lack of variation in the ponding tolerance ratings occurs because they are based on one source, the NWPL wetland indicator rating, whenever this rating is available. The species included in

Figure 3.4 (drought tolerance) and Figure 3.5 (salt tolerance) are the 49 species that are included in at least four of the five manuals. (Of these 49, seven are included in all five manuals.) For each species, the point corresponds to the mean tolerance rating read from the horizontal axis, while the whiskers to the right and left of the point represent the maximum and minimum tolerance values derived for that plant species from information in any of the manuals or databases. The numbers above and to the right of the points represent the number of pieces of information included in the mean. For example, the “3” annotated above and to the right of *Lobelia siphilitica* in Figure 3.4 indicates that the mean drought tolerance value plotted is derived from three pieces of information: drought tolerance ratings from the St. Louis manual (medium or 2.0), the Pennsylvania manual (low or 1.0), and the Toronto manual (low or 1.0). The mean rating is 1.33, the arithmetic mean of these three values, indicating low tolerance, and the range is low (1.0) to medium (2.0) tolerance. For some plant species, the range reported by different sources is the widest possible extending from low to high (e.g., *Spiraea alba*), indicating lack of consensus between sources. For others there is a consensus on a single value based on multiple pieces of information (e.g., *Caltha palustris*). In some cases, multiple pieces of information may be derived from a single manual or database. Each piece of available information is given equal weight in the mean regardless of source.

Figure 3.4. Range and Variability of Standardized Drought Tolerance Ratings Across Sources

Figure 3.5 represents the degree of consensus and variability of qualitative salt tolerance ratings reported by available sources. The points represent the mean rating for each plant species, while the whiskers represent the range for ratings reported by multiple sources. The numbers above and to the right of each point indicate the number of source ratings used to calculate the mean. For the 49 species shown, the mean rating is never in the “High” category (defined as ≥ 2.5 on the numeric scale). This result may be considered in the context of Table 3.5 which shows that when all species in the list are considered, each of the design manuals other than the St. Louis manual includes some species rated for high salt tolerance. Table 3.5 suggests that there is a lack of consensus among the sources on the most salt tolerant species, while there is greater consensus on the least salt tolerant species. While this compilation of salt tolerance information represents an increase in salt tolerance information compiled in one place and readily available compared to the past, design professionals should consider the salt tolerant ratings presented in this list alongside location-specific knowledge and professional judgment.

Figure 3.5. Range and Variability of Standardized Salt Tolerance Ratings Across Sources

3.3.4 *Lepidoptera* Host Plant Status

As discussed in Chapter 2, support for the larval stages of *Lepidoptera* has been proposed by a range of researchers as a good proxy measure for overall terrestrial ecosystem function (also see Myers et al., 2025). Figure 3.6 is a visualization of data posted by Narango et al. (2020) for Lancaster County, Pennsylvania. The top plot is a histogram (with unequal bin widths) of the number of *Lepidoptera* species larvae supported by plant genera known to be present in the county. The bottom plot in Figure 3.6 illustrates the number of *Lepidoptera* species larvae supported by the 26 plant genera known to support more than 100 *Lepidoptera* species larvae in total. Intentionally including more plant genera acting as host plants for *Lepidoptera* larvae is one quantitative way for bioretention designers to increase overall ecological function and biodiversity in urban landscapes.

Figure 3.6. Number of *Lepidoptera* Species Reported to be Supported by Plant Genera Recommended for Bioretention Basins

3.3.5 Synthesis of Environmental Tolerance and *Lepidoptera* Host Plant Information

Summarizing the information presented in this chapter, Figure 3.7 combines ponding tolerance, drought tolerance, and *Lepidoptera* host plant status for species reported by USDA PLANTS to be native to the continental United States and distributed in the state of Pennsylvania. Alphanumeric codes correspond to unique symbols assigned to each plant taxon in the USDA PLANTS database. This subset includes 578 plant taxa out of the total of 736 in the

master data set. A bioretention designer can select the regions of the plot representing expected environmental conditions (e.g., medium to high ponding tolerance and low to medium drought tolerance) and then further screen for plant species that serve as larval hosts for *Lepidoptera* species. Following this process will allow designers to expand the set of initial plant choices to consider beyond what is currently considered in many cases.

3.4 Conclusions and Recommended Steps for Engineering Practice

The newly compiled master plant list presented in this chapter provides professionals involved in bioretention planning and engineering with a wider range of plant species to consider than many teams may have considered in the past. A suggested procedure for using this information is presented below. Prior to implementing these steps, it is assumed that an engineering design has been completed that will meet minimum legal requirements and other stakeholder priorities in terms of managing the hydrologic cycle, managing pollutant loads discharged to surface water and groundwater, and managing peak flows. Design professionals will typically also consider a range of additional factors such as aesthetics, space constraints, light and shade characteristics, line of site to signs and traffic signals, local codes and ordinances, and stakeholder/landowner preferences while stepping through the recommended procedure presented below.

Plant species included in the master list are intended to apply inside the boundaries of the Eastern Temperate Forests ecoregion. In the U.S. Mid-Atlantic and Midwest states and southern portions of Ontario, the list can be considered a comprehensive guide to plant species that have been recommended for bioretention by multiple government entities in this region. Many species included are also relevant to bioretention designs in the Southeast states. However, practitioners in these states may wish to consult sources published in the region for additional species recommendations. In all regions, practitioners may wish to investigate cultivars within species of interest bred specifically for their conditions.

3.4.1 Filter plant species by geography.

The list is most applicable to designs and design guidelines for the U.S. Mid-Atlantic and Midwest states, with a particular focus on those states shown in darker colors in Figure 3.3. The planner or designer may first wish to filter the list to just those species reported in the USDA

PLANTS database to occur in the state where the design will be implemented or where a set of guidelines will have jurisdiction. To widen the range of plant species considered initially, the filter could be set to the state of interest and adjacent states. A planner or designer can filter the list to include only species included in the design manual published by their applicable regulatory jurisdiction, if desired. There is no scientific or technical reason to limit choices to those listed in one manual, but professionals may deem from experience that there is an advantage in streamlining the location-specific regulatory approval process.

3.4.2 Filter by native status.

To maximize terrestrial ecosystem functions, many designers and planners may prefer to consider only plant taxa native to the continental United States (“L48 (N)” in the USDA PLANTS database) or to Canada.

3.4.3 Screen for invasive plants.

The previous steps of filtering by geography and by native status may eliminate many or most plant taxa with potential to become invasive. Additionally, each plant list included in a source design manual has been screened by its original authors, who typically have professional and administrative expertise with stormwater management design in their local jurisdiction. USDA PLANTS provides additional information on plant taxa flagged as potentially invasive in various jurisdictions, and this information has been included in the master list for review by the user. Although the data set contains these safeguards against inclusion of invasive species, it is still important for individual practitioners to consider applicable regulations on invasive species when making final plant selections.

3.4.4 Screen by environmental tolerance – ponding (saturated soil) tolerance, drought tolerance, and salt tolerance.

This screening will require application of judgment on the part of the design engineer and can be based on a number of factors such as the bioretention surface area relative to the impervious watershed area (relevant to duration of wet and dry periods), overflow weir height (also relevant to duration of wet and dry periods), and soil characteristics (relevant to soil drying). Whether salt tolerant species will be required will be a function of climate and of land use (particularly adjacency to transportation infrastructure). Designers and landowners may also consider their own risk tolerance and resources available for operation and maintenance. For example, if it is important for a given site to be as low maintenance as possible, the designer may want to limit plant taxa considered to a few highly tolerant choices. Conversely, if resources and personnel are available to replace plants that do not survive, it may be acceptable to experiment with some less tolerant taxa. Internal topography of the bioretention basin also can be considered. For example, it may be possible to plant saturation-tolerant taxa around the edges of a system while accepting that vegetation will not survive in the deepest portions of the basin during prolonged ponding. Vegetation may be able to expand into this portion of a basin in drier years even if it does not establish there permanently.

3.4.5 Screen by potential to enhance terrestrial ecosystem functionality.

Simply increasing the total number (richness) of plant species is one approach to boosting ecosystem functionality. Plants which serve as hosts for large numbers of butterfly and moth larvae have been suggested in the literature as particularly advantageous boosters of terrestrial ecosystem function (Chapter 2), and this information has been included in the master data set. Designers also may wish to support pollinators by choosing native flowering plant species with a range of bloom times and colors. The USDA PLANTS database includes information on bloom

color, and some of the design manuals (e.g., St. Louis) include regional information on bloom times.

3.4.6 Consider commercial availability for successful implementation.

Commercial availability of plants varies locally, and engineers, landscape architects, landscapers, and nursery professionals practicing in a given location will have the most relevant knowledge about what plants are readily available. The plant species in the master list have been included based on the professional judgment of local officials and practitioners in at least one of the manual publication locations, suggesting that most species listed were available around the time and place of publication. Where time frames for establishment and stakeholder/landowner preferences permit, growing some plants from seed may provide additional flexibility to implement a wider range of plant taxa over a period of time. Longer term, the choices of government agencies developing design standards for public infrastructure and codes regulating private property may be able to expand the market for desirable species, leading to their increased commercial availability in the future.

3.4.7 Final Thoughts

The order of the suggested procedure may change depending on design professionals' priorities. For example, if salt tolerance is a key determining factor for plant selection, Step 3.4.4 may be the first. The newly compiled database discussed in this chapter will improve the ability of designers to create systems that will be resilient under a range of future scenarios. Future research can further extend this procedure by developing a more quantitative description of environmental conditions and linking this to a quantitative index of plant suitability. This more quantitative approach will be of interest in research settings and in some professional design settings where available resources and stakeholder preferences permit. Chapter 4 develops this idea.

This analysis has compiled largely qualitative information in government and professional publications related to bioretention design, in two large U.S. government databases, and in one recent academic publication from the field of ecology. The scope of this research task has not included publications and resources available from the horticultural and soil science communities. Future research could incorporate more quantitative information (for example, on drought and salt tolerance of various landscape plant taxa) from these fields in the data compilation presented here.

CHAPTER 4. Site-Scale Tradeoffs Between Stormwater Management and Terrestrial Ecological Function Objectives

4.1 Introduction

This chapter makes two important contributions to the field of water resources and urban hydrologic management. First, it demonstrates the validation and application of the publicly available simulation code Hydrus 1D to a 20-year continuous simulation of a range of common bioretention design choices. This model is most commonly used for short-term simulations in agriculture and soil science applications (Simunek et al., 2018). Analyzing the results of these simulations, I derive a range of performance measures of interest to bioretention planners and designers. These include typical engineering objectives such as management of the hydrologic cycle, peak flows and pollutant loads. Also included is a novel quantitative index of potential plant biodiversity building on the qualitative approach presented in Chapter 3. Finally, I derive an index of potential *Lepidoptera* (butterfly and moth) biodiversity for each studied variation on the industry-standard bioretention design. This index serves as a proxy for terrestrial ecosystem function (see Chapter 2) and has never before been developed from numerical simulations. I formulate and test hypotheses concerning potential tradeoffs between these traditional engineering and novel ecological indices. Finally, in the final section of this chapter I present examples of how the performance indices developed in the course of this work can be combined and employed in decision making in a professional context.

4.2 Data and Methods

4.2.1 Model Selection and Validation

4.2.1.1 Definitions and Statement of Model Purpose

This study will make use of both empirical data and results of numerical simulations. My primary objective is to compare the performance of alternative design scenarios that have not yet

been implemented, and simulation outputs based on validated numerical models are the most viable basis for distinguishing between the expected performance of the scenarios. Comparison of the simulation framework to high quality field observations from an established bioretention installation helps establish the validity of the simulation approach. Rykiel (1996) provides one useful definition of model validation in an engineering context: "Validation is a demonstration that a model within its domain of applicability possesses a satisfactory range of accuracy consistent with the intended application of the model." The intended application of the modeling framework employed in this study is to rank multiple design scenarios and to determine if any scenarios are superior using a specified set of performance criteria. In the Rykiel (1996) concept, calibration is one part of a larger umbrella concept of validation. Rykiel (1996) defines calibration as "the estimation and adjustment of model parameters and constants to improve the agreement between model output and a data set". For the purposes of this study, I have adopted the definitions of model validation and calibration provided by Rykiel (1996).

The performance measures employed in the current study are intended to inform decisions of practicing engineers aimed at desirable design outcomes. It is not an objective of the simulation approach presented here to replicate the observed behavior of a specific bioretention system installed in the field to date. Rather, the simulation results presented here are compared to field data collected from the Bioinfiltration Traffic Island at Villanova University to demonstrate that the model is a reasonable one-dimensional representation of one implemented bioretention design representative of industry standard design and can therefore credibly serve as a basis for engineering decisions about future designs with similar characteristics.

4.2.1.2 Selection and Configuration of Hydrus 1D

The open source software Hydrus-1D Version 4.17 (Simunek et al., 2018) was selected as a simulation tool for the current research exercise. Hydrus-1D simulates soil water dynamics

using a numerical solution to the one-dimensional Richards equation for unsaturated and saturated soil. Soil moisture characteristic curve fitting parameters are provided in the form described by Van Genuchten (1980) using the pore-size distribution model of Mualem (1976). Among several options implemented internally in Hydrus-1D, these relationships can be estimated through a library of pedotransfer functions called Rosetta DLL which was originally developed at the U.S. Salinity Laboratory. The solution to the Richards equation predicts the downward flux of water due to gravity during and after a ponding event. Upward flux of water due to evaporative demand is simulated using the approach of Hargreaves and Samani (1985). Plant root water uptake is simulated using the method proposed by Feddes et al. (1978).

A variable computation time step was employed in the simulations, ranging from a maximum of six minutes to a minimum on the order of one second. Output variables other than soil water content throughout the soil profile were reported at the computation time step. Soil water content at 1 cm depth increments throughout the soil profile was reported at six-hour intervals. Time periods represented in the simulation ranged from 29 months for the validation simulation to 20 years for each of the 18 design scenario simulations. The 20-year duration allowed characterization of conditions over a range of wetter, dryer, and more typical conditions.

4.2.1.3 Selection of Field Data from Villanova Bioinfiltration Traffic Island

An inflow time series to serve as the hydrologic driver for the present analysis was derived from a 20-year time series of inflow to Villanova University's Bioinfiltration Traffic Island (BTI). The development of this data set was described in detail by McGauley et al. (2023). McGauley et al. (2023) used physics-based theory and statistical modeling of continuous field data collected at 5-minute increments to construct a continuous record of inflow for 20 years. I derived a time series of hourly inflow to the basin for the period January 1, 2003 through December 31, 2022. I summed the 5-minute inflow volume data provided by McGauley et al.

(2023) to create an hourly record, with values recorded at the top of each hour assigned to the previous hour's sum. To facilitate one-dimensional modeling, I divided this hourly inflow record by two areas. First, I divided by the surface area of the BTI to obtain a value suitable for comparison between observed and simulated values in model validation. Second, I divided by the area of impervious surfaces contributing runoff to the basin (including the basin surface area) to obtain a record that can be treated as a proxy for rainfall falling on the watershed. This second time series is appropriate to serve as a boundary condition in simulating alternative future design scenarios for a hypothetical bioretention basin similar to the BTI but with variations in design and underlying conditions. I also obtained hourly rainfall data reported at the Philadelphia International Airport for the period December 1-31, 2002 for the sole purpose of obtaining an estimate of antecedent conditions in the modeled bioretention scenarios on January 1, 2003. Table 4.1 summarizes assumptions about the BTI employed in the current study and the source of each assumption.

Table 4.1. Assumed Dimensions and Characteristics of Bioinfiltration Traffic Island

Assumption	Value	Units	Source
watershed area	5,261	m ²	Sokolovskaya et al. (2021)
watershed imperviousness	50	%	McGauley et al. (2023)
bioretention surface/infiltration area	144	m ²	Sokolovskaya et al. (2021)
maximum ponding depth	49	cm	Sokolovskaya et al. (2021)

Jenkins et al. (2010) provided information on the particle size distributions of both the engineered soil and underlying soil at this site. Table 4.2 includes information from Jenkins et al. (2010) relevant to the current study, and Appendix B contains additional information on finer particle sizes than those reported in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Particle Size Distribution of BTI Reported by Jenkins (2010)

Particle Size (mm)	Percent Passing		
	Native Soil - 2001	Engineered Soil - 2009 (Site S-2)	Engineered Soil - 2009 (Site S-4)
2	93.06	99.00	98.60
0.84	86.12	90.00	86.20
0.425	78.95	75.25	70.20
0.15	66.26	59.75	47.40
0.075	58.12	34.50	23.00

The Villanova Center for Resilient Water Systems maintains an extensive database of environmental measurements for the BTI, including water level and soil moisture data, as described by Smith et al. (2023). Soil moisture data have been derived from tensiometers deployed at 10 cm, 35 cm, and 65 cm depths in the engineered bioretention soil (Shakya et al., 2023).

I applied a quality control protocol consisting of visual inspection of time series plots of the data by month. I screened for the continuous availability of data, whether the data fall within physically meaningful ranges, and whether the data display expected time patterns (i.e., response to measured rainfall and drying during periods of no rainfall). Finally, I reviewed the last frost date (last calendar date with a recorded minimum temperature below 0°C) for each year with available data. I selected the growing seasons of 2016-2018 because they passed these criteria for soil moisture data availability, quality, and entirely or mostly frost-free conditions during the month of April. These years also represent a range of conditions, where 2016 and 2017 had the two lowest inflow volumes during the twenty years studied and 2018 had the second highest (Table 4.10). Within these growing seasons, I selected the month of April to represent relatively low-transpiration conditions and the months of July and August to represent high-transpiration conditions. High-quality water level data derived from pressure transducer apparatus is also available for these periods. Table B.2 in Appendix B provides more detailed information on the availability and quality assessment of soil moisture data for the BTI.

4.2.1.4 Selection of Calibration Events

From the validation period, sixteen wet weather events were selected for calculation of quantitative calibration metrics (Table 4.3). From the set of all wet weather events that occurred during the validation period, events with peak water levels less than 15 cm were excluded because the assumption of a linear surface area-volume relationship is assumed not to hold below approximately this level. The justification for this assumption is that the bowl-shaped geometry and microtopography of the basin bottom have a proportionately greater effect on storage volume, spatial variability of soil moisture, and spatial patterns of infiltration during smaller wet weather events (Sokolovskaya et al., 2021). The 15 cm cutoff was chosen based on visual analysis of the observed-simulated peak depth relationship, where the relationship diverges from the line of equal agreement below approximately this level (Section 4.3.1). Events with peak water levels greater than the weir height (49 cm) also were excluded because the chosen modeling framework does not represent the hydraulics of depths that exceed this elevation.

Table 4.3. Wet Weather Calibration Events

Wet Event	Event Start	Duration (hr)	Maximum Level (cm)	Inflow Volume (watershed-mm)
4	2016-04-09 12:00:00	49	15.5	8.21
5	2016-04-12 08:00:00	30	20.7	6.14
29	2016-08-12 15:00:00	14	24.4	13.8
32	2016-08-21 15:00:00	30	42.9	24.4
58	2017-03-31 01:00:00	70	38.1	31.6
59	2017-04-04 00:00:00	21	15.5	6.08
60	2017-04-06 10:00:00	49	39.9	16.5
64	2017-04-25 13:00:00	38	24.7	15.0
77	2017-07-06 15:00:00	15	18.2	13.2
79	2017-07-07 20:00:00	14	16.8	5.40
83	2017-07-23 20:00:00	54	38.7	32.0
86	2017-08-05 02:00:00	17	25.3	17.1
87	2017-08-07 07:00:00	37	32.6	20.1
141	2018-07-15 11:00:00	16	21.7	12.5
143	2018-07-21 19:00:00	49	34.4	29.0
146	2018-08-03 16:00:00	41	34.5	38.1

Dry periods (with no ponding depth) also were defined for comparison of observed and simulated minimum soil water contents. Because all dry weather periods during the validation period were included in the analysis, the number of dry weather periods considered was greater than the number of wet weather periods considered.

4.2.1.5 Selection of Efficiency Measures

In model calibration, agreement between observed and simulated values was evaluated by visually comparing time series and by assessing the values of quantitative metrics. Three quantitative metrics were selected to evaluate goodness of fit: percent bias (Gupta et al., 1999), root mean square error (e.g., Dodson, 2022), and Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). Equations and additional discussion of these metrics are provided in Appendix C. These metrics were calculated for observed and simulated peak water level during each wet weather period of the calibration period, for the mean slope of the hydrograph recession limb during each wet weather period, and for the minimum volumetric soil water content at 10 cm, 35 cm, and 65 cm depths at the end of each dry weather period during the calibration months. A minimum six-hour interevent time (dry period with no system inflow) was employed to distinguish between wet weather events.

4.2.2 Conceptual Design Scenarios

Eighteen hypothetical bioretention scenarios, each consisting of a set of design choices and an assumption about underlying soil properties, were created for calculation and analysis of engineering and ecological performance measures (Table 4.4). These scenarios can be thought of as variations on the BTI, but none is identical to the BTI. The purpose of the scenarios is to represent a range of choices and conditions that an engineer might encounter in a planning or design situation. The 18 scenarios have equivalent total storage capacity (within 0.05 watershed-cm due to rounding of dimensions) calculated as the sum of surface storage and storage in the

engineered soil pores. Methods and conclusions are limited to systems with designs and boundary conditions similar to the BTI. These assumptions include the presence of native soil deep enough to accommodate the roots of the bioretention plant species considered, absence of shallow bedrock, and absence of a shallow water table (i.e., the capillary fringe does not extend from the water table to the bottom of the plant roots). This design does not include an underdrain, and results and conclusions are not applicable to underdrained systems.

Table 4.4. Design and Simulation Scenarios

Variable	Scenario																	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
watershed/ bioretention area ratio	5	15	15	5	15	15	5	15	15	5	15	15	5	15	15	5	15	15
maximum ponding depth (cm)	12	73	49	12	73	49	12	73	49	12	73	49	12	73	49	12	73	49
engineered soil depth (cm)	61	61	122	61	61	122	61	61	122	61	61	122	61	61	122	61	61	122
underlying soil Ksat (cm/hr)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76
root depth (cm)	10	10	10	60	60	60	120	120	120	10	10	10	60	60	60	120	120	120
maximum leaf area index	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
surface storage (watershed-cm)	2.0	4.6	3.1	2.0	4.6	3.1	2.0	4.6	3.1	2.0	4.6	3.1	2.0	4.6	3.1	2.0	4.6	3.1
soil storage (watershed-cm)	4.1	1.5	3.1	4.1	1.5	3.1	4.1	1.5	3.1	4.1	1.5	3.1	4.1	1.5	3.1	4.1	1.5	3.1
surface + soil storage (watershed-cm)	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1	6.1

The watershed area includes the area of impervious surfaces contributing runoff to the bioretention basin, and it is also defined to include the surface area of the bioretention basin itself. The simulated root depth represents the depth of a plant serving a root uptake and transpiration function in the simulation. It does not represent any specific plant in the master plant list described in Chapter 3. Roots are present throughout the year, but transpiration occurs only when leaves are present during the growing season (assumed to be March 15 to November 15).

Each of the design scenarios was represented in Hydrus-1D. The validated model described in Section 4.2.1 was used as a starting point for development of these scenarios. Inflow hydrographs provided by McGauley et al. (2023) were manipulated to represent one-dimensional

inflow per unit of bioretention surface area in each of the 18 scenarios. Potential evapotranspiration was calculated within the Hydrus-1D simulation using the method of Hargreaves and Samani (1985). To represent surface ponding, the Hydrus input parameter “hCritS” was set to the maximum ponding depth, representing the maximum positive pressure head allowed to develop at the soil surface.

The Hydrus simulations include root water uptake and transpiration using the method of Feddes et al. (1978). Changes in osmotic pressure due to salinity were not represented in the simulations. Roots were assumed to be constant in depth throughout the year, but transpiration could only occur in the simulation during the leaf-on season, assumed to be March 15 through November 15. Following an approach similar to Hess et al. (2017), leaf area index (total leaf surface area in three dimensions divided by the plant’s two-dimensional ground projection) was assumed to increase linearly from one-third of its maximum value on March 15 to its maximum value on May 1, and then to decrease linearly from its maximum value to one-third its maximum value between October 1 and November 15. Two maximum values of leaf area index were simulated. A maximum leaf area index of 4.5 is similar to measurements reported by bioretention plants grown in lysimeters by Hess et al. (2017) and to herbaceous agricultural crops such as alfalfa (Simunek et al., 2018). A maximum leaf area index of 8.5 was assumed to represent larger trees (Scurlock, 2002).

The starting point for root water uptake properties was a set of assumptions for alfalfa included in the library of values provided within the Hydrus graphical user interface. However, the wilting point parameter was reduced from a soil pore tension of -8,000 cm to -20,000 cm. This value represents a highly drought tolerant plant and was chosen to ensure that soil drying occurs throughout the root zone during periods without simulated ponding.

The boundary condition at the bottom of the underlying soil layer in all the simulations was set to a pore tension of -100 cm. Creating an unsaturated condition at the bottom boundary was found to be necessary to ensure convergence of the numerical solution under conditions in which the entire soil profile became saturated and a positive pressure head existed at the soil surface.

For the simulations assessing design alternatives, each 20-year continuous simulation result was constructed from a sequence of 40 individual seven-month simulations. This approach was necessary due to limitations on the number of output time steps written by the Hydrus 1D code. With the exception of the first simulation in the series, the first calendar month of each seven-month simulation overlapped with the final month of the previous simulation and was used to establish antecedent moisture conditions. For the first simulation, inputs to the first month (December 2002) were constructed from a runoff time series generated by a rational method approach applied to Philadelphia International Airport rainfall data. For each seven-month simulation, this first month was dropped from the time series used to construct the 20-year sequence.

The van Genuchten-Mualem soil moisture characteristic model was employed without the option to allow an air-entry value of -2 cm. No hysteresis was permitted in the soil moisture behavior. Although Simunek et al. (2018) recommend allowing no more than 10 iterations for the numerical simulation to converge, this limit was found to be impractical when running a long-term continuous simulation. Up to 1,000 iterations were allowed for convergence, as this condition occurred during very few time steps representing just a few seconds over the course of each seven-month simulation. Other iteration tolerance criteria were not changed from the values recommended by Simunek et al. (2018).

4.2.3 Performance Measures

The approach proposed here is intended to help planners and designers project engineering performance of a proposed bioretention design and to narrow down the wide range of potential plant choices using quantitative information. Bioretention manuals often provide lists of qualitative and semi-quantitative information on plants and recommend the designer apply professional judgment in selecting plants that are suitable for site conditions. The approach proposed here is intended to supplement rather than replace professional judgment, providing designers with additional information to help justify their plant choice decisions. It is important to acknowledge that the approach presented here will not be able to make a quantitative scientific prediction of the probability of plant survival. With additional empirical research, it might be possible for a research team with expertise in fields such as biology and horticulture to develop the logic presented here into a prediction of plant survival probability.

4.2.3.1 Water Budget

Simulated water budget components were summed and calculated from continuous Hydrus time series outputs. Table 4.5 summarizes the Hydrus variables employed and transformations performed on these simulation outputs.

Table 4.5. Derivation of Water Budget Components from Hydrus Simulation Output

Component	Hydrus Output File	Hydrus Output Variable	Units	Transformations
Evaporation	T_Level.out	sum(Evap)	cm	differenced between reporting time steps; summed over simulation period
Transpiration	T_Level.out	vRoot	cm/ Δt	summed over simulation period
Surface Outflow	T_Level.out	RunOff	cm/ Δt	summed over simulation period
Groundwater Recharge (Bottom Flux)	T_Level.out	vBot	cm/ Δt	summed over simulation period
Change in Storage	T_Level.out	Volume	cm	took difference between value at end and beginning of simulation period

4.2.3.2 Total Nitrogen Loads Exported to Surface Waters

Estimated total nitrogen loads in bioretention surface inflow and surface outflow were estimated using an event mean concentration (EMC) approach. Assumptions employed in the

calculations are derived from the values shown in Table 4.6, a summary of data reported by U.S. National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System permittees in Pitt et al. (2022). Weighting the mean values shown in Table 4.6 by sample size results in weighted EMCs for TKN of 1.36 mg/L and nitrate-nitrite of 0.59 mg/L. Summing these values results in an estimated total nitrogen EMC of 1.95 mg/L.

Table 4.6. Event Mean Concentrations for Nitrogen Species Reported in the National Stormwater Quality Database by Pitt et al. (2018)

Constituent	Land Use(s) Reported by Permittees	N	Median (mg/L as N)	COV
TKN	freeway and residential	2,290	1.5	1.12
TKN	commercial, industrial, and institutional	2,028	1.2	2.28
NH3	freeways	88	0.9	1.44
NH3	commercial, industrial, institutional, and residential	1,821	0.3	1.51
NO2+NO3	freeways	115	1.2	0.96
NO2+NO3	commercial, industrial, open space, and residential	3,125	0.6	1.49
NO2+NO3	institutional	292	0.2	1.24

Assumed EMCs for total nitrogen in bioretention surface outflow were derived from a published analysis of data in the International Stormwater BMP Database (Water Research Foundation, 2020). This publication reported a median total nitrogen concentration in the effluent of 318 bioretention basins (reported by 25 unique studies) of 0.96 mg/L (95% confidence interval 0.815 – 1.06 mg/L). This value was multiplied by the simulated volume leaving bioretention through the surface pathway to estimate a mass load of total nitrogen in surface outflow.

4.2.3.3 Peak Flow

Three wet weather events during the 2003-2022 period were chosen to represent peak flow control objectives. From the analysis of historical data at Philadelphia International Airport published in NOAA Atlas 14 (Bonnin et al., 2006), historical means and 90% confidence intervals were identified for depth and peak hourly intensity of storms with 1-2 year expected return period and 24-hour duration. These values are provided in Appendix D. Events of this

magnitude were assumed to represent events likely to impact banks and channels in small streams. The 90% confidence intervals also were identified for depth and peak hourly intensity of storms with 10-25 year expected return period and 24-hour duration. Events of this magnitude were assumed to represent conditions likely to cause urban pluvial flooding with a risk to human life and property if left uncontrolled.

Next, wet weather events in the 2003-2022 watershed unit-area runoff record derived from McGauley et al. (2023) were examined to identify wet weather events falling within the 1-2 year return period range and within the 10-25 year return period range. Table 4.7 summarizes the selected events, and hyetographs of these events may be found in Appendix D.

Table 4.7. Wet Weather Events Selected to Represent Stream Channel Protection and Flood Control Objectives

Event	Start Time	End Time	Duration (hr)	Depth (watershed-mm)	Peak Intensity (watershed-mm/hr)
Channel Protection 1	2014-04-15 10:00	2014-04-16 00:00	14	73.9	32.5
Channel Protection 2	2018-04-15 12:00	2018-04-16 10:00	22	76.3	31.6
Flood Control	2021-09-01 15:00	2021-09-02 00:00	9	143	55.6

4.2.3.4 Plant Species Richness Index

An index of potential plant species richness for each design scenario was calculated by determining the number of plant species included in the master bioretention plant list (Chapter 3) that achieve at least a 0.75 score on a Plant Tolerance Index unique to the environmental conditions created by that design scenario. The overall Plant Tolerance Index is defined as the product of an Inundation Tolerance Index and a Drought Tolerance Index, both defined on a scale of 0 (least tolerant) to 1 (most tolerant). This concept is inspired by a framework used by biologists to characterize salmon tolerance to multiple environmental factors in the Pacific Northwest (Lestelle et al., 2004). Because it is multiplicative, a plant must be tolerant of

extremes of both wet and dry conditions present in a given basin over the course of a simulation to achieve a high overall score.

$$\text{Plant Tolerance Index} = \text{Ponding Tolerance Index} \times \text{Drought Tolerance Index}$$

where

Plant Tolerance Index indicates the tolerance of one plant to the time pattern of both wet and dry conditions created by one set of design conditions (0 = least suitable, 1 = most suitable),

Ponding Tolerance Index indicates the tolerance of one plant to the time pattern of surface ponding duration created by one set of design conditions (0 = least suitable, 1 = most suitable), and

Drought Tolerance Index indicates the tolerance of one plant to the time pattern of 10-day soil moisture deficit created by one set of design conditions (0 = least suitable, 1 = most suitable).

Environmental conditions created by particular design scenarios are characterized by results of the 20-year simulations, while tolerance of particular plant taxa to these environmental conditions is derived from literature information. Shaw and Schmidt (2003) provide quantitative information on ponding duration tolerance for over 100 bioretention plants. Figure 4.1 presents the information reported by Shaw and Schmidt (2003) categorized by wetland indicator ratings in the National Wetland Plant List (2020). These results indicate that plants rated as obligate (OBL) or facultative (FACW) wetland plants tend to tolerate ponding durations of at least 3-4 days. This ponding duration also represents a practical upper limit recommended in many bioretention design guidelines. Plants rated as facultative wetland (FAC), facultative upland (FACU), and upland (UPL) plants are adversely impacted at shorter ponding durations.

Figure 4.1. Histogram of Ponding Duration Tolerance for Bioretention Plants (Shaw and Schmidt, 2003)

The Shaw and Schmidt (2003) ponding duration tolerance information has been developed into curves (Figure 4.2) that can be used to screen the master list of bioretention plants

for suitability to ponding durations created by a particular design scenario. An important caveat is that this information is intended only for screening of the plant list in a planning or design context. The information should not be interpreted as a scientific prediction of plant survival probability.

Figure 4.2. Ponding Tolerance Curves Relating Ponding Duration to a Dimensionless Ponding Index

The ponding tolerance curves were developed through the following steps:

1. For plants in each inundation tolerance category, a mean and standard deviation were calculated for inundation tolerance durations given in Shaw and Schmidt (2003).
2. To create a probability density function within each tolerance category, a t-distribution was defined as a function of mean, standard deviation, and degrees of freedom ($n - 1$, where n is the number of plants included in each tolerance category).
3. The probability distribution functions were scaled so that their maximum values are equal to 1.

$$t_{scaled} = \frac{t}{\max(t)}$$

4. The inundation tolerance index was created within each tolerance category by setting all values to the left of the peak to 1.

$$(inundation\ tolerance\ index)_{category} = \begin{cases} 1.0, & x \leq x_{peak} \\ t_{scaled}, & x > x_{peak} \end{cases}$$

where

category is the inundation tolerance category for a given plant (low, medium, or high),

and

x_{peak} is the inundation duration in days corresponding to the peak of the probability density function for a given inundation tolerance category.

In Figure 4.2, the horizontal axis represents the ponding duration that will begin to cause stress in plants as dissolved oxygen in soil pores is depleted under saturated soil conditions. When applying this concept to plant screening, I chose to interpret this axis as the mean of the maximum ponding durations occurring during each year of the 20-year simulations. The plant screening results should be interpreted as an index appropriate for ranking of design alternatives by plant diversity they are able to support. The results should not be interpreted as a precise quantitative prediction of plant survival probability.

To screen the plant list for tolerance to drought conditions in the context of a particular design, I established a relationship between soil moisture deficit and a form of the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index, SPEI (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). The SPEI can be derived from a number of different distributions. I have chosen to use a normal distribution where SPEI is defined as the number of standard deviations below mean soil moisture deficit. The steps followed to develop this index are described below.

1. The bioretention inflow time series was divided by watershed impervious area, resulting in a proxy for rainfall. Hereafter, this result is referred to as the "rainfall only" scenario.
2. Bioretention inflow is also expressed per unit of bioretention surface area, representing concentrated runoff. Hereafter, this result is referred to below as the "runoff" scenario.
3. Soil moisture deficit is calculated as the daily difference between net inflow ("rainfall only") and PET (calculated using Hargreaves method). Net inflow is the surface inflow less surface outflow during each hourly time step, if any. The deficit is accumulated over a 10-day rolling period.
4. The number of standard deviations from the mean soil moisture deficit is calculated daily for the 10-day rolling sum. This establishes the relationship between 10-day soil moisture deficit and SPEI in the "rainfall only" condition. This relationship does not vary between design scenarios.
5. The 10-day soil moisture deficit calculations are repeated for the "runoff" scenario representing concentrated runoff for a particular design of interest. This time series varies between design scenarios.
6. The 10-day soil moisture deficit values for the "runoff" case are related to SPEI using the curve produced in the "rainfall only" case (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3. Relationship Between Soil Moisture Deficit (Standard Deviations Below the Mean) and 10-Day Soil Moisture Deficit

The SPEI is one component informing qualitative drought severity categories defined by U.S. Drought Monitor (Figure 4.4). U.S. Drought Monitor considers other criteria in addition to SPEI in assigning its drought categories. I have developed my drought classifications from the SPEI alone and have not included any other criteria used by U.S. Drought Monitor.

Category	Description	Example Percentile Range for Most Indicators	Values for Standard Precipitation Index and Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index
None	Normal or wet conditions	30.01 or Above	-0.49 or above
D0	Abnormally Dry	20.01 to 30.00	-0.5 to -0.79
D1	Moderate Drought	10.01 to 20.00	-0.8 to -1.29
D2	Severe Drought	5.01 to 10.00	-1.3 to -1.59
D3	Extreme Drought	2.01 to 5.00	-1.6 to -1.99
D4	Exceptional Drought	0.00 to 2.00	-2.0 or less

Figure 4.4. Categories Used by U.S. Drought Monitor (Source: droughtmonitor.unl.edu)

Curves relating minimum annual 10-day soil moisture deficit to the Drought Tolerance Index are displayed in Figure 4.5. Like the ponding tolerance curves, these curves should be used only to screen the plant list in a planning/design context.

Figure 4.5. Relationship Between Soil Moisture Deficit (Standard Deviations Below the Mean) and Dimensionless Drought Tolerance Index

The curves in Figure 4.5 were developed as follows. First, a lower limit is defined for each drought tolerance category, representing a minimum (most negative) 10-day soil moisture deficit which plants in that category are able to withstand. This logic is consistent with values used by U.S. Drought Monitor.

$$\mu = \begin{cases} -0.6, & \text{for low drought tolerance} \\ -1.3, & \text{for moderate drought tolerance} \\ -2.0, & \text{for high drought tolerance} \end{cases}$$

where

μ is the lower (most negative) limit 10-day soil moisture deficit for the tolerance range of interest, expressed in terms of standard deviations below mean 10-day soil moisture deficit for the "rainfall-only" case.

Second, a normal probability density function is defined to create a curve within each tolerance category.

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

where

σ is a standard deviation chosen by judgment of the researcher to assign a range to each curve, here set to 0.2, and

x is the 10-day soil moisture deficit at any given time.

Next, the probability distribution functions are scaled so that their maximum values are equal to 1.

$$\Phi_{scaled} = \frac{\Phi}{\max(\Phi)}$$

Finally, the drought index is created within each tolerance category by setting all values to the right of the peak to 1.

$$(\text{drought tolerance index})_{category} = \begin{cases} \Phi_{scaled}, & x < x_{peak} \\ 1.0, & x \geq x_{peak} \end{cases}$$

where

category is the drought tolerance category for a given plant (low, medium, or high), and x_{peak} is the 10-day soil moisture deficit corresponding to the peak of the probability density function for a given drought tolerance category.

4.2.3.5 Plant and Lepidoptera Species Richness

An index of potential *Lepidoptera* species richness was developed, representing the estimated number of *Lepidoptera* species that can be supported if at least one example of each genus is present for all host plants identified as suitable for environmental conditions.

First, the plants identified as suitable for the system (see Section 4.2.3.4) are sorted in order of largest overall tolerance index to smallest tolerance index. Second, the genus of the first plant in the list is matched to the total *Lepidoptera* species richness supported in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania according to Narango (2020). The host plant genus also is matched to the scientific names of unique insect species supported by that genus according to the HOSTS

database (Chapter 3). The genus of the second plant on the list is then matched to the scientific names of insects supported according to HOSTS, but only insects not supported by the first plant on the list are retained. The algorithm proceeds through each plant in the list in this manner so that the incremental species richness added by each species is determined. Next, the incremental contribution of each plant species is scaled to a percentage. The data are then scaled so that the *Lepidoptera* species richness supported by the first plant on the list matches that reported by Narango (2020), and species richness supported by all other plant host species in the list are scaled accordingly.

The intention of this work was to provide a framework that may be used to analyze plant choice against bioretention basin design, and an example was used to illustrate this framework. It is acknowledged that the numerical modeling approach represented a simplified one-dimensional representation of a bioretention basin. Each model simulation included one type of plant with one root depth and one value of leaf area index. Development of the plant richness index was not constrained by these root depth and leaf area index assumptions made in the simulations for each design scenario. For example, trees, shrubs, and herbaceous species were all included in the screening results even if the root depth and leaf area index assumed in a given scenario would imply an herbaceous species only. This choice was made because while the simplified model representation provides valuable insights into system behavior, a real implemented bioretention basin will contain heterogeneous soil, plant, and topographic conditions not represented in these simulations.

4.2.4 Correlation and Tradeoff Analysis

4.2.4.1 Correlation

Correlations between performance measures were computed according to the Pearson method, providing information on the presence and strength of linear relationships between

variables. Correlations were calculated between each pair of the variables listed in Figure 4.6. For water budget components, inputs to the analysis were expressed in units of depth over the watershed impervious surface area, allowing fair comparisons between design alternatives with different ratios of watershed to basin surface area. For total nitrogen load comparisons, loads were expressed in units of mass per unit of watershed impervious surface area.

Figure 4.6. Performance Measures Included in Correlation Analysis

With the exception of the event-based measures, correlations were computed using the mean of annual values for each metric resulting from the 18 simulations representing different design choices and underlying soil conditions. Temporal autocorrelations for individual metrics at the annual time scale were assumed to be negligible.

4.2.4.2 Hypothesis Testing

The purpose of hypothesis testing is to examine any evidence that it is necessary to accept a decrease in "traditional" engineering measures of water resources management in order to achieve increases in plant species richness or *Lepidoptera* species richness for a given design scenario. Testing results may help identify a set of design characteristics (e.g., surface area, hydraulic configuration, engineered soil properties) that avoid or minimize these tradeoffs, allowing the designer to maximize performance across both traditional and ecological objectives.

The hypotheses to be tested can first be stated in a general form. The alternative hypothesis (H_a) states that an improvement in a terrestrial ecological performance measure requires acceptance of a change in a traditional water resources management objective. Whether an increase or decrease represents an improved value of the traditional objective depends on the specific objective and measurement convention. The null hypothesis (H_0) states that there is no relationship between the terrestrial ecological performance measure and the traditional water resources management objective. Table 4.8 states each hypothesis in a form that can be tested using formal statistical inference.

Hypotheses were tested by performing a linear regression with the ecological measure as the explanatory variable (horizontal axis) and the traditional engineering water resources management measure as the response variable (vertical axis). The null hypothesis was rejected if the slope of the regression line was found to be significantly different than 0 at the 95% confidence level (probability value for t statistic ≤ 0.05).

Table 4.8. Tradeoff Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Relationship	Alternative Hypothesis (H _a)	Null Hypothesis (H ₀)
1	Plant species richness vs. surface outflow	An increase in plant species richness index requires acceptance of a change in surface outflow volume.	There is no relationship between plant species richness index and surface outflow volume.
2	Plant species richness vs. groundwater recharge	An increase in plant species richness index requires acceptance of a change in groundwater recharge.	There is no relationship between plant species richness index and groundwater recharge volume.
3	Plant species richness vs. evapotranspiration	An increase in plant species richness index requires acceptance of a change in evapotranspiration.	There is no relationship between plant species richness index and evapotranspiration volume.
4	Plant species richness vs. channel protection	An increase in plant species richness index requires acceptance of a change in mean peak flow reduction for two selected 1-2 year return period storms.	There is no relationship between plant species richness index and mean peak flow reduction for two selected 1-2 year return period storms.
5	Plant species richness vs. flood peak control	An increase in plant species richness index requires acceptance of a change in peak flow reduction for a selected 10-25 year return period storm.	There is no relationship between plant species richness index and peak flow reduction for a selected 10-25 year return period storm.
6	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. surface outflow	An increase in <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index requires acceptance of a change in surface outflow volume.	There is no relationship between <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index and surface outflow volume.
7	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. groundwater recharge	An increase in <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index requires acceptance of a change in groundwater recharge.	There is no relationship between <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index and groundwater recharge volume.
8	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. evapotranspiration	An increase in <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index requires acceptance of a change in evapotranspiration.	There is no relationship between <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index and evapotranspiration volume.
9	<i>Lepidoptera</i> richness vs. channel protection	An increase in <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index requires acceptance of a change in mean peak flow reduction for two selected 1-2 year return period storms.	There is no relationship between <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index and mean peak flow reduction for two selected 1-2 year return period storms.
10	<i>Lepidoptera</i> richness vs. flood peak control	An increase in <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index requires acceptance of a change in peak flow reduction for a selected 10-25 year return period storm.	There is no relationship between <i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness index and peak flow reduction for a selected 10-25 year return period storm.

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Model Validation

Figure 4.7 is one example comparing observed and simulated time series for July 2018. Visually, the simulated timing of rainfall response and the hydrograph shapes fit the observed data closely. While the observations include water levels above the weir elevation during larger events, the Hydrus maximum ponding level does not exceed the overflow elevation as expected. For smaller wet weather events such as the ones on July 6 and July 15, simulated peak water level is less than observed water level. Water level recession rates following cessation of inflow

appear similar to observed rates for the larger events and greater than observed rates for the smaller events. The timing and magnitude of simulated volumetric water content is similar to observed values derived for tensiometer data. At 10 cm depth, the rate of soil drying indicated by simulation results is slower than that indicated by the tensiometer data, while at 35 cm depth the rates are a good match and at 65 cm the rate is faster. Given uncertainty in soil properties and field measurements of tension in soil pores, visual inspection of these results suggests that the simulated system behavior is consistent with behavior indicated by the field measurements.

Figure 4.8 through Figure 4.10 summarize observed-simulated value comparisons visually, while Table 4.9 presents the final quantitative calibration metrics for the simulation selected as best representing the physical system behavior. The percent bias results indicate that water level recession rate and minimum soil water content are relatively unbiased (within 5% of the line of equal fit). Results for peak water level are biased (observed greater than simulated because the one-dimensional assumption of constant depth-volume relationship does not hold for small volumes). Events with observed peak levels less than 15 cm have been excluded from the analysis, and excluding additional small events would reduce the calculated bias.

Figure 4.7. Example Comparison of Observed and Simulated Time Series for the BTI, July 2018

RMSE for the minimum water content results indicates both a close fit and a low degree of scatter relative to observed values. Although the results for recession rate are relatively

unbiased, RMSE is affected by both positive and negative outlier events. NSE values for water content at 10 cm and 35 cm depths indicate both a close fit and minimal scatter about the line of equal fit. NSE for soil moisture at 65 cm depth and for peak water level is low because the results are biased, while NSE for recession rate is low due to scatter about the line of equal fit, even though the results are relatively unbiased.

Table 4.9. Calibration Metrics

Variable	Percent Bias	RMSE	NSE
wet event peak level (cm) ¹	31.6	11.5	-0.565
wet event level mean recession rate (cm/hr) ²	-2.81	0.777	-2.26
dry event minimum water content (10 cm depth) ³	1.09	0.0287	0.441
dry event minimum water content (35 cm depth) ³	-0.177	0.0194	0.610
dry event minimum water content (65 cm depth) ³	-4.52	0.0481	-1.03

- 1: peak water level during each wet weather event selected for calibration
- 2: water level at observed cessation of rainfall divided by time from observed cessation of rainfall to time when observed water level drops below 1 cm, for each wet weather event selected for calibration
- 3: volumetric soil water content at the end of each (dry) interevent period during the calibration period

Figure 4.8. Comparison of Observed and Simulated Peak Water Level for Validation Events

Figure 4.9. Comparison of Observed and Simulated Mean Water Level Recession Rates for Validation Events

Figure 4.10. Comparison of Observed and Simulated Minimum Volumetric Water Content at 10 cm Depth for Dry Weather Validation Events

Using the definition of Rykiel (1996), the results presented in this section demonstrate that this “model within its domain of applicability possesses a satisfactory range of accuracy consistent with the intended application of the model.” The Hydrus 1D framework is an

appropriate choice because it acceptably represents all the hydrologic processes needed to meet the stated objectives of this study. Overall, the visual results and quantitative calibration metrics demonstrate a good balance between fitting a variety of performance measures using a variety of quantitative metrics. The excellent fit and low scatter for minimum soil water content at 10 cm and 35 cm depth indicates that physical soil properties affecting drying have been appropriately represented at these depths. Fitting soil water content accurately at multiple depths is known to be a challenge in the Hydrus framework due to the many parameters involved in root water uptake and partitioning between evaporation and transpiration (Sutanto et al., 2012; Tue et al., 2020). The low bias in mean water level recession rate also indicates that soil properties have been appropriately captured. The relatively high bias in peak water level is acceptable because the results demonstrate good agreement with observations during larger storms, where the one-dimensional depth-volume assumption can be assumed to hold. This result is acceptable because the stated objective of the model framework is to test and distinguish between the performance of multiple hypothetical bioretention designs of the same general type as the BTI, and not to replicate the observed behavior of the BTI itself as precisely as possible.

4.3.2 Water Balance Components

Mean annual unit-area runoff (a proxy for rainfall) derived from the McGauley et al. (2023) time series for the period 2003-2022 was 1196 mm with a range of 719 mm in 2017 to 1727 mm in 2011 (Table 4.10). Defining unique events as those separated by a minimum period of six hours with zero runoff, the cumulative distribution of event depths is shown in Figure 4.11. The median dry period duration was 56 hours (2.3 days), while the mean dry period duration was 84 hours (3.5 days), reflecting the right-skewed distribution of dry period durations and the influence of outliers on the mean. The longest dry period in this record is 1042 hours (43 days) lasting from October 9 to November 21, 2008.

Table 4.10. Unit-Area Runoff from BTI Watershed Impervious Surface Area, Derived from McGauley et al. (2023)

Year	Runoff (watershed-mm)
2003	1,330
2004	1,459
2005	1,193
2006	1,407
2007	1,272
2008	907
2009	1,325
2010	1,180
2011	1,727
2012	972
2013	1,353
2014	1,177
2015	930
2016	820
2017	719
2018	1,569
2019	1,245
2020	1,327
2021	1,013
2022	986

Figure 4.11. Cumulative Distribution of Wet Weather Event Depths (Watershed Unit-Area Inflow)

Figure 4.12 summarizes the simulated mean annual hydrologic cycle components for each of the 18 design scenarios. Not included in Figure 4.12 are inflow, change in storage, and

computational error. The scenarios have the same annual unit-area inflow depth within a small rounding error (< 1 cm). Mean annual change in storage is very small (< 1 mm), and mean annual computational error ranges from 0.64 to 2.35 watershed-cm across the 18 simulations.

Some observations can be made from examination of Figure 4.12. The reduction in annual surface outflow volume relative to inflow is substantial (77-83%) across all scenarios. Flux to groundwater is the dominant process accounting for reduction of surface outflow as a fraction of inflow (67-79%) across all scenarios. Evaporation and transpiration also remove significant volumes (5-15% of inflow), and these processes account for more volume in scenarios with larger bioretention surface areas (i.e., smaller ratios of watershed area to bioretention area). In scenarios where evaporation and transpiration are larger components of the water budget, groundwater recharge is a smaller component indicating that some volume that would otherwise have reached groundwater has been transferred to the atmosphere.

Figure 4.12. Simulated 20-Year Mean Annual Water Budget Components Across Design Scenarios

The 18-year water budget values reported for Villanova's Bioretention Traffic Island (BTI) by McGauley et al. (2023) can be compared to simulated results for Scenario 9, the most similar design. Surface outflow as a percent of inflow is similar between the Scenario 9 Hydrus simulation (22%) and the value reported by McGauley et al. (26%). This value is also similar to the range reported in the literature surveyed by McGauley et al. for low-intensity development (7-28% with a median of 21% across six sources). The sum of evapotranspiration and groundwater recharge is similar between the two analyses, but the Hydrus simulation results in a greater proportion of inflow transmitting to groundwater rather than evapotranspiration (72% and 5% respectively). From the McGauley et al. estimate, 54% of inflow is transmitted to groundwater and 19% to evapotranspiration. It would be possible to adjust the Hydrus model configuration to better match the McGauley results, for example by setting a much lower wilting point value for the roots, but this would result in a worsening of the quantitative calibration metrics when the model has been judged fit for its intended purpose.

4.3.3 Total Nitrogen Loads

Influent and effluent total nitrogen loads are depicted in Figure 4.13, sorted from greatest mean annual effluent load (worst performance) on the left to smallest effluent load (best performance) on the right. Because a constant effluent total nitrogen concentration was assumed, the reduction in total nitrogen follows the same trend as the difference between surface inflow and surface outflow. All designs provide effective pollutant load reductions in surface outflow relative to inflow. The results fall into four groupings. The first grouping (scenarios 9, 3, 6, 18, 12, and 15), representing the greatest median effluent pollutant loads, has small bioretention areas relative to watershed area (15:1 watershed:bioretention area ratio) and moderate (49 cm) maximum ponding depths. The second (scenarios 7, 1, and 4) and third (scenarios 16, 10, and 13) groupings have slightly greater median removal rates. These groupings include all the

scenarios with the largest bioretention areas relative to the watershed area. Different soil types explain the presence of annual loads designated as outliers (distance from the 75th percentile greater than 1.5 times the interquartile range) in the third grouping compared to the second grouping. The final grouping (scenarios 17, 11, 14, 8, 2, and 5) has small bioretention surface areas but allows the greatest surface ponding depth of 73 cm. These results confirm that some design choices that tend to minimize surface outflow and its attendant pollutant loads are (1) larger bioretention surface areas relative to watershed area and (2) larger surface ponding depths. It is important to note that many regulatory jurisdictions place limits on maximum duration of surface ponding that is considered acceptable, and these regulations may preclude the design choices represented in the third grouping for some jurisdictions.

Figure 4.13. Interannual Variability of Total Nitrogen Loads by Scenario

4.3.4 Peak Flow

Each of the design scenarios results in a substantial reduction in hourly peak flow (66-84%) for the two events chosen to represent a stream channel protection objective. Larger reductions correspond closely to surface storage volumes in each of the designs, an intuitive

result. Peak flow reductions for the storm chosen to represent a flood protection objective are modest, and the set of design alternatives represented in this study is not an ideal design for providing flood protection without further modification. Among the modest reductions, designs with larger bioretention surface areas relative to watershed area consistently provide slightly better results regardless of total surface storage volume present. A possible physical explanation for this behavior is that more surface storage capacity is available at the peak of this storm in the scenarios with greater surface areas. The peak of the selected storm occurs relatively late in the event, and this hyetograph shape will allow more significant infiltration to occur in scenarios with greater areas open to infiltration. Because this result depends on the timing of the peak, it is specific to the storm studied and cannot be generalized to other storms of similar magnitude but different time patterns. This result is consistent with results reported by Amur et al. (2022, 2024), who found that the timing of peak inflow during an event can have a substantial impact on bioretention basin performance.

4.3.5 Plant Species Richness

Figure 4.14 presents the results of the plant species richness calculations. The number of plants passing the selected screening threshold (a score of at least 0.75 out of a maximum 1.0 in the tolerance index) ranged from a low of 25 to a high of 156 across the scenarios. The scenarios supporting the greatest potential plant diversity have the largest bioretention areas relative to surface area, the lowest maximum ponding volumes, and the greatest overall engineered soil volumes among the scenarios. This combination of design choices creates a time pattern of soil moisture conditions that tends to have soil water contents closer to the lower limit of the range among the scenarios studied. Appendix E presents additional data related to Figure 4.14.

Table 4.11. Peak Flow Reduction Provided by Each Design Scenario

Scenario	Percent Reduction in Peak Hour Flow	
	Channel Protection Events (Mean)	Flood Protection Event
1	66.5	4.69
2	82.4	3.00
3	69.0	2.34
4	66.7	5.13
5	82.4	2.67
6	68.7	2.55
7	66.0	5.03
8	82.2	3.05
9	68.5	2.60
10	70.7	5.44
11	83.7	1.67
12	69.9	1.98
13	71.1	5.42
14	83.8	1.68
15	69.6	1.95
16	69.2	5.36
17	83.7	1.66
18	69.1	1.98

Figure 4.14. Plant Species Richness Index by Scenario

4.3.6 *Lepidoptera* Species Richness

Figure 4.15 presents the *Lepidoptera* species richness index for each of the 18 scenarios.

The 18 design scenarios result in three distinct levels of *Lepidoptera* richness and follow the

same groupings as the plant richness result. Examining these groupings more closely, the first grouping, supporting the greatest plant and *Lepidoptera* richness, includes all the scenarios with five units of watershed area per unit of bioretention area. These scenarios represent the “dryer” scenarios and are consistent with findings in the plant section that dryer conditions can support greater biodiversity in terms of both plants and insects. These findings are significant considering that the master plant list contains more plant recommendations adapted to relatively wet conditions than to relatively dry conditions (Table 3.5). The second and third groupings include all the scenarios with a 15:1 ratio of watershed to bioretention area. The difference between the second and third groupings is explained by a specific combination of soil conditions. If the underlying soil is less permeable (second soil type with a saturated hydraulic conductivity of 0.76 cm/hr), the engineered soil must be deeper (122 cm vs. 61 cm) in order to support greater biodiversity. If the underlying soil is more permeable (first soil type with a saturated hydraulic conductivity of 1.00 cm/hr), the engineered soil can be less deep and still support the intermediate level of biodiversity. Considering the plant and *Lepidoptera* richness results together, three design implications are suggested. The first is that maximizing bioretention soil footprint, where this is feasible in urban environments, will tend to support a wider range of both plants and insects. The second is that a deeper layer of engineered soil can help compensate for a relatively impermeable underlying soil layer in terms of providing larval host plant support for *Lepidoptera* species. The third is that a greater allowable maximum ponding depth, while it may help compensate for a smaller bioretention footprint in space-constrained urban environments, results in wetter soil conditions over time that tend to preclude some plant genera of benefit to the terrestrial ecosystem.

Figure 4.15. *Lepidoptera* Species Richness Index by Scenario

4.3.7 Correlation Analysis

Correlations between metrics (Figure 4.16) provide some insights into which metrics may be appropriate for inclusion in an index to inform decisions between planning and design alternatives. First, as expected with an EMC approach, surface outflow and pollutant loads in surface outflow are perfectly correlated, and including both of these measures in an index would not provide additional information compared to selecting one of them. Second, ponding duration is strongly correlated with groundwater recharge. This observation is useful because many simulation tools commonly used in urban planning and design (e.g., EPA SWMM) are effective at calculating rainfall-runoff responses but are less effective at partitioning hydrologic losses into evaporation, transpiration, and groundwater recharge. Most tools are effective at predicting a time series of water level. The results presented here suggest that ponding duration may be a suitable proxy for groundwater recharge in a simplified decision making context. This conclusion is specific to designs that do not include an underdrain. Third, the channel protection index also is strongly correlated with ponding duration. Fourth, the results suggest that SPEI is a suitable proxy for evapotranspiration. Fifth, plant richness and butterfly (*Lepidoptera*) richness are found

to be highly correlated. However, it is worth including both of these indices in any ecological performance index because a planner or designer can calculate the *Lepidoptera* richness index projected for the exact plant taxa being considered in a given design. Doing so may yield additional insights compared to the broader index based on the list of all plants suitable for the environmental conditions.

Figure 4.16. Pearson Correlation Between Performance Measures

Figure 4.17. Relationships Between Engineering and Ecological Variables

4.3.8 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing results corresponding to the relationships shown in Figure 4.17 are summarized in Table 4.12. No significant relationship was found at the 5% level between surface outflow volume and either plant species richness or *Lepidoptera* species richness. A significant negative relationship was found between both plant and *Lepidoptera* species richness and groundwater recharge. Significant positive relationships were found between species richness and evapotranspiration. These results are consistent with findings presented throughout this chapter indicating that many bioretention plants considered are sensitive to prolonged periods of inundation. The results suggest that to maximize biodiversity, bioretention systems need sufficient soil drying to occur in order to maintain unsaturated conditions between most wet weather events. These findings suggest that designs that maximize surface area relative to watershed area and include relatively deep and permeable soils will promote more biodiversity. These design choices are generally consistent with recommendations intended to manage the hydrologic cycle and protect downstream aquatic ecosystems in the humid Mid-Atlantic and Midwest U.S. states.

Of interest, a significant negative relationship was found between the biodiversity measures and measures designed to protect stream channels from erosion. A significant positive relationship was found between the biodiversity measures and the flood protection measure, although it is important to note that the flood protection benefit of the range of bioretention designs included in this study is modest. More complex design features such as multi-stage outlet structures and spillover to supplementary storage elements during large storms may be able to meet these peak flow objectives without sacrificing either water quality or biodiversity objectives. These design variations were beyond the scope of the current study and could be considered in future research.

Table 4.12. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Slope	P Value	Test Result
1	Plant species richness vs. surface outflow	-0.0053	6.95E-01	do not reject
2	Plant species richness vs. groundwater recharge	-0.0864	1.07E-06	reject
3	Plant species richness vs. evapotranspiration	0.1014	6.72E-11	reject
4	Plant species richness vs. channel protection	-0.0873	3.86E-03	reject
5	Plant species richness vs. flood peak control	0.0277	1.18E-11	reject
6	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. surface outflow	-0.0001	9.72E-01	do not reject
7	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. groundwater recharge	-0.0154	7.59E-07	reject
8	<i>Lepidoptera</i> species richness vs. evapotranspiration	0.0171	6.18E-08	reject
9	<i>Lepidoptera</i> richness vs. channel protection	-0.0166	1.37E-03	reject
10	<i>Lepidoptera</i> richness vs. flood peak control	0.0048	8.64E-10	reject

4.4 Conclusions and Engineering Applications

The results discussed throughout this chapter can inform choices of bioretention planners and designers. In professional practice, it is common for water resource engineering projects to prioritize only one or two objectives. These priority objectives are often driven by legal requirements, such as the water quality-based requirements of the Clean Water Act in the United States or the habitat loss mitigation requirements of the Federal Act on the Protection of Waters in Switzerland. Improved approaches to multiple-objective design have been discussed in the academic literature and in professional practice for several decades with limited progress (Cook et al., 2024).

One way professionals can consider multiple objectives is through a stakeholder-informed alternative scoring and ranking process that assigns weights to performance criteria, which are in turn tied to explicitly defined objectives (e.g., Keeney, 1996; Lacroix et al., 2024). Different project sponsors and stakeholders may have a variety of objectives and values that inform their preferred choices.

Table 4.13 illustrates weight sets that might be preferred by four different hypothetical stakeholders on the bioretention design project discussed throughout this chapter. Ultimately, these stakeholders might prefer different design scenarios as illustrated by the rankings in Table 4.13.

To calculate the values in Table 4.13, results for each performance objective were transformed on a linear scale where 0 represented the worst result across the eighteen objectives and 1 represented the best result across the eighteen objectives. For example, plant richness values of 25, 61, and 156 were assigned scaled ratings of 0, 0.27, and 1 respectively. Each of these scaled values was then multiplied by the weight assigned to plant richness by an individual hypothetical stakeholder. The resulting weighted ratings for each of the five performance measures were summed for each design scenario and for each stakeholder to result in a weighted rating for each design scenario and for each stakeholder. For each stakeholder, design scenarios were ranked from 1 (highest composite weighted score) to 18 (lowest composite weighted score).

In this example, if the terrestrial ecosystem-focused stakeholder were not involved in the decision, the group might come to a consensus on scenarios 2, 5, 8, 11, or 14, which always appear in the top five most preferred scenarios. However, the terrestrial ecosystem focused stakeholder may resist agreeing on this choice, preferring scenarios 10, 13, or 16 which maximize plant and insect biodiversity. In a real design scenario, it may be unlikely that any one stakeholder would have such an extreme preference. This hypothetical scenario is meant to illustrate how adding terrestrial ecosystem functional objectives to the decision making process may influence the outcome. It is also important to acknowledge that in a real design scenario, cost-effectiveness and other constraints could play an important role in the ultimate decision, and some stakeholders (e.g., the land owner or project financial sponsor) may have a more powerful say in the final choice than others. Nonetheless, these results illustrate how injecting quantitative terrestrial ecosystem objectives and criteria may be able to influence and improve urban ecological function.

Table 4.13. Weights Assigned to a Decision Framework Preferred by Four Hypothetical Stakeholders with Different Priorities

Stakeholder Focus	Performance Metric				
	groundwater recharge volume	surface outflow / effluent pollutant load	channel protection event peak reduction	plant diversity	butterfly diversity
Balanced	33%	17%	17%	17%	17%
Groundwater Recharge	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
Aquatic Ecosystem Protection	10%	40%	40%	5%	5%
Terrestrial Ecosystem Enhancement	10%	5%	5%	40%	40%

Table 4.14. Alternative Ranks Preferred by Four Hypothetical Design Stakeholders

Ranking	Scenario			
	Balanced Focus	Groundwater Recharge Focus	Aquatic Ecosystem Focus	Terrestrial Ecosystem Focus
1	2	11	11	10
2	8	2	2	13
3	5	8	5	16
4	11	5	14	1
5	14	14	8	4
6	17	17	17	7
7	10	12	13	2
8	13	15	10	8
9	16	18	16	5
10	4	3	4	12
11	7	6	1	15
12	1	9	7	18
13	12	10	12	3
14	15	13	15	6
15	18	16	18	9
16	3	1	3	11
17	6	4	6	14
18	9	7	9	17

To demonstrate how this framework may be applied, the numerical modeling approach represented a simplified one-dimensional representation of a bioretention basin. Development of the plant richness index was not constrained by root depth and leaf area index assumptions made in the simulations for each design scenario. This choice was made because while the simplified model representation provides valuable insights into system behavior, a real implemented bioretention basin will contain heterogeneous soil, plant, and topographic conditions not represented in these simulations.

The conclusions and applications discussed here are limited to the effects of two environmental conditions, the time patterns of surface ponding and dry periods, on performance measures, which were chosen to demonstrate the framework. The framework presented can be extended to additional environmental conditions that affect bioretention plants and bioretention performance. For example, loads of deicing salts and their effects on plants are important factors in cold climates and could be added to the framework. The direct physiological effects of increased temperatures and duration of future heat waves could be added to this quantitative framework, in addition to the effects of temperature on evapotranspiration and soil moisture which have been considered in the current analysis. Finally, intense urban runoff can cause soil erosion and damage to more fragile plants within bioretention basins. Where these effects cannot be remediated through hydraulic design elements such as energy dissipation structures, future research can develop methods to add these direct physical impacts as additional factors in the quantitative tolerance equation.

CHAPTER 5. Selecting an Ensemble of Global Circulation Models to Explore End-of-Century Bioretention Performance

5.1 Introduction

This chapter demonstrates one practical approach to selection of appropriate ensembles of global circulation models (GCMs) for use in urban water resources engineering applications including watershed and stormwater management. Typically, engineers engaged in planning and design need time series of projected precipitation to serve as boundary conditions for simulations and design calculations. The results of these simulations and calculations in turn provide information on the projected effectiveness of water resources infrastructure in meeting its stated objectives. Ensemble selection can be tailored to the specific objectives of a particular planning or design project. For example, a bioretention project focused on urban runoff management might prioritize projections made by models shown to agree with observed monthly precipitation totals for the geographic region where the project is being implemented. Conversely, a study focused on drought resilience might prioritize projections from GCMs that are shown to agree with the time pattern of historical dry periods for the geographic region of interest.

A key objective of the analysis was to investigate whether there is a set of common quantitative metrics used in the literature to compare GCM outputs to observed precipitation data. Another objective was to evaluate whether a subset of the metrics identified would be appropriate for evaluation and selection of GCM outputs to serve as hydrologic boundary conditions in urban water resources planning and management applications, such as bioretention design. While these metrics may have a variety of uses, I use the metrics in the current analysis to compare GCM outputs to benchmark values and to inform selection of a GCM ensemble that is appropriate for derivation of boundary conditions for simulations and design calculations. To carry out this evaluation, I developed a set of performance objectives for an example water

resources application. I then demonstrated how this set of metrics can be weighted to select a GCM model ensemble tailored to the specific water resources engineering project.

I provide an example weight set illustrating how the selection of a relatively small ensemble (10 models) can be tailored to the objectives of an urban stormwater engineering design incorporating soil and vegetation, such as a bioretention basin. I then visualize the distribution of daily precipitation and dry period duration for the selected ensemble for the projected period 2081-2100 compared to the historical period 1995-2014. My case study applies the steps to GCM projections relevant to the U.S. state of Pennsylvania, located in the Mid-Atlantic region. The proposed method is intended to be appropriate for practicing engineers to employ on planning and design projects with a degree of effort that is acceptable in a business context.

The skill with which individual CMIP6 models represent historical rainfall for specific geographic regions has been reported in the literature. For example, Donat et al. (2023) reported that CMIP6 models represent historical precipitation trends with an acceptable degree of skill for much of Europe, Asia, Northeastern North America, portions of South America, and Western Australia. Western North America and portions of Africa were identified by Donat et al. (2023) as regions where CMIP6 models match historical precipitation data less skillfully. Donat et al. (2023) employed the R package *Climpact* which standardized calculation of a set of weather extreme metrics documented by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Expert Team on Climate Information for Decision-making.

Feng et al. (2023) also employ a subset of the indices developed by the WMO Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices to evaluate outputs of 23 CMIP6 models relative to an observed data set. These included total precipitation, daily intensity, number of heavy rain

days (> 20 mm), maximum 1-day precipitation, and number of consecutive dry days. They present their results as Taylor diagrams, heat maps, and choropleth maps. They note “marked uncertainties” in predictions for South America.

Akinsanola et al. (2020) compared daily precipitation simulated by 16 CMIP6 models to three gridded observation data sets for summer (JJA) and winter (DJF) precipitation. Metrics employed included daily intensity, consecutive dry days, consecutive wet days, total precipitation, heavy precipitation days (> 10 mm), very heavy precipitation days (> 20 mm), maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation, very wet days (95th percentile and above), and extremely wet days (99th percentile and above). These indices were selected from recommendations of the Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices (Klein Tank et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2011). For each model-observation pair, they reported percentage bias, normalized root mean square error, and pattern correlation coefficient in a qualitative format.

5.2 Data and Methods

5.2.1 Overview of Methods

The steps employed in this study were as follows. First, I identified studies in the literature that provide quantitative data comparing GCM precipitation projections against benchmarks. Second, I normalized the result of each projection-benchmark comparison to a common scale. Third, I developed an example weight set representing the priorities of a hypothetical engineering project, and I then developed an index combining the projection-benchmark comparisons and the weight set. I used this index to rate and rank a set of GCMs and identified a subset that is appropriate for use on the example project. For the subset of ten models, I collaborated with others in the Villanova Center for Resilient Water Systems to download daily GCM outputs for a geographic region centered on Southeast Pennsylvania, USA. I characterized the statistical properties of precipitation projected by the individual models and

model ensemble mean for the AR6 scenario SSP5-8.5 and the time period 2081-2100. The aim of these steps was to identify a time series of projected precipitation that can be used for water resources planning and the design of water resources infrastructure that will be in service near the end of the century.

5.2.2 Data Set Description

I identified four studies that calculated quantitative metrics comparing GCM outputs to precipitation benchmarks and posted relevant quantitative information. The authors of these studies either published their results in an open source format or identified an open source repository of the information used to derive their results. Benchmarks varied by author and consisted either of field/remote sensing observations or of calculated model ensemble means.

Ahn et al. (2023) evaluated historical precipitation output of 36 CMIP6 models and compared to 6 gridded remote sensing-based data sets: IMERG, TRMM, CMORPH, GPCP, PERSIANN, and ERA5. The geographic scale of this analysis was the AR6 evaluation regions (e.g., Eastern North America). The calculations of Ahn et al. (2023) were based on an open source data set maintained by the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (PCMDI, 2024). For my own analyses, I have drawn my source information directly from information in this database as of July 2024.

The United States Geological Service has developed an internet-based tool, the National Climate Change Viewer that provides access and visualization of precipitation data projected by 27 CMIP6 models statistically downscaled using the LOCA2 methodology (Alder, 2014). The user can choose to area-weight results within geographic units provided by the USGS Watershed Boundary data set. Metrics provided include the projected change in precipitation between historical conditions and future conditions under Shared Socioeconomic Pathways considered under the CMIP6 framework.

Xue and Ullrich (2021) evaluated results of 33 CMIP6 models using metrics specifically focused on drought conditions. They compared model results to the NOAA CPC Unified Gauge-Based Analysis observed precipitation data set. Their analysis focused on three U.S. geographic regions: the New England, Lower Mississippi, and California regions.

Mahony et al. (2022) evaluated results of 33 CMIP6 models downscaled using the LOCA2 method. While these authors evaluated bias in projected values compared to historical precipitation data, they also applied a range of more qualitative criteria intended to avoid biases and localized spatial anomalies in model results. Their criteria resulted in a recommended ensemble of 13 models they consider to be most appropriate for applications in North America. They further provided a ranking of 8 models ranked in order of preference for each AR6 region.

5.2.3 Comparison and Scaling of GCM Precipitation Metrics in the Literature to Relevant Benchmarks

To gauge the accuracy of precipitation projections from a range of global circulation models, I compared a set of published metrics derived from these outputs to a set of benchmarks and transformed the results to a common scale. Table 5.1 presents the list of metrics selected for my case study. The range of metrics discussed includes a set that benchmark accuracy under “typical” hydrologic conditions, defined as conditions with mean recurrence on a monthly or seasonal time scale. The list also includes metrics that characterize extremes of both dry and wet conditions, where thresholds for extremes are defined by each individual source as documented in Table 5.1. The benchmarks employed vary by source study and include precipitation observations, mean values across multi-model ensembles, and qualitative criteria.

Table 5.1. Selected Metrics Employed in the Literature to Characterize Accuracy of GCM Precipitation Outputs Relative to Benchmarks

Source	Benchmark	Abbreviation	Type	Description
Anh et al. 2023	6 historical observed data sets (IMERG, TRMM, CMORPH, GPCP, PERSIANN, ERA5)	amtP10_ANN	dry extreme	fraction of annual precipitation in the bottom 10th percentile
		amtP90_ANN	wet extreme	fraction of annual precipitation at or above the 90th percentile
		amtpeak_ANN	wet extreme	rain rate at which maximum frequency occurs (Pendergrass and Deser, 2017)
		frqP10_ANN	dry extreme	fraction of rain frequency in bottom 10th percentile of observed
		frqP90_ANN	wet extreme	fraction of rain frequency in top 90th percentile of observed
		frqpeak_ANN	frequent/typical	rain rate at which the maximum frequency occurs (Pendergrass and Deser, 2017)
		prdyfrac_ANN	frequent/typical	annual wet days divided by total days
		sdii_ANN	frequent/typical	annual precipitation divided by wet days
		unevenness_ANN	wet extreme	number of wettest days making up half annual precipitation
Xue and Ullrich 2021	NOAA CPC Unified Gauge-Based Analysis observed precipitation data set	A1 Mean Precip	frequent/typical	monthly mean regional precipitation
		B1 Season Precip	frequent/typical	seasonal precipitation
		C1 Frac. Cover.	dry extreme	fraction of grid points experiencing drought
		D1 Dry Frac.	dry extreme	fraction of months classified as dry
		E1 Intensity	dry extreme	intensity of drought periods
		F1 Prob. Init.	dry extreme	probability the following month will be dry if the current month is not dry
		F2 Prob. Term.	dry extreme	probability the following month will be wet if the current month is dry
		Total Score	Multiple	sum of other metrics, with value of each metric capped at 2.0
Alder 2014	LOCA2 ensemble mean	Annual-SSP245	frequent/typical	change in annual precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP2-4.5
		Winter-SSP245	frequent/typical	change in winter precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP2-4.5
		Summer-SSP245	frequent/typical	change in summer precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP2-4.5
		Annual-SSP370	frequent/typical	change in annual precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP3-7.0
		Winter-SSP370	frequent/typical	change in winter precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP3-7.0
		Summer-SSP370	frequent/typical	change in summer precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP3-7.0
		Annual-SSP585	frequent/typical	change in annual precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP5-8.5
		Winter-SSP585	frequent/typical	change in winter precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP5-8.5
		Summer-SSP585	frequent/typical	change in summer precipitation from historical period to 2075-2099, SSP5-8.5
Mahony et al. 2022	Qualitative Criteria	Rank	N/A	rank in recommended ensemble

For each model and metric, I calculated the absolute value of the difference between the value of the metric and the value of its benchmark as provided in the source data set. I then

linearly scaled the absolute value difference for each metric from 0 (worst agreement with benchmark across models) to 1 (best agreement with benchmark across models). For the qualitative criteria reported by Mahony et al. (2022), I assigned a rating to each model between 0 (least recommended) and 1 (most recommended). Table 5.2 is an illustrative example applying this procedure to metrics derived from one model (MIROC6), one source of published metrics (Ahn et al., 2023), and one AR6 geographic region (Eastern North America). The purpose of this illustrative example is to demonstrate the method that was applied to all combinations of model and source of metrics.

Table 5.2. Example Illustrative Calculation of Scaled Scores for One Model, One Source of Metrics, and One Geographic Region

Metric ¹	Benchmark (Mean Observed Value) ²	Model Value ³	Abs. Value (Model - Observed) ⁴	Largest Difference Across Models ⁵	Smallest Difference Across Models ⁶	MIROC6 Scaled Value ⁷
amtP10_ANN	0.115	0.142	0.0263	0.0717	0.000216	0.64
amtP90_ANN	0.0336	0.0150	0.0186	0.0334	0.000832	0.45
amtpeak_ANN	21.5	21.3	0.187	10.6	0.187	1.00
frqP10_ANN	0.617	0.668	0.0516	0.0890	0.000911	0.43
frqP90_ANN	0.00169	0.000581	0.00111	0.00168	0.000226	0.39
frqpeak_ANN	3.98	2.03	1.95	3.86	0.213	0.52
prdyfrac_ANN	0.412	0.435	0.0225	0.0843	0.00260	0.76
sdii_ANN	8.41	7.78	0.623	2.12	0.0258	0.72
unevenness_ANN	28.3	27.8	0.516	8.79	0.0152	0.94

1: Metric name

2: Benchmark value (mean observed value for the specified metric). The set of benchmark values provided by Anh et al. (2023) consists of mean observed values. Other sources provide different types of benchmarks.

3: Simulated value for the specified metric and one example model (MIROC6)

4: Absolute value of the difference between the benchmark value and the value simulated by one example model (MIROC6)

5: Largest absolute value difference between the benchmark value and values simulated by all models in the data set provided by Anh et al. (2023)

6: Smallest absolute value difference between the benchmark value and values simulated by all models in the data set provided by Anh et al. (2023)

7: Scaled value for one example model (MIROC6). $1 - [(Column\ 4 - Column\ 6) / (Column\ 5 - Column\ 6)]$

5.2.4 Selection of Global Circulation Model Ensemble

To illustrate application of the scaled ratings in an engineering decision context, I developed an example set of weighting criteria for a hypothetical urban water resources management project (Table 5.3) such that the sum of all weights equaled 1. I multiplied the

scaled value of each metric relative to its applicable benchmark by an example weight assigned to the metric based on the project objectives. Finally, I summed the weighted ratings for all the individual metrics to produce a weighted rating for one GCM.

In the Table 5.3 example, greater weight is given to metrics published by sources (Ahn et al., 2023; Xue and Ullrich, 2021) employing observed data as benchmarks and lesser weight to sources employing model ensembles and qualitative criteria. In a professional context, these weights are subjective choices reflecting the judgment of the planning or design team, and they should be chosen in consultation with project stakeholders. In the example, the professional team has chosen to give equal consideration to criteria representing frequent/typical conditions and to criteria representing extremes of wet and dry conditions. This choice would be appropriate on a multiple-objective urban stormwater management design incorporating vegetation. In this application, typical design objectives include control of peak flows (extremely wet conditions), an appropriate soil moisture range to support chosen vegetation (considering both extremely dry and extremely wet conditions), promotion of groundwater recharge, and prevention of nutrients in runoff from reaching downstream aquatic ecosystems (typical/frequent conditions leading to impacts that are cumulative over time). The team has also chosen to give greater weight to the “High” greenhouse gas emission scenario (SSP3-7.0) and less weight to the “Intermediate” and “Very High” scenarios. In a professional context, this choice is also subject to project objectives and stakeholder preferences. Finally, the team has chosen in the example to consider the qualitative criteria proposed by Mahony et al. (2022) but has chosen to give these only 20% weight.

Table 5.3. Example Weight Set Tailored to a Set of Specific Objectives on an Engineering Project

Source	Metric Abbreviation	Weight Given to Source	Weight Within Source
Ahn et al. 2023	amtP10_ANN	35%	11%
	amtP90_ANN		11%
	amtpeak_ANN		11%
	frqP10_ANN		11%
	frqP90_ANN		11%
	frqpeak_ANN		11%
	prdyfrac_ANN		11%
	sdi_ANN		11%
	unevenness_ANN		11%
Xue and Ulrich 2021	A1 Mean Precip	25%	7%
	B1 Season Precip		7%
	C1 Frac. Cover.		7%
	D1 Dry Frac.		7%
	E1 Intensity		7%
	F1 Prob. Init.		7%
	F2 Prob. Term.		7%
	Total Score		50%
Alder 2014	Annual-SSP245	20%	8%
	Winter-SSP245		8%
	Summer-SSP245		8%
	Annual-SSP370		17%
	Winter-SSP370		17%
	Summer-SSP370		17%
	Annual-SSP585		8%
	Winter-SSP585		8%
	Summer-SSP585		8%
Mahony et al. 2022	Rank	20%	100%

5.2.5 Characterization of Historical and Projected Precipitation and Dry Periods for an Example Model Ensemble

For my case study comparing historical and future time periods for the selected model ensemble, I chose projections made under scenario SSP5-8.5, representing very high greenhouse gas emissions resulting in 8.5 W/m² radiative forcing and a best estimate of greater than 4°C increase in global surface temperature relative to the 1850-1900 period (IPCC, 2021). The most extreme scenario was selected to illustrate application of the method for characterizing historical and future projections. The same method can be applied by a practitioner to other scenarios of interest.

When comparing historical and future time periods for the selected model ensemble, I chose to compare the projected end of century period 2081-2100 to the historical period 1995-2014. The historical period was selected to represent the most recent continuous 20-year period for which model outputs were compared to observations across the models.

Advantages of a multi-model ensemble include minimization of bias and incorporation of variance between projections (Milinski et al. 2020). These advantages increase as more models are added to the ensemble, but computation time and resources required also increase. I have selected an ensemble of 10 models to represent the region where returns begin to diminish in a professional water resources engineering setting.

Data were obtained through the Copernicus applied programming interface. For the 10 models selected to be part of the case study, results were obtained for all grid cells intersecting the geographic boundary displayed in Figure 5.1. This area is centered on Southeast Pennsylvania and also includes portions of New Jersey, Delaware, and Maryland (boundaries 41.5° to the north, 39.5° to the south, -74.5° to the east, -76.5° to the west). This geographic scope was selected to cover scales at which water resources engineering analyses are most commonly conducted, ranging from watershed scale to site scale. Boundaries were selected to avoid overlapping significantly with large bodies of water including the Chesapeake Bay and Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 5.1. Geographic Scope of GCM Outputs Obtained for Case Study (Credit: Matthew McGauley)

A time series of precipitation was obtained for all combinations of (1) GCM (10 models), (2) time period (1995-2014 and 2081-2100) and (3) AR6 scenario SSP5-8.5. For each 20-year model time series (all combinations of GCM and time period for the SSP5-8.5 scenario), daily precipitation depths were classified as wet weather or dry weather using the IPCC threshold of 1 mm daily precipitation (Calvin et al., 2023). For the set of all wet weather days, a value was calculated for each integer percentile, ranging from the minimum value (0th percentile) to the maximum value (100th percentile). Based on the procedure of Maimone et al. (2019), daily rainfall depths corresponding to the same integer percentile were arithmetically averaged across the GCMs selected for the case study, resulting in an ensemble mean daily precipitation corresponding to each integer percentile. This process was then repeated for the length of consecutive dry days (daily rainfall 1 mm or more) in all the GCM time series.

To evaluate and describe the resulting cumulative distributions of daily rainfall depth, a set of statistics was calculated. First, the variance of points on the cumulative distribution was calculated relative to the model ensemble mean. This procedure was repeated for each unique combination of time period (historical or future) and season. Second, percent bias was calculated for each unique combination of time period, season, and GCM relative to the ensemble mean following the procedure of Gupta et al. (1999).

5.2.6 Adjustment of Historical Unit-Area Rainfall Record

This analysis utilizes a modified version of the “change factor” approach proposed by Maimone et al. (2019). A historical time series based on empirical measurements is adjusted to reflect one possible future under the “very high” emissions scenario SSP5-8.5. In the approach of Maimone et al. (2019), change factors are applied the depths of wet weather events. The approach detailed in Figure 5.2 extends this approach by also applying change factors to the durations of wet and dry weather events.

Figure 5.2. Process for Adjusting Historical Time Series with Change Factors Developed from GCMs

5.2.7 Calculation of Bioretention Performance Measures

For simulation of bioretention basins under projected future climate conditions, EPA SWMM 5.2 (Rossman and Simon, 2022) was selected. SWMM was chosen rather than Hydrus (Simunek et al., 2018) for the 20-year continuous simulations due to numerical instabilities found when pilot testing Hydrus with the adjusted time series needed for this application. SWMM was found to converge numerically for these same time series. A disadvantage of SWMM is that it does not simulate soil physical processes as realistically as Hydrus and that it does not easily permit partitioning of hydrologic losses between evaporation, transpiration, and deep groundwater percolation. Both Hydrus and SWMM simulations were performed for the period selected for model validation (April 2016 to August 2018), and the results of the two models were then compared.

Design scenarios 1, 2, and 3 described in Chapter 4 were set up for simulation in EPA SWMM version 5.2. In addition, the current configuration of the Bioinfiltration Traffic Island was represented for model validation purposes. The configuration consisted of fully impervious watersheds with no depression storage tributary to storage elements and overflow conduits representing each bioretention basin. The storage elements and overflow conduit elevations were configured to represent the surface storage present in each bioretention design scenario. The Green-Ampt method was selected to represent infiltration into the bioretention soil. Initially, Green-Ampt parameters were selected from those reported for silt loam by Rawls et al. (1982). Soil properties were refined in the course of calibration to the time pattern of water levels simulated by Hydrus-1D (described in Chapter 4).

The plant and *Lepidoptera* diversity indices were recalculated from the SWMM results using the same procedures described in Chapter 4 for the Hydrus results. The indices were

calculated for the SWMM simulations representing 1995-2014 conditions and for 2081-2100 conditions.

5.3 Results and Discussion

5.3.1 Accuracy of 58 CMIP6 GCM Precipitation Outputs Relative to Benchmarks

The four sources of published metrics considered herein considered a total of 58 unique GCMs. Figure 5.3 through Figure 5.5 visually present results for all combinations of GCMs and metrics. Figure 5.3 displays all GCMs included in at least three of the four studies. Figure 5.4 displays all GCMs included in two of the studies, and Figure 5.5 includes GCMs included in just one study.

Figure 5.3. Comparison of Individual GCM Metrics to Benchmarks for GCMs Considered by at Least Three of the Four Literature Studies. Benchmarks are defined in Table 5.1. Gray color indicates a particular metric was not studied for a particular model.

Figure 5.4. Comparison of Individual GCM Metrics to Benchmarks for GCMs Considered by Two of the Four Literature Studies. Benchmarks are defined in Table 5.1. Gray color indicates a particular metric was not studied for a particular model.

Figure 5.5. Comparison of Individual GCM Metrics to Benchmarks for GCMs Considered by One of the Four Literature Studies. Benchmarks are defined in Table 5.1. Gray color indicates a particular metric was not studied for a particular model.

5.3.2 Historical and Projected Precipitation for an Example Selected Ensemble

Using the information displayed in Figure 5.3 through Figure 5.5 and the subjective weight set displayed in Table 5.3, an ensemble of 10 GCMs was selected for more detailed characterization. As an illustrative example, mean daily precipitation depths for this ensemble were compared for historical conditions (1995-2014) and future conditions under AR6 scenario SSP5-8.5.

In Figure 5.6, the cumulative distribution of daily precipitation depths for each of the 10 individual GCMs included in the ensemble is shown for the historical period 1995-2014. Also included is the ensemble calculated by averaging values at each integer percentile. Each distribution is calculated by season (e.g., DJF represents December-January-February). Figure 5.7 shows the distribution of projected daily depths under SSP5-8.5 for the period 2081-2100. Finally, Figure 5.8 overlays the model ensembles for the historical and projected periods to illustrate projected changes in rainfall totals over time under this scenario.

The variance of the ensemble model outputs relative to the ensemble mean provides information on the degree to which the simulations agree or differ from each other within a given time period and scenario. For model output representing the historical period, the variance of the ten selected model projections relative to the ensemble cumulative distribution is greatest for the summer (June-July-August) season (11.06 mm²/day), while for other seasons it is less than half this value, ranging from 3.11 to 4.93 mm²/day. Among the SSP5-8.5 projections for the 2081-2100 period, variance is greatest for the fall (September-October-November) season (26.74 mm²/day) and least for the winter (December-January-February) season (5.80 mm²/day). Variance increases between the historical and projected outputs for all seasons, but winter has the smallest increase in variance (from 4.93 to 5.80 mm²/day).

When interpreting model outputs for potential use as boundary conditions for water resource applications, it is instructive to identify models that tend to produce more extreme values relative to others and any models that tend to consistently overpredict or underpredict relative to the model ensemble. Outliers are evident from visual inspection of plots for the spring, summer and fall seasons for the SSP5-8.5 2081-2100 period. For spring and summer seasons, outliers are produced by the MIROC6 model (131.7 and 149.3 mm/day, respectively). For the fall season, outliers are produced by the BCC-CSM-MR2 model (242.53 mm/day) and the CNRM-CM6-1-HR model (118.6 mm/day). There is little consistency in which models tend to overpredict or underpredict relative to the ensemble as measured by percent bias. For example, CanESM5 exhibits the largest positive bias among the ensemble for the historical winter season and the 2081-2100 winter and spring seasons, but it exhibits the largest negative bias for the historical summer and 2081-2100 fall seasons. These findings reinforce the recommendations of past researchers (e.g., Milinsky et al., 2020) that relatively large model ensembles be employed as a basis for prediction and planning.

Projected increases in precipitation depth provide a starting point for development of time series that can serve as appropriate boundary conditions for urban water resources simulations and other applications. Change factors are most pronounced in the winter (December-January-February) and spring (March-April-May) months, and the largest projected daily depth increases of approximately one-third tend to happen during larger storms. In the winter season, the largest change factor projected is 1.32, occurring at multiple percentiles ranging from the 75th to 97th percentile daily depths. During the spring months, the largest change factor projected is 1.33 occurring between the 92nd and 97th percentile depths. The largest single daily depths projected (100th percentile) for each season were excluded from this analysis. Conversely, comparing the

historical and projected SSP5-8.5 2801-2100 ensemble depths at lower percentiles indicates that minimal increases or even small declines in depth are projected. Minimum change factors range from 0.96 (71st to 73rd percentiles, fall season) to 1.01 (1st and 2nd percentiles, winter season).

Figure 5.6. Cumulative Distribution of Rainfall Simulated by 10 GCMs and Model Ensemble for the Historical Period 1995-2014

Figure 5.7. Cumulative Distribution of Rainfall Simulated by 10 GCMs and Model Ensemble for 2081-2100 Under SSP5-8.5

Figure 5.8. Cumulative Distribution of Rainfall Simulated by Ensemble of 10 GCMs for the Historical Period 1995-2014 and Projected Period 2081-2100 Under SSP5-8.5

For many water resources applications, it is important to understand not only the magnitude of projected future wet weather events but the duration of dry periods between wet weather events. Figure 5.9 through Figure 5.11 illustrate these results for the selected ensemble of 10 global circulation models. Variance about the ensemble mean is greatest in the summer (June-July-August) period for simulations representing both the historical and future periods (0.93 and 0.36 days², respectively). The smallest variance occurs during the spring season for both periods (0.36 and 0.47 days², respectively). Variance increases between the historical and future periods for all four seasons, suggesting increased uncertainty about the length of future dry periods. The largest projected number of consecutive dry days for any one season is 31 days

for the historical period (winter, GFDL-ESM4) and 42 days for the future period (fall, CNRM-ESM-2-1). Compared to the results for daily precipitation depth, there is more consistency in which models produce results with the most positive and negative biases relative to the ensemble mean. For example, CNRM-ESM2-1 is the model with the largest or second largest positive bias for three out of four seasons during the 1995-2014 period and all four seasons during the 2081-2100 period. GFDL-ESM4 is the model with the largest or second largest negative bias for all four seasons during the 1995-2014 period and three out of four seasons during the 2081-2100 period.

The change in the ensemble mean distribution from the historical period to the 2081-2100 period under SSP5-8.5 suggests that the length of dry periods will become more variable in the future. Relatively short dry periods (the 27th to 36th percentile) are projected to become slightly shorter (4-6% reduction in length) in the future period during the winter, spring, and summer seasons. However, summer and fall extended dry periods (the 85-86th and 72nd percentiles, respectively) are projected to become approximately one-fourth longer (by 26% and 25%, respectively). In the winter and spring, dry periods closer to median duration (the 38th and 45th percentiles, respectively) experience the greatest increases in duration (30% and 14%, respectively). The single largest storms (100th percentile) are displayed for each season on the plots but are not included in the values discussed above.

Figure 5.9. Cumulative Distribution of Consecutive Dry Days Simulated by Ensemble of 10 GCMs for the Historical Period 1995-2014 Under SSP5-8.5

Figure 5.10. Cumulative Distribution of Consecutive Dry Days Simulated by Ensemble of 10 GCMs for the Future Period 2081-2100 Under SSP5-8.5

Figure 5.11. Cumulative Distribution of Consecutive Dry Days Simulated by Ensemble of 10 GCMs for the Historical Period 1995-2014 and Projected Period 2081-2100 Under SSP5-8.5

5.3.3 Adjusted Unit-Area Inflow Record

Results of the rainfall (unit-area inflow) record adjusted as described in Section 5.2.6 are displayed in Table 5.4. The results suggest that by the end of the 21st century under the very high emissions scenario, the number of dry days will increase and the number of wet days will decrease on a mean annual basis by 3.5% of calendar days, even as total precipitation increases. The trend of more days classified as dry (< 1 mm rainfall) holds across all four seasons, but it is most pronounced at 5.5% of days in the autumn season (September-October-November) and least pronounced at 1.1% of total days in the spring season (March-April-May). This trend has implications for common water resources engineering objectives. For example, where surface

water is an important source of potable water, longer dry periods require greater storage volumes. In bioretention basins, a greater proportion of dry days may underscore the importance of selecting drought tolerant plant species.

Table 5.4. Wet and Dry Weather Calendar Days (Percent of Total Days) Under Historical Conditions and AR6 Scenario SSP5-8.5

Season	Historical (1995-2014)		SSP5-8.5 (2081-2100)	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
annual	79.9	20.1	83.4	16.6
DJF	81.9	18.1	84.0	16.0
JJA	77.6	22.4	82.9	17.1
MAM	79.7	20.3	80.8	19.2
SON	80.5	19.5	86.0	14.0

Figure 5.12 displays an example of a historical precipitation time series record using the change factor approach described in Section 5.2.6. Observed and adjusted values are displayed for the four wet weather events that occurred during a two-week period in May 2004. The same events are displayed after adjustment of these storms to represent the 2081-2100 period. In the historical record, depths for these events range from the 49th to the 62nd percentile during the spring season, indicating that events of this magnitude occur on average 34 to 43 times per year. Management of frequent events such as these is required to achieve groundwater recharge and pollutant removal objectives. Change factors for events at these percentiles during the spring season (Figure 5.11) indicate that depths and peaks for these events may increase 11-16%. To continue to achieve pollutant loads and groundwater recharge objectives under this projected future scenario, storage in bioretention of other stormwater management elements likely will need to be increased to accommodate these larger and more intense storms.

Figure 5.12. Example Time Series Before and After Adjustment for the Period May 7-21, 2004

5.3.4 SWMM Validation

For the April 2016 to August 2018 validation period, SWMM simulation results were compared to results of the Hydrus model validated to field observations as discussed in Chapter 4. Visual examination of surface ponding depths reported by Hydrus and SWMM indicates that patterns and magnitudes are very similar between the two models (Figure 5.13). Peak depths for individual wet weather events match closely during the 2016-2018 selected model validation period.

Figure 5.13. Example Time Series Comparing Hydrus and SWMM Surface Ponding Depth

Figure 5.14. Comparison of Hydrus and SWMM Simulated Peak Depths During the 2016-2018 Validation Events

Figure 5.15 compares mean water level recession rates for the wet weather event selected for validation. Over the course of the validation procedure, it became apparent that soil

properties selected to match event peak depths using SWMM’s Green-Ampt algorithm do not result in also matching the recession rates. Recession rates are consistently lower (less steep, leading to longer ponding durations) in SWMM compared to Hydrus. Matching peak depth was prioritized in the calibration process. The differences in simulated recession rates may be explained by the more physically based Richards equation approach implemented in Hydrus compared to the simplified Green-Ampt approach implemented in SWMM.

Figure 5.15 Comparison of Hydrus and SWMM Simulated Recession Rates During the 2016-2018 Validation Events

Table 5.5. Calibration Statistics for SWMM and Hydrus Results, Selected Events During the 2016-2018 Growing Seasons

Metric	RMSE	NSE	Percent Bias
Event Peak Depth (cm)	1.87	0.975	-0.989
Event Recession Rate (cm/hr)	0.598	-4.88	35.4

5.3.5 End-of-Century Bioretention Performance Under SSP5-8.5

Within the scope of the current study, plant survival is impacted by the magnitude and time pattern of surface ponding and soil moisture. While the results indicate changes to these patterns when climate change is taken into account, these hydrologic changes alone do not alter the list of plant species identified in this analysis to be appropriate to the environmental conditions in any of the alternative designs. While there may be more inflow due to increased rainfall volume and intensity and subsequently more outflow in the future, the duration of ponding is limited by the storage volume and weir height of each design, which do not change between the historical and future periods. The maximum 10-day soil moisture deficit changes less than 1 cm per year as increases in potential evapotranspiration are balanced by increases in net inflow to the system. Appendix G includes additional results and analysis related to these findings. In other words, the results of the simulation exercise did not indicate a change in the plant diversity index for the three bioretention design scenarios simulated before and after adjustment to represent the SSP5-8.5 precipitation and temperature projections. The results indicate that design scenario 1 can support 156 plant species while scenarios 2 and 3 can support 61 plant species under both current and future climate conditions. This research result must be considered in light of several limitations, and without additional investigation it is not a suitable basis for practical design decisions in the long term. First, these results should be considered preliminary in nature because they reflect the impacts of only two factors, ponding duration and soil moisture changes. Second, while the GCM ensemble mean daily temperature projections for 2081-2100 under SSP5-8.5 are reflected in the soil moisture deficit estimates, these results do not reflect direct physiological effects of heat on specific plant species in the master bioretention plant list, and therefore they are likely to underestimate climate change impacts on potential plant diversity. Third, the approach presented here links the presence of *Lepidoptera* only to the

presence of suitable larval host plants. In reality, *Lepidoptera* present in a particular habitat patch will themselves be directly affected by heat, by moisture availability, and by the state of the regional populations of species in the larger landscape. Finally, while plants may be a particularly climate change sensitive component of future bioretention basins, designing to meet engineering performance objectives in an altered climate will not rely solely on plant choice. New thinking and redesign of structural components impacting hydraulics will be important to mitigate effects of projected rainfall volumes and intensities.

Figure 5.16. Plant Species Richness Index by Scenario

5.4 Conclusions and Engineering Applications

The protocol suggested here allows climate projections to be translated to an actionable framework for use by engineers and scientists working on water management applications in the urban environment, including bioretention planning and design. Broad applications include utilizing this protocol to simulate designs and models under relevant future conditions, along with developing infrastructure and policy measures to restore a more natural balance between runoff, infiltration, and evapotranspiration in urbanized and urbanizing watersheds over the long run. When making decisions about long-lived infrastructure and land use today, professionals

need to be able to project how systems are likely to function under future climate scenarios. For example, the results presented in Section 5.3.3 suggest that the number of calendar days classified as dry (< 1 mm precipitation) will increase by 3.5% of annual days as a 20-year average under SSP5-8.5. This increase may impact the sizing of reservoirs in communities that rely on surface water as a source of potable water. To achieve pollutant load reduction and groundwater recharge design objectives, the example results presented in Section 5.3.3 for May 2004 indicate that precipitation depths and peak intensities for the events shown may increase by 11-16%. To achieve the current level of performance under SSP5-8.5 during these storms will require an increase in capacity of stormwater designs intended to manage pollutant loads and the hydrologic cycle, such as bioretention basins.

The model ensemble projected time series of precipitation discussed in this chapter may be suitable to serve as hydrologic drivers for some urban water resource applications on some temporal scales without further modification. Because precipitation depths are expected to be relatively unbiased at the monthly or seasonal scales, these results may be appropriate as drivers for a water supply or reservoir operation study, for example. However, because precipitation intensity and duration projections are known to be biased toward lesser intensities and greater durations compared to historical data, these results may not be appropriate for wet weather sewer overflow, urban stormwater management, or urban pluvial flooding applications without further modification. The method presented in Section 5.2.6 and results in Section 5.3.3 are one logical approach to producing a time series appropriate for study of water resources processes at small time scales (sub-daily to sub-hourly). More research building on these initial results is recommended.

Because the estimate of potential plant diversity did not change between the historical condition and the projected condition, the estimated *Lepidoptera* species richness that can be supported did not change in these estimates. The results indicate that the plant species present in design scenario 1 can serve as larval hosts for 1772 species of *Lepidoptera*, while the plant species present in scenarios 2 and 3 can host 1295 species of *Lepidoptera*. The results reflect only the change in availability of host plant species for *Lepidoptera* larvae and do not reflect any direct physiological effects of heat or drought on *Lepidoptera* larvae or adults. Because of these caveats, this preliminary conclusion should be applied in practice with caution.

CHAPTER 6. Considering Water Management and Terrestrial Ecological Function Objectives Together at the Watershed Scale

6.1 Introduction

Biodiversity at the site scale is mediated both by local environmental conditions and by biodiversity present in the surrounding landscape. Chapters 3-5 focused on how plant choice and other design decisions can affect water management and ecosystem function objectives within a bioretention basin in the context of a single site. However, it is important to recognize that bioretention basins represent both new water management features and new habitat patches added to existing urban landscapes and watersheds. These new basins become part of and interact with the network of vegetated habitat patches in the urban landscape. Reaching the full potential biodiversity for a given bioretention basin at the site scale depends in part on the presence and dispersal ability of plant and animal species in the surrounding urban landscape. Conversely, as groups of new engineered stormwater management practices are implemented in the urban landscape over time, their locations can potentially improve ecological connectivity of the larger urban landscape by facilitating plant and animal dispersal between habitat patches and along habitat corridors.

An ecological corridor can be defined as a pathway connecting two patches of suitable habitat (Beninde et al., 2015). To create a corridor for dispersal, it is necessary to have either continuous linear habitat facilitating movement or to have patches close enough so that organisms can disperse between the patches across any less suitable terrain between patches. The latter concept is sometimes referred to as “stepping stones” and sometimes distinguished from a corridor consisting of continuous suitable habitat (e.g. Beninde et al., 2015). I have chosen to use the term corridor to refer to any successful dispersal pathway between patches in the urban

environment where continuous habitats are likely to be interrupted by human-dominated land cover features.

Both the effectiveness of water management and the degree of habitat connectivity in a watershed are influenced by the decisions of engineers and municipal officials who choose project sites and set land use policies. The spatial configuration of bioretention basins may be able to help create corridors that enhance dispersal of plants and animals, particularly through the most intensely developed urban areas where surface runoff management is also most needed. Before addition of new bioretention basins or other stormwater management facilities, networks of existing habitat patches in urban watersheds may include larger parks and nature reserves, neighborhood parks and recreation facilities, trees along streets and on private property, and wetlands along riparian corridors and near bodies of water. These vegetated habitat patches often are separated by expanses of urban land cover types such as buildings and pavement which provide little suitable habitat for plants and animals. Figure 6.1 is an example of land cover present in a mixed urban/suburban/rural watershed in the vicinity of Lancaster, Pennsylvania, USA. In this example, a forested patch to the northwest is separated by a central business district from a riparian corridor to the southeast. An example habitat suitability model (discussed in Section 6.2.2) indicates that portions of these areas are likely suitable for selected indicator species of *Lepidoptera*. The habitat suitability model indicates that the central business district is not suitable habitat for the indicator species. At the same time, the central business district includes a high intensity of impervious surfaces generating runoff. Therefore, installing bioretention basins is a potential solution to the stormwater management needs in this urban area. By making plant choices that support *Lepidoptera* larvae as proposed in Chapters 3 and 4, designers of the bioretention basins also have an opportunity to create a habitat corridor allowing

Lepidoptera to disperse more easily between the existing habitat patches to the northwest and southeast.

Figure 6.1. Illustration of a Potential Corridor Connecting Existing Habitat Patches in the Vicinity of Lancaster, Pennsylvania, USA

While bioretention basins have potential to address both water management and ecological connectivity objectives in watersheds, an open question is whether a minimum density and spatial arrangement of bioretention basins sufficient to alter hydrology in a watershed will

also be sufficient to enhance connectivity. To achieve water resources engineering objectives within urbanized or urbanizing watersheds, it is necessary to control the volume, rate, and pollutant loads associated with a significant portion of runoff-producing surfaces. For example, in a highly urbanized watershed in Philadelphia, Kwak et al. (2024) were able to document decreases in the frequency of peak streamflow with runoff from approximately 5% of impervious surfaces draining to stormwater controls. Other researchers have analyzed data on benthic macroinvertebrates and fish in watersheds at varying stages of urbanization to estimate thresholds at which aquatic ecosystem functions begin to decline. For example, Schueler et al. (2009) estimated that aquatic ecosystem function begins to degrade when on the order of 10% of surfaces in a watershed are converted to impervious materials such as pavement and rooftops. The open research question is whether, if the types of vegetated stormwater controls described in Chapters 2-4 are implemented on the scale required to protect and restore hydrologic functions in urban watersheds, terrestrial ecosystem functions will also be protected or restored.

In order to make decisions on bioretention basin placement that will both achieve water resources objectives and increase habitat connectivity at the watershed scale, municipal officials and other stakeholders need quantitative metrics allowing them to compare alternative placement plans and policies. This is the subject of Research Question 2, “What subset of habitat connectivity measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that can provide actionable information to decision makers with influence over bioretention placement and land use policy?” In Sections 6.2.5 and 6.3, I propose some methods to explore this question from the habitat connectivity perspective. I conclude the chapter with recommended future research to help refine the answer to this research question. It is hoped that the proposed methods and future research discussed in this chapter ultimately may provide a means of understanding how best to integrate

green stormwater infrastructure such as bioretention basins into larger urban green infrastructure networks including trees, parks, wetlands, and bodies of water.

6.2 Linking Spatial Configuration of Habitat to Temporal Dynamics of Animal Populations within Ecosystems

6.2.1 Introduction

Aspects of approaches employed in ecology and conservation planning may be adaptable for use in watershed-scale bioretention siting and policy decisions. At the watershed scale, dynamic processes affecting the spatiotemporal distribution of plants and animals in a watershed will be altered when new bioretention basins are added to the urban landscape. A long-term vision is that planners and engineers will one day have practical tools to inform bioretention placement and policy in light of these dynamic effects. There is a large gap between this vision and current water resources engineering practice. A more practical near-term goal may be to adapt static measures of spatial landscape configuration currently employed widely in conservation science and planning as proxies for ecological dynamics. A range of these static measures will be discussed in Section 6.3. Nonetheless, it is worthwhile to briefly survey for an engineering audience some key concepts, studies, and terms related to ecosystem dynamics at the watershed scale. The concepts, studies, and terms reviewed here are selected because they are directly relevant to discussion to follow later in this chapter. A more comprehensive review of ecosystem dynamics is beyond the scope of the current engineering study.

6.2.2 Habitat

Chapter 3 discussed the importance of vegetation suited to local environmental conditions in providing habitat for native *Lepidoptera* species, while Chapter 2 provided evidence that *Lepidoptera* in turn serve as an indicator that multiple trophic levels are present in urban ecosystems. Suitable habitat for an organism can be defined as an aggregation of areas in

the landscape which collectively allow the organism to complete its life cycle (Baguette and Mennechez, 2004). Habitat suitability models seek to translate spatial data on environmental characteristics or land cover into functional maps of which areas in a landscape can best support an organism of interest (Fahrig et al., 2011). While a wide range of approaches has been employed including some complex statistical approaches (Guisan et al., 2017), qualitative models relying on expert judgment remain common in the practice of conservation (Zeller et al., 2012).

Figure 6.2 presents results of an example habitat suitability model relating the land cover classes present in Figure 6.1 to resources needed by three different butterfly species common in eastern Pennsylvania. Applying this model allows the land cover map shown in Figure 6.1 to be translated into a functional map of suitable habitat for these three species, following the example of Fahrig et al. (2011).

Figure 6.2. Illustration of Habitat Suitability and Habitat Patch Concepts

The left panel in Figure 6.2 depicts habitat as a gradient from least to most suitable for the three selected butterfly indicator species. In the right panel, a threshold has been selected for a binary classification below which the landscape is classified as unsuitable (gray color). Areas rated above this threshold provide multiple resources needed by all three of the butterfly species and therefore are deemed highly suitable habitat. The right panel also depicts hypothetical locations where bioretention basins could be implemented both to manage urban runoff and to provide new habitat. It is presumed that these bioretention basins are designed following the guidelines suggested in Chapters 3 and 4, thereby providing the favorable local environmental conditions and larval host plants needed for these butterfly species to persist. I will now consider how the spatial configuration of these habitat patches in the urban landscape is important when understanding ecosystem functions at the local patch level.

6.2.3 Species Richness from Local to Regional (Watershed) Scale

Species richness at the local patch scale, such as within an individual bioretention basin, is limited by species richness at the regional or watershed scale. The analysis presented in Chapters 3-5 implicitly assumes that species richness at the site scale is dependent only on conditions and resources at the site scale and is therefore independent of species richness at larger spatial scales. However, local species richness has been shown empirically to be strongly correlated to regional species richness for a range of organisms including insect herbivores (e.g., Cornell, 1985). This result is consistent with theory indicating that species richness in a given location results from a balance between processes tending to increase and decrease the number of species over time (Ricklefs, 1987). The ability of an individual species to persist (thereby preventing a decrease in species richness) in a local habitat depends on its ability to effectively utilize available resources to increase in population and approach some equilibrium carrying capacity when local environmental conditions are favorable (Pasztor et al., 2016). In order for the species to persist, this ability to increase must over time counteract factors tending to cause localized extinction of species. These factors include time periods of unfavorable environmental conditions (e.g., high or low temperature, water abundance or scarcity), competition between species for available resources, predation, disease, death of individuals due to natural life span, and small-scale disturbances. Other than formation of new species on evolutionary time scales, an increase in local species richness requires immigration of a new species into a local patch from the surrounding landscape. The potential for this immigration depends in turn on the history of climatic conditions and disturbances determining overall species richness in the surrounding landscape, and it depends on the geographic configuration of dispersal barriers and corridors within the landscape (Ricklefs, 1987).

6.2.4 Dispersal

Dispersal is a key concept when considering how the geographic configuration of habitat patches relates to populations of plants and animals within those patches throughout the larger landscape. Dispersal is also related to the concept of species range and is therefore key to understanding whether species can adjust their ranges to cope with shifting environmental conditions driven by climate change (e.g., Vasiliev and Greenwood, 2021). A definition of dispersal is movement of individuals or propagules with potential influence on gene flows through space (LeGrand et al., 2012; Ronce, 2007). In other words, dispersal is movement with a reproductive purpose. A dispersal movement includes an organism leaving one location (“departure” or “emigration”), a movement stage (also called a “vagrant” stage), and an arrival (“settling” or “immigration”) stage at a new location (Ronce, 2007). Dispersal is important because it can allow a species to persist regionally even if it goes extinct locally due to a random event such as a storm or due to a disturbance event such as land clearing by humans. Following a disturbance event, dispersal can allow recolonization of a patch by individuals from nearby patches assuming the vacated patch is still suitable for the species (Ronce, 2007). Dispersal is sometimes measured empirically as a rate at which individuals leave a habitat patch, without specifics about the distance or direction of movement. A more mathematically precise description consists of a dispersal kernel, or the probability density that an individual initially at a set of spatial coordinates will be found at another set of coordinates after a period of time (Ronce, 2007). Butterflies have been common subjects of empirical dispersal studies (e.g., LeGrand et al., 2012; Stevens et al., 2010).

6.2.5 Potential Dynamic Approaches in a Planning/Engineering Decision Making Context

Available dynamic models of organisms in fragmented environments make use of local-scale habitat and regional-scale dispersal concepts. One relatively simple mathematical model

that may be adaptable for engineering applications is the patch-occupancy model of Levins (1969). This model provides a diffusion-based analytical solution to predict the proportion of total patches occupied by a species at equilibrium. Required inputs are an estimated migration rate (probability that individuals from one patch will successfully colonize another patch in some time period), an extinction rate (probability of local extinction with respect to time), and the total number of patches suitable for occupation. Levins suggested assuming that successful migration probability would decay exponentially with increasing distance between two patches in the absence of other information.

A more sophisticated mathematical model that may be adaptable for engineering applications was proposed by Hanski (1998), building on the conceptual foundation established by Levins (1969). This model was shown to fit extensive field data documenting dispersal of the Glanville fritillary butterfly (*Melitaea cinxia*) in fragmented habitats in Finland (Wahlberg et al., 1996). In Hanski's model, extinction-colonization dynamics of individual patches are simulated over time by predicting probability of dispersal between the patches. The approach is spatially explicit, meaning the coordinates of the patches and distances between them are inputs to the calculations. Dispersal probability between two patches is influenced by the distance between the patches and the population present within the patches. This distance between patches can be further modified to an "effective distance" reflecting mortality or difficulty of traveling the straight-line path between two points (e.g., Adriaensen et al., 2003; Zeller et al., 2012). Hanski (1998) was able to calibrate this approach based on extensive capture-recapture data for the Glanville fritillary for various landscapes. Stochastic processes with available data on mortality (e.g., mortality in response to weather events such as extreme heat, cold, wind) also can be incorporated to influence dispersal probability in this simulation framework. Using this

framework, increases, decreases, and extinctions of populations within all patches in the landscape can be simulated over time, resulting in an estimate of the total metapopulation (sum of the subpopulations in individual patches) in the regional network of habitat patches over time. More complex simulation approaches with many more parameters have also been developed (e.g., Akcakaya and Ferson, 1992), and these could be considered for engineering applications such as comparing alternative placement schemes for a network of bioretention basins. However, Hanski (1998) felt that the parameters in these models are challenging to validate using available data.

In the metapopulation concept of Hanski, the total regional population of a species in a fragmented habitat represents the sum of many small local populations which may be individually increasing, decreasing, going extinct, or repopulating empty patches over time. Individual subpopulations may never reach equilibrium, but the regional metapopulation can remain relatively stable if the processes causing populations to increase and decrease in local habitat patches are balanced in the aggregate. On the other hand, disturbances, habitat loss, and changes in environmental conditions can alter this balance and lead to decrease or extinction of the metapopulation some period of time after these events have occurred (Hanski, 1998). This concept is relevant to land use and engineering siting decisions made by professionals because the regional consequences of these decisions (i.e., species loss due to habitat loss) may not be evident for a period of time after localized interventions in the landscape have occurred.

6.2.6 Landscape Spatial Configuration as a Proxy for Dynamic Processes

In conservation planning, quantitative descriptions of landscape-scale spatial patterns are often used as proxies for dynamic processes affecting plant and animal dispersal and diversity. Even if these spatial metrics are not linked explicitly to biodiversity measures, it is possible to infer the expected direction of change in biodiversity measures based on changes in these

metrics. Knowing the expected direction of change can in turn inform planning and policy decisions. The total area of suitable habitat can be seen as a proxy for the potential population size, or carrying capacity, of a species a given landscape can support. This carrying capacity can be modified by the quality of the individual patches, including resources they provide and edge effects leading to harsher environmental conditions than a larger patch would provide. The total carrying capacity of the larger landscape is then modified by factors that influence dispersal between habitat patches. Dispersal in turn is affected by the distance organisms must travel between patches through unsuitable habitat (e.g., Baguette and van Dyck, 2007). More complex analyses can modify travel distance to gradations of unsuitableness or risk that organisms must traverse to move between patches (e.g., Gustafson and Gardner, 1996).

Spatial metrics describing fragmentation, connectivity, and corridor concepts have been applied to rural landscapes for a range of species including plants, reptiles, amphibians, and birds (e.g., Schindler et al., 2013). A number of studies have focused on reserve design and conservation policy development for large charismatic mammals (e.g., Rabinowitz and Zeller, 2010). Butterflies have been a common subject of patch isolation and connectivity studies in forest and grassland environments (Thomas et al., 2001). Fragmentation, connectivity, and corridor measures have also been explored in urban contexts (e.g., Lepczyk et al., 2017). Beninde et al. (2015) performed a meta-analysis on data taken from studies of habitat and biodiversity in 75 cities worldwide. They found strong evidence in the literature that total habitat area, characteristics of habitat including vegetation type, and the presence of corridors (narrow, continuous linear habitats) are significant predictors of urban biodiversity for a range of species. A range of quantitative measures of landscape fragmentation and connectivity proposed in the literature will be presented in Section 6.3.

6.3 Measures and Tools for Quantifying Landscape Spatial Configuration

6.3.1 Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization

Table 6.1 lists a range of metrics available for characterizing the geometric shapes and configurations of habitat patches. The first group of spatial metrics characterizes the geographic configuration of the urban landscape, including patches of suitable habitat and areas of "matrix" or unsuitable habitat. Once a raster representing habitat suitability is created, many metrics listed in this table can be calculated using the R package "landscapemetrics" (Hesselbarth et al., 2019).

The next group of metrics listed in Table 6.1 characterizes the size and shape of habitat patches identified as suitable for the indicator species. First, the number of patches and sum of all suitable patch areas in the study area can be calculated for a given alternative. These values can be normalized to area per 100 ha of study area to allow potential comparison across multiple study areas. The area of the largest patch as a fraction of the study area is calculated, although this value may not often vary in the context of bioretention basins being added to a watershed-scale landscape.

Table 6.1. Selected Measures for Characterizing Habitat Fragmentation and Spatial Configuration within a Landscape

Category	Name	Practical Goal	Theoretical Range
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Total Area of Patches	Increase	0 (worst) - total watershed area (best)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Patch Size (Mean, Summary Statistics)	Increase*	0 (worst) - total watershed area (best)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Number of Patches	Increase*	not applicable
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Total Area of Patches as a Fraction of the Landscape	Increase*	0 (worst) - 1 (best)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Patch Density	Increase*	not applicable
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Total Edge	Decrease*	0 (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Edge Density	Decrease*	0 (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Largest Patch Index	Increase*	0 (worst) - 1 (best)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Perimeter-Area Ratio (Mean, Summary Statistics)	Decrease*	$2\pi r$ (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Related Circumscribing Circle (Mean, Summary Statistics)	Decrease*	1 (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Patch Size/Shape Characterization	Shape Index (Mean, Summary Statistics)	Decrease*	1 (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Fragmentation	Connectance (contagion)	Increase*	0 (worst) - 100 (best)
Habitat Fragmentation	Division Index	Decrease*	0 (best) - 1 (worst)
Habitat Fragmentation	Effective Mesh Size	Increase*	0 (worst) - scale-dependent upper limit (best)
Habitat Fragmentation	Landscape Shape Index	Decrease*	1 (best) - ∞ (worst)
Habitat Fragmentation	Splitting Index	Decrease*	1 (best) - (number of pixels) ² (worst)
Habitat Connectivity - Patch Based	Euclidean Nearest Neighbor Distance (Mean, Summary Statistics)	Decrease**	0 (best) - watershed diameter (worst)
Habitat Connectivity - Patch Based	Travel Cost/Friction/Risk	Decrease**	0 (best) - scale-dependent upper limit (worst)
Habitat Connectivity - Patch Based	Effective Distance, Cost-Weighted Distance	Decrease**	0 (best) - scale-dependent upper limit (worst)
Habitat Connectivity - Patch Based	Resistance/Conductance (Circuit Theory)	Decrease**	0 (best) - scale-dependent upper limit (worst)
Habitat Connectivity - Patch Based	Effective Resistance/Effective Conductance (Circuit Theory)	Decrease**	0 (best) - scale-dependent upper limit (worst)

* Changing the value of the metric in this direction is positive as long as total habitat area is constant or increasing.

** Decreasing these values can be considered to increase dispersal probability up to some maximum limit as travel distance/difficulty becomes small.

Next, the mean, standard deviation, and selected percentiles for individual patch areas within a defined landscape/watershed-scale study area can be calculated. Calculating and plotting the distribution of patch areas can provide insights into the median and range of patch sizes as well as any skew in the data toward larger or smaller patches (Hesselbarth et al., 2019). A function such as a logistic function also can be fit to the data, with the curve-fitting parameters serving to characterize the distribution.

A variety of measures have been proposed in the literature to describe the shapes of habitat patches and the geometric relationship between area and edge (perimeter). Habitat edges are deleterious to some species. Characterizing changes in the values of these metrics between watershed-scale alternatives may aid the decision maker if a species of interest would benefit from more regularly shaped patches. At the watershed scale, these relationships can be described by summary statistics for individual patches, such as mean, standard deviation, and selected percentiles (Hesselbarth et al., 2019).

For individual patches, perimeter-area ratio, related circumscribing circle, and shape index describe the shape and compactness of patches (Figure 6.3). Perimeter-area ratio is self-explanatory, with units of L^{-1} . The shape index for an individual patch is defined as patch perimeter divided by the perimeter of a square with the same area as the patch. For both these metrics, a larger value indicates a more irregularly shaped patch with more edge relative to its area. Related circumscribing circle is the smallest circle with an area equal to the area of a patch. A perfectly circular patch would have a value of 0, while a patch approaching a linear shape would have a value approaching 1. As the regularity of the patch decreases, the ratio will increase. Patches with larger ratios will tend to have more edges and less core area relative to their sizes. The mean and summary statistics for this metric provide information about the regularity of all patches in the landscape (Hesselbarth et al., 2019).

Total edge and edge density provide information on the amount of edge in the landscape, and edge density scales total edge to the area of the landscape, creating a metric that is independent of landscape size. Edge density can be compared between landscapes of different sizes, while total edge is meaningful only for the specific landscape where it is measured (Hesselbarth et al., 2019).

Figure 6.3. Illustration of Habitat Patch Shape Metrics

6.3.2 Measures of Fragmentation and Connectivity

The literature suggests many measures of habitat fragmentation. Calculating a selection of these at the watershed scale will aid the decision maker in identifying alternatives that reduce fragmentation and thereby promote movement of animals and plant propagules. Five measures of fragmentation will be discussed in this section. Based on a raster classifying a landscape as habitat and non-habitat, these measures can be calculated using the R package *landscapemetrics* (Hesselbarth et al., 2019).

The first fragmentation metric, connectance or contagion index, describes the probability of two random adjacent cells belonging to the same class (e.g., suitable habitat) (Hesselbarth et al., 2019; Riitters et al., 1996). Higher probabilities indicate a greater degree of connection. The second metric, division index, describes the probability that two randomly selected cells are not part of the same patch. Lower values indicate greater connection. The third metric, effective

mesh size, conceptually is the inverse of the division index. A value of 0 would indicate all habitat in the landscape consists of one large patch (not fragmented). A value of 1 would indicate that the landscape is made up of many small patches of only one pixel each (highly fragmented). A decreasing value of this metric across design scenarios indicates choices are being made to decrease fragmentation and increase connectivity (Hesselbarth et al., 2019; Jaeger, 2000). The fourth metric, landscape shape index, is the ratio between total edge length and the hypothetical minimum edge length if only one large (circular or square) patch were present. This index is influenced by patch number, size, and shape. A ratio of 1 would indicate all habitat contained in a single patch or reserve. As the index increases, available habitat has the same area but is more dispersed in the landscape and has more edges (Hesselbarth et al., 2019). The final fragmentation metric, splitting index, is defined as the number of patches if all patches in the landscape were equally sized (Jaeger, 2000). Greater values indicate increasing fragmentation.

Another group of measures evaluates the ease with which species can travel between specific habitat patches. Euclidean nearest neighbor distance characterizes connectivity by measuring the straight-line distance between nearby patches, measured from edge to edge (Hesselbarth et al., 2019). This result can be characterized statistically (e.g., mean, standard deviation, percentiles) for all pairs of nearest-neighbor patches within the watershed. This measure is intuitive and can be compared to what is known about *Lepidoptera* dispersal. In a refinement to the straight-line distance, areas of low habitat suitability between patches can be characterized by the degree of impediment or risk they pose to a species attempting to traverse them. This is sometimes referred to as "cost" and can be expressed in dollar or time units. Effective distance or cost-weighted distance is an alternative way of describing travel cost. Simple distance between patches may be the most important factor for some species, while the

presence of particular environmental conditions or physical barriers such as roads may play an important role for others. For example, these measures could compare the ease of travel between the largest existing patch in the watershed and a new patch created by placement of a bioretention basin. They could also characterize ease of travel between two large existing patches, with the travel passing through the bioretention basin. In this way, the effect of the bioretention basin in facilitating movement can be assessed even if a qualitative scale is used. Landscape features which reduce risk or facilitate travel, such as urban tree canopy or presence of water, can be considered even if these features are outside designated habitat patches (Dutta et al., 2022).

Circuit theory provides a final alternative to evaluate travel cost or risk. Measures of resistance are defined similarly as in the travel cost/effective distance measures, but they are calculated using equations analogous to electric circuits. Just as electrical current will take the "path of least resistance" from one point to another, subject to some stochasticity, the paths organisms will take can be calculated using a combination of circuit theory and random walk theory. An advantage of circuit theory is that it can predict the relative probabilities of organisms taking multiple potential pathways (McRae et al., 2008). In this analysis, the travel path would not need to be forced through a newly added bioretention basin, but some estimate of the probability of organisms choosing that path could be determined. Circuit theory-based analyses can be performed using the open source software Circuitscape.

6.3.3 Measures Related to Network Characteristics

The configuration of habitat patches within a landscape can be characterized using network theory (referred to as graph theory in formal mathematics). To perform network analyses, the landscape of patches is transformed into a node-and-link network. Links are often referred to as "edges" by mathematicians, but here they will be referred to as links to avoid

potential confusion with the perimeters of patches. One way to generate the network is to define a centroid for each patch and connect each patch to its nearest neighbors with a straight line. The links can then be characterized by the straight-line distance between the centroids, by the shortest distance between patch edges, or by an effective distance modified to reflect travel difficulty for an organism of interest. Once the network is defined, one available tool for calculation of the measures discussed below is the R package "igraph" (Csardi, 2006). Table 6.2 lists selected network-based measures with relevance to the watershed-scale alternatives analysis.

Table 6.2. Network-Based Measures for Characterizing Habitat Fragmentation and Spatial Configuration within a Landscape

category	name
Habitat Connectivity - Network Based	Node Connectivity
Habitat Connectivity - Network Based	Cut Points or Node Sensitivity
Habitat Connectivity - Network Based	Graph Diameter
Habitat Connectivity - Network Based	Patch Centrality

If portions of a network are disconnected, it can be inferred that animal movement will be inhibited. A network is disconnected if its nodes can be divided into two subsets with no links between them. If a network is not disconnected, it is connected (Wallis, 2007). Connectivity can be evaluated by determining the minimum number of nodes in a network that must be removed to disconnect the network. All other factors being equal, a more complex and resilient landscape will require removal of more nodes before it becomes disconnected. Cut points are key nodes whose removal results in a sharp decrease in network connectivity. A specific metric of cut points therefore is a list of the nodes whose removal would result in disconnection. The two metrics (node connectivity and cut points) are useful together. With knowledge of what nodes/habitat patches are most important to node connectivity, the decision maker can protect these nodes (if they already exist) or add them to the network if they do not yet exist. Put another way, this

approach allows the planner/engineer to test the potential advantage of adding new habitat patches to an existing network.

Graph diameter provides another measurement relevant to patch connectivity and animal movement. Graph diameter is the longest path that can be taken between any two nodes in a network such that the path length between the nodes is the shortest possible. For a given network, graph diameter will increase initially as nodes or edges are removed because traveling between a given set of points will require longer distances. This may occur as an initially homogeneous landscape becomes fragmented. In a landscape that has already become fragmented (typical of urban areas), diameter will then decrease again as "stepping stone" nodes are lost (Urban and Keitt, 2001).

The measures discussed above can be assessed to characterize the centrality or importance of a given node, such as a proposed bioretention basin. One way to quantify the importance of a node is to calculate a variety of metrics such as connectivity and graph diameter, remove the node, and then recalculate the measures. By repeating this process for individual nodes and then ranking the results, the importance of each node (e.g., a bioretention basin or other patch of suitable habitat) can be evaluated (Urban and Keitt, 2001).

6.4 Conclusions and Engineering Applications

Based on the results of the literature review presented in this section, a preliminary answer to Research Question 2 is to calculate the following metrics to help inform a stakeholder choice between alternative plans or policies that will influence bioretention placement over time: total habitat area, distribution of Euclidean distances between nearest-neighbor pairs of suitable habitat, and the five fragmentation metrics listed in Table 6.1. In the field of conservation planning, these metrics have been applied in many geographic regions including humid, arid, tropical, and subtropical areas of the world. However, links between these spatial metrics and

dispersal can be expected to vary by region and by the specific indicator organisms chosen. The preliminary conclusions presented in this section are based on an initial literature review, and further research is recommended to confirm and test them in practical application and in specific locations.

Planners, engineers, municipal officials, and land managers can intentionally influence the spatial arrangement of bioretention basins and other forms of urban green infrastructure over time. These choices can facilitate terrestrial ecosystem connectivity while providing necessary water management functions. For example, municipal officials can choose specific locations of bioretention basins on public lands to increase measures of ecosystem connectivity discussed in Section 6.3. Municipal officials also design and implement policies, such as zoning codes and land bank operations, which influence locations of bioretention basins on private property and can influence ecosystem connectivity over time. For instance, two alternative policies under consideration could incentivize butterfly host plants in bioretention basins either throughout a watershed or only within a particular butterfly movement corridor. To assess the connectivity implications of these policies, planners would calculate each of the recommended metrics (discussed in more detail in Section 6.4.1.3) for each of the alternatives under consideration. The alternative policies can then be ranked according to more and less desirable values of these metrics, and this ranking can inform a stakeholder decision process as discussed in Section 4.4.

Historically, terrestrial habitat connectivity has not been considered when choosing implementation strategies and policies that influence bioretention placement over time. For this reason, there is substantial potential to improve information available when comparing alternative plans and policies. Improvements can be made in the short term by calculating a limited set of straightforward metrics to better inform choices between alternative plans or

policies. In parallel to these short-term improvements, research can be conducted to determine whether more sophisticated approaches can further improve outcomes of planning and policy choices.

6.4.1 Recommended Steps for Planning and Engineering Practice

6.4.1.1 Choose one or more indicator organisms.

Common butterfly species are recommended for the wide range of reasons discussed in Chapters 2 and 6. Among these reasons are that butterfly dispersal has been widely studied and their larvae serve the critical function of transferring energy and biomass from green plants to higher trophic levels including birds.

6.4.1.2 Develop and implement a simple habitat suitability model to map patches of habitat for the indicator species.

While many complex approaches are discussed in the literature, relatively simple approaches employing widely available land cover and expert judgment are common and recommended as a step that can immediately improve engineering practice. Fahrig et al. (2011) provides one discussion of this approach along with an illustrative example.

6.4.1.3 Calculate selected metrics for the baseline landscape and for each alternative plan or policy being considered.

The most important measure to track when considering alternative plans or policies is simply total habitat area (e.g., Hanski, 1998). As a supplementary metric, the distribution (for example, mean and standard deviation) of Euclidean nearest neighbor distance between suitable habitat patches is recommended. If the distance between patches is decreased by a given plan or policy while total habitat area is maintained, it can be inferred that plant and butterfly dispersal are likely to increase. The five fragmentation measures listed in Table 6.1 are also suggested. Again, if these measures are changing in the desirable direction while total habitat area is not decreasing, it can be inferred that biodiversity will benefit. The various measures of patch shape

are suggested for optional consideration as they have not been as conclusively tied to biodiversity benefits in urban environments as they have in rural environments. Nonetheless, these are easy to calculate once a habitat patch and matrix classification has been established for a given landscape, and they may provide useful information supplemental to the other measures.

6.4.2 Recommendations for Further Research

6.4.2.1 Evaluate whether an effective distance approach would improve engineering decision making.

Using Euclidean nearest neighbor distance as a proxy for dispersal assumes that areas between habitat patches are completely unsuitable to support indicator species. Future research can explore using a continuous scale of suitability for these areas to produce measures of effective distance that consider the difficulty of travel. This is a common practice in conservation planning. The relevant research question in a planning and engineering context is whether adding this layer of complexity to the analysis would improve decision making (such as choosing between alternative bioretention siting alternatives or policies) compared to the simpler approach.

6.4.2.2 Consider further development of network (graph) theory-based metrics in an urban planning and engineering context.

While characterizing the distribution of distances between patches in the landscape provides valuable information, network theory-based measures provide additional information on the connectivity and centrality of particular patches within the larger network. These measures may be able to identify critical “stepping stone” patches whose loss would significantly degrade overall connectivity of the landscape. These ideas could be further tested in an urban context to determine whether the information they provide can further improve decision making in a planning and engineering context in addition to the measures discussed in Section 6.4.1.

6.4.2.3 Evaluate whether a dynamic modeling approach would improve engineering decision making.

With more research and interdisciplinary collaboration in the future, a goal could be for practicing engineers to be able predict the impacts of a new design or policy on the spatial and temporal dynamics of an indicator species in a landscape. The scale and configuration required to achieve desired impacts could then be aligned with the scale and configuration required to achieve desired hydrologic and water quality outcomes. Using information on the spatial arrangement of habitat patches and available data on dispersal, dynamic models can produce quantitative projections of populations of indicator species in the landscape, allowing computation of biodiversity indices.

An open question for further research is whether the simplified approach suggested by Levins (1969) would be sufficient to improve decision making in land use planning and engineering relative to use of the static geographic measures alone. If the Levins (1969) approach is found to be too simplistic to improve decision making, as some researchers have suggested, the approach suggested by Hanski (1998) could be explored. This approach may be attractive in an engineering context because it is based on relatively few parameters, is spatially explicit, incorporates dynamic processes and time lags relevant to systems not in a state of equilibrium, and is validated to extensive field data on butterfly movements. Even more detailed simulation approaches using many more input variables are available and could be explored to determine whether they would improve decision making, albeit at a cost in effort and time spent in a planning and engineering decision context. Put another way, a research question could be which method represents the least cost of data collection and modeling effort to yield a result that will improve decisions sufficiently on professional planning and engineering projects.

6.4.2.4 Further explore the role of urban habitat connectivity in facilitating climate adaptation.

As discussed above, understanding dispersal is a key to projecting whether the population of an organism will be stable, increasing, or declining over time in a fragmented habitat. The ability to move between patches can impact a population's ability to recover from short-term disturbances such as storms and fires. Over longer periods of time, dispersal is also a key to understanding whether organisms, including plants and butterflies, can successfully expand or shift their ranges to adapt to climate change. As environmental characteristics such as temperature and available soil moisture shift spatially over time, habitat fragmentation in urban areas may act as barriers preventing organisms from being able to expand and shift their ranges in response to these changing conditions. Improving habitat connectivity and reducing fragmentation in urban areas may help mitigate this effect (e.g., see Oliver et al., 2015). Future research can explore the role in bioretention basin placement, in the larger context of urban green infrastructure networks, in facilitating both the resilience of plant and animal populations to short-term disturbance events and to longer-term climate shifts.

CHAPTER 7. Summary of Conclusions and Engineering Applications

7.1 Answers to Research Questions

This research project has sought to identify specific metrics and methods engineers can employ to improve the terrestrial ecological functions in and around bioretention basins designed to manage urban surface runoff. The research has been motivated by the documented decline in natural habitats and biodiversity globally, including declines in insect habitat, abundance, and diversity in urban areas. Insect herbivores are a critical element of terrestrial ecosystems because they enable flows of energy, carbon, and nutrients from green plants to higher trophic levels. *Lepidoptera* species, butterflies and moths, have been shown to be particularly important because they transfer more energy and mass between trophic levels than all other insect herbivores. Their larval host plants, habitat preferences and dispersal characteristics have been widely studied, making them suitable indicators of habitat adequacy and connectivity in urban environments. Finally, they are sensitive to environmental conditions and environmental change, including longer term climate change. Planning and design choices that intentionally support butterfly diversity in and around bioretention basins can therefore be expected to improve terrestrial ecological outcomes. The research has sought to provide answers to four formal research questions relevant to these choices, while also suggesting a planning and design framework demonstrated for one region and adaptable to other regions, infrastructure types or environmental conditions. These conclusions are specific to systems with designs and boundary conditions similar to the Bioinfiltration Traffic Island at Villanova University, representing a typical bioretention design for the region. These assumptions include the presence of native soil deep enough to accommodate the roots of the bioretention plant species considered, absence of shallow bedrock, and absence of a shallow water table (i.e., the capillary fringe does not extend from the water table to the bottom of the plant roots).

Research Question 1.1: To increase measures of ecological performance at the site scale, is it necessary to accept decreases in traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures?

Research Question 1.1 is answered in Table 4.12. No significant relationship was found between plant or *Lepidoptera* biodiversity and surface outflow volume. Surface outflow volume can also be interpreted as a proxy for effluent nitrogen loads. This result is encouraging, indicating that a combination of design configuration and plant choices exists that can achieve the traditional engineering objectives of limiting surface outflow and effluent pollutant loads while at the same time maximizing potential biodiversity at the site scale. A significant tradeoff was found between groundwater recharge volume (a proxy for the hydrologic regulation functional objective) and potential biodiversity. In other words, it is necessary to accept a reduced groundwater recharge volume (i.e., worse hydrologic regulation performance) in order to increase biodiversity for the range of designs considered in this study. This tradeoff exists because groundwater recharge volume (a measure of design performance) and ponding duration (a description of an environmental condition) are closely related, and some plants that promote greater biodiversity are adversely impacted by longer durations of saturated soils. A significant positive relationship was found between evapotranspiration and biodiversity. This relationship is a logical converse of the saturated soil-biodiversity relationship – greater durations of unsaturated soil conditions lead to greater transpiration. The study found significant relationships between peak flow reduction objectives and biodiversity objectives. However, in many cases the best design choice will be to include an offline storage element in parallel or in series with the bioretention design in order to achieve peak flow control for larger, infrequent storms.

Research Question 1.2: Under projected end-of-century rainfall and temperature conditions, will it be necessary to accept decreases in additional traditional engineering stormwater management performance measures compared to the results of Research Question 1.1?

Research Question 1.2 is answered in Chapter 5 within a limited context permitted by the study design. Results indicated that the time pattern of soil moisture in the bioretention designs studied can be expected to change by the 2081-2100 time period relative to the 1995-2014 period. Under the worst-case scenario SSP5-8.5, while the magnitude of wet weather events increases relative to the baseline time period, temperatures and the duration of dry periods also increase. This result suggests that drought-tolerant plant taxa will continue to be necessary in bioretention basins, unless maintenance practices such as irrigation or periodic replacement of vegetation are adopted to offset the projected changes in environmental conditions. However, since drought tolerant taxa are already required to maximize biodiversity under existing conditions, the answer to Research Question 1.2 is that no further tradeoffs are required to maximize biodiversity for the future climate scenario compared to the historical scenario studied under Research Question 1.1. This research result will have limited applicability to practice without further investigation for several reasons. First, only change in the soil moisture regime was considered. Direct physiological effects of increased heat on both plants and indicator species should also be considered before developing recommendations for practice. Second, this result does not consider the possibility that species of interest may be absent from the surrounding landscape (see Chapter 6 and Research Question 2) under future climatic conditions, and this limitation may lead to extinction of the species in a local habitat patch such as a bioretention basin even if environmental conditions in the patch are suitable for the species.

Research Question 1.3: What subset of traditional and ecological performance measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that will provide actionable information to a professional bioretention designer seeking to rank design alternatives?

Research Question 1.3 is answered in Section 4.4. A minimal set of performance measures recommended in a practical design decision making framework includes annual groundwater recharge volume (a proxy for hydrologic cycle management), surface outflow volume (a proxy for surface effluent pollutant loads), peak flow reduction for one or more events with potential to erode stream channels, the plant diversity index presented in Chapter 4, and the *Lepidoptera* diversity index presented in Chapter 4. These performance measures can be weighted according to stakeholder preferences to inform the ultimate choice of a design or policy.

Research Question 2: What subset of habitat connectivity measures is suitable for inclusion in a composite index that can provide actionable information to decision makers with influence over bioretention placement and land use policy?

Research Question 2 is answered in Section 6.4.1. The most important measure to track when comparing alternative designs, plans, or policies at the watershed scale is simply the total habitat area. A second recommended measure is the distribution (for example, mean and standard deviation) of Euclidean nearest neighbor distance, the straight-line distance between pairs of suitable habitat patches in the larger landscape. Five additional measures of habitat fragmentation are recommended, as defined and discussed in Section 6.4.1. Additional measures, including measures of patch shape, are less important but easy to calculate, and these may also be considered.

7.2 Products and Recommendations for Professional Water Resources Engineering Practice

In addition to answering the formal research questions presented in Section 7.1, this research project has produced knowledge and products of immediate use both to academic researchers and to water resources engineers in professional practice. The literature review presented in Chapter 2 surveys suggestions made to date on designing bioretention and other green stormwater installations to promote terrestrial ecosystem function. Chapter 2 includes a list and discussion identifying a wide range of open data available to researchers and practitioners interested in incorporating terrestrial ecosystem functional objectives into their work. Finally, Chapter 2 concludes with a list and detailed discussion of potential future research topics at the intersection of water resources engineering and ecology.

Chapter 3 provides a description and analysis of a new compilation of plant recommendations made by a range of published government and industry bioretention design guidelines. This information will be of immediate use to planning and design practitioners in the U.S. Northeast and Midwest regions. It will expand the range of plant choices to consider for professionals currently consulting a single source of design guidelines. Practitioners will be able to filter and sort the data set by variables such as geographic range, native status, and tolerance (as stated by the manuals) to extremes of wet conditions, dry conditions, and loads of deicing salts.

Chapter 4 presents a planning and design decision framework, and this framework is demonstrated with example specific performance measures for practitioners to consider incorporating when applying the framework within a project context. These performance measures address both traditional engineering performance objectives and terrestrial ecological function objectives. The suggested measures can be derived from simulated or observed time

series of water level and temperature using models and methods familiar to many practicing engineers and can be combined with other measures deemed important by the practitioner.

Chapter 5 suggests a specific procedure for choosing global circulation models to inform planning and design decisions in urban water resources systems under projected climate change conditions. Criteria considered in the suggested procedure can be weighted in relation to the objectives of a specific urban water resources engineering project, such as a bioretention design. Chapter 5 also explores an experimental procedure for adjusting observed precipitation time series to represent future conditions. This procedure may produce time series that appropriately capture temporal patterns and variation at time scales relevant to urban water planning and engineering projects.

Chapter 6 gathers information from the literature on landscape/watershed scale habitat connectivity indices that may be relevant to networks of green stormwater infrastructure installations. While additional research on this topic is recommended to refine the most appropriate approaches for planning and policy applications, some recommendations are offered that should immediately improve outcomes in professional practice. The chapter identifies measures of habitat fragmentation and connectivity that can be developed from widely available land use/land cover data using geographic information systems. Two key measures are the total area of suitable habitat and distribution of Euclidean (straight line) distances between neighboring habitat patches. Measures of habitat fragmentation and patch shape are suggested to supplement these two key measures. Larger scale planning exercises such as development of watershed plans, zoning codes, and comprehensive plans can calculate values of these metrics with and without projected green stormwater infrastructure installations. By quantifying

improvements in these metrics under alternative plans or policy choices, the contribution of green stormwater infrastructure to urban ecology at larger scales can begin to be understood.

7.3 Recommendations for Further Research

Chapter 2 includes extensive suggestions for further research, including many interdisciplinary topics at the intersection of water resources engineering and urban ecology. These topics include further development of the role bioretention plants can play in nectar provision and pollination both at the site scale and at the watershed scale. Another topic suggested in the literature review that is highly relevant to engineers and architects working at the site scale is the influence of design choices on microclimates and the influence of microclimates on biodiversity. A number of potential research topics are suggested that explore the temporal, spatial, and stochastic complexity of urban ecosystems. In an engineering context informed by ecology, research questions should focus on what level of complexity needs to be accounted for in order to improve design outcomes.

Chapter 6 proposes additional research to refine approaches to evaluating the effects of bioretention placement on habitat connectivity. These include refining the Euclidean nearest neighbor distance metric to consider travel difficulty, considering approaches based in network (graph) theory, and considering dynamic modeling approaches able to provide quantitative population projections for organisms within patches and across all patches in the landscape.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Additional Information on the Bioretention Plant Data Set

Appendix B: Additional Information on BTI Field Data

Appendix C: Additional Information on Validation Measures

Appendix D: Additional Information on Wet Weather Events Representing Peak Flow Objectives

Appendix E: Additional Details and Discussion of Figure 4.14

Appendix F: Larval Host Plants for 100 or More Species of *Lepidoptera*

Appendix G: Additional Analysis of Climate Change Bioretention Simulations

Appendix A: Additional Information on the Bioretention Plant Data Set

Sections A.1 through A.7 contain additional details on how the data in the original source documents was processed to create the master bioretention plant data set. Section A.8 contains a description of all the fields included in the master data set. Please note that descriptions of some variables in Section A.8 refer to lookup tables presented in Sections A.1 through A.7.

A.1 Additional Notes on Taxonomy and Standardized Plant Names

Scientific names listed in each of the data sources were reduced to a genus and species name. More specifically, some sources included a cultivar, variety or sub-species name, and this information was not considered in matching across databases. The original source information was preserved and is available for users of the master data set to inspect. The scientific names (genus and species only) listed in each source were first matched to the name (genus and species only) in the USDA PLANTS database. For the majority of plant taxa in all the data sets, this step resulted in a match and no further steps were necessary. For taxa that did not result in an exact match, the species information stated in the original source was manually looked up in the online version of the USDA PLANTS database. This database lists a large number of pseudonyms for many taxa, and in many cases one of the pseudonyms listed matched the name used in the source data sets. In cases where an exact match did not occur, listed names were looked up using a general internet search (Google search engine) to identify small spelling errors and variations in names. In most cases, a single clear match then emerged from this analysis. In a small number of cases where no unique match was found through the above processes, I made a decision based on the following hierarchy: (1) most similar scientific name (genus and species) between a pseudonym in USDA PLANTS and the name used by the source, (2) most similar variety or sub-species name (i.e., occasionally the species name in a source is listed as a sub-species in USDA

PLANTS or vice versa), (3) largest reported geographic distribution when choosing between closely related species, and finally (4) higher position on the list on the USDA website (used in very few cases).

Once scientific names were standardized to be consistent with USDA PLANTS, they were then matched whenever possible to scientific names in the 2020 National Wetland Plant List. In the vast majority of cases, names in the National Wetland Plant List match the name listed in USDA PLANTS. In a small number of cases, they match a pseudonym or contain a minor spelling variation compared to the closest match in USDA PLANTS.

USDA PLANTS also includes taxonomic information for most species. For a small number of species with no family group listed in USDA PLANTS, I manually looked up family groups through a general internet search identifying sources such as the Lady Bird Johnson Wildflower Center, Missouri Botanical Garden, and state agricultural extension services. I chose to characterize native/introduced status using the USDA PLANTS category “L48 (N)” to denote a native plant taxon, with all other categories coded as “non-native or unclassified”. Native/non-native information is available for most taxa in the data set. The small number of plants in the data set considered “introduced” were lumped together with the small number of taxa with no information on native status.

A.2 Notes on the NWPL Wetland Indicator Ratings

The NWPL applies wetland indicator ratings on a regional basis. I assigned a priority hierarchy to these regions in determining a single standardized rating to report in the master data set. For example, if the first region in the hierarchy has a wetland indicator rating assigned, that rating becomes the standardized value of the rating in the master data set. If no rating is assigned to the first region in the hierarchy, the rating assigned to the second region becomes the

standardized rating in the master data set. This procedure continues through the hierarchy. The hierarchy of regions is (1) Eastern Mountains and Piedmont, (2) Midwest, (3) Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plain, (4) Northcentral and Northeast, (5) Great Plains.

A.3 Notes on Standardization of Growth Habit (Woody/Herbaceous) Categories

The sources use a variety of qualitative categories to describe plant growth habits, and these categories are not always consistent between sources. I chose to simplify growth habit to the binary description “woody or herbaceous” because site designers may wish to filter the database using this categorization depending on urban context of a site (e.g., larger trees and shrubs might be appropriate in a parking lot bioretention system but not a sidewalk bioretention system near an intersection if they would occlude a traffic sign or signal). I derived a standardized growth habit value from USDA PLANTS whenever this was available, and filled in values from other sources when this was not available using the PADEP value followed by a manual internet search for the species (very few cases). For the small number of vines included in the data set, a manual internet search was conducted to determine whether these species are predominately herbaceous or typically include woody tissues. Full details of lookup codes are provided in the data description supplement.

Table A.1

Growth Habit (USDA)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Graminoid	Herbaceous
Forb/herb, Subshrub	Herbaceous
Forb/herb	Herbaceous
Tree	Woody
Tree, Shrub	Woody
Vine, Subshrub	Woody
Shrub	Woody
Vine	(varies)
Shrub, Subshrub	Woody
Subshrub, Forb/herb	Woody
Subshrub, Shrub	Woody
Shrub, Tree	Woody
Tree, Subshrub, Shrub	Woody
Subshrub	Woody
Subshrub, Shrub, Forb/herb	Woody
NA	NA

Table A.2

Plant Type (PADEP)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Grass	Herbaceous
Forb	Herbaceous
Grass-like	Herbaceous
Fern	Herbaceous
Grass-like	Herbaceous
Shrub	Woody
Tree (small)	Woody
Tree	Woody
NA	NA

Table A.3

Plant Type (St. Louis)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Forbs	Herbaceous
Grasses/Sedges	Herbaceous
Trees/Shrubs	Woody

Table A.4

Growth Habit (Toronto)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Nurse Crops	Herbaceous
Broadleaf Herbaceous and Ferns	Herbaceous
Graminoids	Herbaceous
Trees	Woody
Shrubs	Woody
Vines	(varies)

A.4 Notes on Standardization of Ponding Tolerance Categories

The tables below match codes in each of the source documents to a standardized ponding tolerance ratings on a scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant).

Table A.5

Wetland Class (NWPL)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
UPL	1
FACU	1
FAC	2
FACW	3
OBL	3
NA	NA

Table A.6

Anaerobic Tolerance (USDA)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
None	1
Low	1
Medium	2
High	3
NA	NA

Table A.7

Inundation Frequency (Shaw and Schmidt)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Low	1
Low-Mod	1
Mod-Low	2
Mod	2
High	3
NA	NA

Table A.8

Inundation Frequency (Maryland)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
NO"	1
SALT,EDGE	1
SALT, EDGE	1
LIMITED	1
SEASONAL	2
SOME	2
0-3'	3
REG.INUNDA	3
1' MIN-24'	3
YES	3
SATURATED	3
SATURATE	3
2\-1"	3
1' MIN	3
0-3"	3
6\SATURATE"	3
1-3'	3
SAT.0-6\'' SAT.	3
6\-'Sat"	3
2-6'	3
0-6\''"	3
0-6\''	3
1' MIN-6'	3
0-2'	3
SAT. 0-2'	3
1-5'	3
Free Float	3
0-1\''"	3
NA	NA

Table A.9

Inundation Tolerance (PADEP)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
No	1
Seasonal	2
sat, 0-1'	3
Sat. 0-3'	3
0-6\	3
sat, 1'\r\nmin.	3
Saturated	3
sat, 0-6\ " Yes"	3
0-12\ " 0-6\ ""	3
Saturated"	3
sat, 0-3\ " Saturated,	3
Sat, 0-6\ " Sat.	3
0-1'	3
sat, 0-2'	3
0-6\ ""	3
0-6\ ""	3
0-3'	3
0-6\,	3
Saturated, 0-2'	3
Saturated"	3
NA	NA

Table A.10

Flood Frequency Tolerance (St. Louis)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
L	1
M	2
H	3
N	NA

Table A.11

Landscape Zone (St. Louis)				
Source Rating				Standardized Rating
Pond Edge and Permanent Water	Lower Slopes and Bioretention Base	Upper Slopes	Over Sand	
N	N	Y	anyvalue	1
N	Y	anyvalue	anyvalue	2
Y	anyvalue	anyvalue	anyvalue	3
N	N	N	Y	NA
N	N	N	N	NA

Table A.12

Hydrologic Zone (Maryland)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
[6]	1
3,4,[5,6]	1
[5],6	1
4,[5,6]	1
5,6	1
2,[3,4]	2
[3,4],5	2
4,5,6	2
3,[4,5],6	2
1,2,[3,4,5]	2
3,[4,5,6]	2
2,3,[4,5],6	2
3,4,5	2
[3,4,5],6	2
[4],5	2
2,[3,4,5],6	2
[3,4,5,6]	2
[4,5,6]	2
3,[4,5]	2
1,2,[3,4,5],	2
[4,5]	2
[4,5],6	2
2[3,4]	2
2,[3,4],5	2
2,[3,4,5]	2
[2],[3,4]	2
3,4,5,6	2
[3,4,5]	2
2,[3,4,5,6]	2
3,4	2
1,[2,3,4,5],	3
1,[2,3],4	3
[1,2],4	3
1,[2],3	3
[1,2]	3
1,2,3	3
[2,3],4	3
[1,2],3	3
[1,2,3],4	3
[1,2],3,4	3
[1,2,3,4],5,	3
[2,3,4,5],6	3
1,[2,3]	3
2,3,4	3
[1,2,3]	3
[2,3,4],5	3
2,3,4,5,6	3
1[2,3]	3
1,[2,3,4],5	3
[1,2],3	3
1,[2,3,4,5,6]	3
[1,2],3	3
2,3	3
[2,3],4	3

Table A.13

Hydrologic Zone (PADEP)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
5, 6	1
4,[5,6]	1
5,6	1
4 (5,6)	1
6	1
3,[4,5]	2
2,[3,4]	2
2, (3, 4)	2
Outer	2
3, 4, 5, 6	2
(4,5) 6	2
2,(3,4),5	2
(3) 4, 5, 6	2
4, 5, 6	2
(4, 5) 6	2
3 (4) 5	2
2 (3, 4)	2
(3),4,5,6	2
[3,4],5,6	2
[3,4],5	2
3, 4, 6	2
(3, 4) 5	2
3,4	2
[4,5],6	2
3, 4, 5	2
1, 2 (3) 4	2
4, 5	2
3,4,5	2
(3,4),5	2
(4,5,6)	2
3, 4	2
4,5,6	2
3 (4, 5)	2
3,[4,5],6	2
2,[3,4],5	2
(4,5),6	2
3,4,5,6	2
3(4,5),6	2
[1,2],3	3
1, (2, 3)	3
[1,2],3,4	3
[2,3],4	3
2,3	3
2,3,4,5,6	3
2	3
2,3,4,5	3
1 (2,3) 4	3
(2, 3), 4	3
(2, 3) 4	3
1, 2, 3	3
1	3
2, 3	3
(2,3),4	3
1,(2,3),4	3

A.5 Notes on Standardization of Drought Tolerance Categories

The tables below match codes in each of the source documents to a standardized drought tolerance rating on a scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant).

Table A.14

Drought Tolerance (PADEP)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
L	1
N	1
No	1
M	2
H	3
NA	NA

Table A.15

Water Use (USDA)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
High	1
Medium	2
Low	3
NA	NA

Table A.16

Water Preference (NGA)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
In Water	1
Wet	1
Wet Mesic	1.5
Mesic	2
Dry Mesic	2.5
Dry	3

Table A.17

Soil Moisture (Toronto)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
W	1.00
WM	1.50
W-M	1.50
WM-M	1.75
W-MD	1.75
WM-MD	2.00
WM-DM	2.00
W-D	2.00
M	2.00
WM-D	2.25
M-MD	2.25
M-DM	2.25
M-D	2.50
MD-D	2.75
D	3.00
Variable	NA

Table A.18

Drought Tolerance (Toronto)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
L	1.0
L-M	1.5
M-L	1.5
M	2.0
M-H	2.5
H/M	2.5
H	3.0

Table A.19

Soil Moisture (St. Louis)			
Dry	Medium	Wet	Standardized Rating
Y	N	N	3.0
Y	Y	N	2.5
N	Y	N	2.0
Y	Y	Y	2.0
N	Y	Y	1.5
N	N	Y	1.0

A.6 Notes on Standardization of Salt Tolerance Categories

The tables below match codes in each of the source documents to a standardized salt tolerance ratings on a scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant).

Table A.20

PADEP (2023)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
N	1
L	1
M	2
H	3
High	3
(blank)	NA
U	NA
NA	NA

Table A.21

Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
N	1
L	1
M	2
H	3
V	NA

Table A.22

Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
L	1.0
L-M	1.5
M	2.0
M-H	2.5
H	3.0
NA	NA
Unknown	NA

Table A.23

Maryland (2009)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
N	1
Y	3
NA	NA

Table A.24

Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
Low	1.0
Moderate to low	1.5
Low to moderate	1.5
Moderately high for spray and moderately low for soil	2.0
Moderate	2.0
Low to high	2.0
Moderate (Tolerates salty soil and water)	2.0
Low to 2,4-D; moderate to soil salt and high to spray	2.0
Moderate; low to 2,4-D	2.0
Moderate to high	2.5
Moderate to high (will tolerate salty soil and water)	2.5
High	3.0
High, especially for soil salt and lower for spray	3.0
Salinity resistant	3.0
NA	NA
Unknown	NA

Table A.25

USDA PLANTS	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
None	1
Low	1
Medium	2
High	3
NA	NA

Table A.26

Toronto	
Source Rating	Standardized Rating
NA	NA
Unknown	NA
L	1.0
L-M	1.5
M	2.0
M-H	2.5
H	3.0

A.7 Notes on Data Processing

Data sets were obtained in spreadsheet form where possible. For example, the Pennsylvania data set was posted online for public comment in 2023 and was available to the research team in spreadsheet format. The Toronto data set is provided online in spreadsheet form. For data sets posted only in portable document format (pdf), these were saved as spreadsheets when possible. When this did not result in a readable table, optical character recognition software

(Microsoft Lens) was employed. For the St. Louis data set only, it was necessary to manually enter values from a table image into a spreadsheet.

State-level geographic distribution information in USDA PLANTS was processed to create 35 fields each representing one of the states intersecting the Eastern Temperate Forests Level 1 Ecoregion. Each of these fields was then populated with a 1 or a 0 indicating that the plant species is or is not known to occur in that state. This data format allows users with any level of experience to identify species known to occur within a user-specified state or group of states.

A.8 Metadata

This section contains descriptions of all fields in the master data set.

Table A.27

Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
plant_type_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	plant type as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.2)
scientific_name_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
common_name_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
wetland_indicator_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	wetland indicator rating as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.5; note ratings may include +/- designations from an earlier release of the NWPL)
hydrologic_zone_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	hydrologic zone used in pond design as shown in raw data; original source not documented	categorical (see Table A.13)
inundation_tolerance_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	ponding depth tolerance as shown in raw data	mixed quantitative and qualitative (see Table A.9)
drought_tolerance_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	drought tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.14)
salt_tolerance_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.20)
mature_canopy_spread_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	mature canopy diameter as shown in raw data	numeric (feet)
mature_height_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	mature height as shown in raw data	numeric (feet)
light_requirement_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	light requirement as shown in raw data	categorical (e.g., "Full Sun", "Part Shade")
commercial_availability_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	commercial availability as shown in raw data	categorical (C=container; P=plug; S=seed)
hardiness_zone_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	USDA cold hardiness zone as shown in raw data	range (e.g., "3-9")

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
wildlife_value_notes_padep_raw	PADEP (2023)	wildlife value notes as shown in raw data	free text
scientific_name_padep_corrected	interpreted from PADEP (2023)	scientific name with minor corrections to match most similar name listed in USDA PLANTS	free text
scientific_name_standardized	interpreted from USDA (2022)	scientific name chosen as most accepted according to information in USDA PLANTS, shortened to genus and species only (see Section A.1 for details)	free text
scientific_name_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
type_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	plant type as shown in raw data	free text
common_name_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
form_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	plant form as shown in raw data	categorical (e.g., "Annual", "Fern", "Grass")
hydrologic_zone_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	hydrologic zone used in pond design as shown in raw data; original source not documented	categorical (see Table A.12)
wetland_indicator_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	wetland indicator rating as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.5; note ratings may include +/- designations from an earlier release of the NWPL)
inundation_tolerance_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	inundation tolerance as shown in raw data	mixed quantitative and qualitative (e.g., "SEASONAL", "SATURATED" "0-3")
pollution_tolerance_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	pollution tolerance as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
salt_tolerance_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N; see Table A.23)
hardiness_zone_md_raw	Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	USDA cold hardiness zone as shown in raw data	range (e.g., "3-9")
scientific_name_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
genus_standardized	USDA (2022)	genus name as shown in USDA PLANTS	free text
common_name_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
water_level_in_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	"water level" or soil moisture preference as shown in raw data	categorical (D = "Dry soils"; I = "Inundation"; M = "Moist/mesic soils"; S = "Saturated soils")
inundation_frequency_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	"inundation frequency" as shown in raw data	categorical ("Low", "Low-Mod", "Mod-Low", "Mod", "High")
max_inundation_in_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	maximum water depth tolerated as shown in raw data	inches
max_inundation_duration_days_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	maximum ponding duration tolerated as shown in raw data	days
salt_tolerance_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.24)

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
nutrient_tolerance_ss_raw	Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	nutrient tolerance as shown in raw data	free text
scientific_name_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
symbol_usda	USDA (2022)	unique symbol	alphanumeric code
smp_type_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	stormwater management practice type as shown in raw data	categorical (e.g., "Bioretention and Organic Filters")
scientific_name_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
plant_type_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	plant type as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.3)
common_name_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
submerged_and_emergent_water_depth_in_feet_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	ponding depth tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical: 0-1 feet, "Y", "N"
pond_edge_and_permanent_water_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for pond edges and open water, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
over_sand_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for planting in sand, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
lower_slopes_and_bioretention_base_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for bioretention lower slopes and bottom, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
upper_slopes_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for bioretention upper slopes, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
height_min_feet_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	minimum of height range, as shown in raw data	feet
height_max_feet_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	maximum of height range, as shown in raw data	feet
spacing_feet_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	plant center spacing, as shown in raw data	feet
seasonal_interest_color_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	flower color, as shown in raw data	categorical (e.g., "white", "plum")
seasonal_interest_jan_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in January, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_feb_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in February, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_mar_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in March, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_apr_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in April, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_may_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in May, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_june_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in June, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_july_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in July, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_aug_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in August, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_sep_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in September, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
seasonal_interest_oct_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in October, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_nov_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in November, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
seasonal_interest_dec_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides visual interest in December, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
sun_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for full sun, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
pt_sun_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for partial sun, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
pt_shade_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for partial shade, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
shade_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for shade, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
dry_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for dry soil conditions, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N; see Table A.19)
medium_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for mesic soil conditions, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N; see Table A.19)
wet_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	suitability for wet soil conditions, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N; see Table A.19)
birds_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	supports birds, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
butterflies_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	supports butterflies, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
fall_color_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides fall color, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
winter_interest_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	provides winter interest, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
flood_frequency_tolerance_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	flood frequency tolerance, as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.10)
flood_height_tolerance_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	ponding depth tolerance as shown in raw data	inches
flood_duration_tolerance_days_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	maximum ponding duration tolerated as shown in raw data	days
salt_tolerance_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.21)
aggressiveness_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	aggressiveness as shown in raw data	categorical (Low, Medium, High)
silt_tolerance_stlouis_raw	Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	silt/sediment tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (Low, Medium, High)
inundation_tolerance_landscape_zone_stlouis_standardized	interpreted from Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	standardized inundation tolerance	categorical (see Table A.11)
drought_tolerance_st_louis_standardized	interpreted from Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	standardized drought tolerance	categorical (see Table A.19)
flood_frequency_tolerance_stlouis_standardized	interpreted from Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	standardized flood frequency tolerance	categorical (see Table A.10)
salt_tolerance_stlouis_standardized	interpreted from Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.21)
plant_type_stlouis_standardized	interpreted from Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012)	standardized plant type	categorical (see Table A.3)

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
growth_habit_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	plant type as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.4)
scientific_name_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	scientific name as shown in raw data	free text
common_name_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
recommended_as_seed_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	recommended to grow from seed, as shown in raw data	logical (Y/N)
soil_type_preference_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	soil texture preference, as shown in raw data	categorical (S = Sand, L = Loam, C = Clay; including combinations)
soil_moisture_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	soil moisture preference, as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.17)
coefficient_of_wetness_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	wetland indicator rating as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.5; note ratings may include +/- designations from an earlier release of the NWPL)
exposure_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	light requirement as shown in raw data	categorical (e.g., "Sun", "Sun / Part Shade")
drought_tolerance_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	drought tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.18)
salt_tolerance_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.26)
urban_tolerances_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	urban stressor tolerance, as shown in raw data	categorical (P = "Pollution", C = "Compaction"; including combinations)
growth_rate_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	growth rate, as shown in raw data	categorical (S = "Slow", M = "Medium", F = "Fast"; includes intermediate values)
height_spread_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	height and spread, as shown in raw data	m, cm (mixed)
spacing_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	spacing, as shown in raw data	cm
ranking_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	ranking, as shown in raw data	categorical (1 = "Selective", 2 = "Selective", 3 = "Better", 4 = "Best", NN = "Non-native")
aesthetic_attributes_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	aesthetic attributes, as shown in raw data	free text
other_information_toronto_raw	Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	other information, as shown in raw data	free text
drought_tolerance_toronto_standardized	interpreted from Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	standardized drought tolerance	categorical (see Table A.18)
salt_tolerance_toronto_standardized	interpreted from Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.26)
soil_moisture_toronto_standardized	interpreted from Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	standardized soil moisture tolerance	categorical (see Table A.17)
growth_habit_toronto_standardized	interpreted from Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010)	standardized plant type	categorical (see Table A.4)
wetland_class_atlantic_and_gulf_coastal_plain_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	wetland indicator rating (Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plain region)	categorical (see Table A.5)
wetland_class_eastern_mountains_and_piedmont_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	wetland indicator rating (Eastern Mountains and Piedmont region)	categorical (see Table A.5)

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
wetland_class_great_plains_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	wetland indicator rating (Great Plains region)	categorical (see Table A.5)
wetland_class_midwest_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	wetland indicator rating (Midwest region)	categorical (see Table A.5)
wetland_class_northcentral_and_northeast_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	wetland indicator rating (Northcentral and Northeast region)	categorical (see Table A.5)
common_name_nwpl	NWPL (2020)	common name as shown in raw data	free text
wetland_class	interpreted from NWPL (2020)	standardized wetland class assigned by geographical hierarchy (see Section A.2)	categorical (see Table A.5)
scientific_name_usda	USDA (2022)	scientific name chosen as most accepted according to information in USDA PLANTS, including cultivars/varieties/sub-species where applicable (see Section A.1 for details)	free text
Family	USDA (2022); various	botanical Family (see Section A.1 for details)	free text
growth_habit_usda	USDA (2022)	plant type as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.1)
native_status_usda	USDA (2022)	North America native status as shown in raw data	categorical (see Section A.1)
anaerobic_tolerance_usda	USDA (2022)	anaerobic tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.6)
drought_tolerance_usda	USDA (2022)	drought tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (Low/Medium/High)
moisture_use_usda	USDA (2022)	water use, as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.15)
salinity_tolerance_usda	USDA (2022)	salt tolerance as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.25)
RootDepthMinimum	USDA (2022)	minimum root depth, as shown in raw data	inches
FederalNoxiousStatus	USDA (2022)	U.S. Federal noxious weed status, as shown in raw data	N/A (as of May 2025, no plant species included in the database have this field populated)
StateNoxiousStatus	USDA (2022)	U.S. state-level noxious weed status, as shown in raw data	list of states and alphanumeric codes (e.g., "PIB", "P"; no publicly available definitions)
Invasive	USDA (2022)	invasive status, as shown in raw data	categorical (list of geographic regions, e.g., "N" "EAST"; no publicly available definitions)
Federal_TE_Status	USDA (2022)	U.S. Federal threatened and endangered status, as shown in raw data	categorical ("Threatened", not applicable)
State_TE_Status	USDA (2022)	U.S. state threatened and endangered status, as shown in raw data	list of states and numeric codes (e.g., E, T, SC; no publicly available definitions)
State	USDA (2022)	U.S. states where this plant species is reported to occur, as shown in raw data	list of U.S. state codes
salt_tolerance_padep_standardized	interpreted from PADEP (2023)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.20)

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Variable	Source	Description/Definition	Units/Scale
salt_tolerance_md_standardized	interpreted from Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.23)
salt_tolerance_ss_standardized	interpreted from Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.24)
SalinityTolerance_standardized	interpreted from USDA (2022)	standardized salt tolerance	categorical (see Table A.25)
salt_tolerance_standardized	various	standardized salt tolerance rating based on mean of all sources	categorical (see Section A.6 and Tables A.20 through A.26)
drought_tolerance_padep_standardized	interpreted from PADEP (2023)	standardized drought tolerance	categorical (see Table A.14)
DroughtTolerance_standardized	interpreted from USDA (2022)	standardized drought tolerance	categorical (Low, Medium, High)
MoistureUse_standardized	interpreted from USDA (2022)	standardized water use	categorical (see Table A.15)
wetland_class_drought_tolerance_standardized	interpreted from NWPL (2020)	standardized drought indicator based on wetland class	categorical (see Section 3.2.2)
water_preference_nga	National Gardening Association (2025)	water preference as shown in raw data	categorical (see Table A.16)
drought_tolerance_standardized	synthesis of multiple sources	standardized drought tolerance based on mean of all sources	scale of 1 (least drought tolerant) to 3 (most drought tolerant)
hydrologic_zone_padep_standardized	interpreted from PADEP (2023)	standardized hydrologic zone	categorical (see Table A.13)
inundation_tolerance_padep_standardized	interpreted from PADEP (2023)	standardized inundation tolerance	categorical (see Table A.9)
hydrologic_zone_md_standardized	interpreted from Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	standardized hydrologic zone	categorical (see Table A.12)
inundation_tolerance_md_standardized	interpreted from Center for Watershed Protection (2009)	standardized inundation tolerance	categorical (see Table A.8)
inundation_frequency_ss_standardized	interpreted from Shaw and Schmidt (2003)	standardized inundation frequency	categorical (see Table A.7)
wetland_class_standardized	interpreted from NWPL (2020)	standardized wetland indicator rating	scale of 1 (least drought tolerant) to 3 (most drought tolerant)
AnaerobicTolerance_standardized	interpreted from USDA (2022)	standardized anaerobic tolerance	categorical (see Table A.6)
mean_inundation_tolerance_standardized1	interpreted from NWPL (2020)	standardized wetland indicator rating based on NWPL	categorical (see Table A.5)
mean_inundation_tolerance_standardized2	synthesis of multiple sources	standardized wetland indicator rating based on mean of sources other than NWPL	categorical (see Section 3.2.2 and Tables A.6 through A.13)
inundation_tolerance_standardized	synthesis of multiple sources	standardized wetland indicator rating based on NWPL if available, other sources if NWPL not available	categorical (see Section 3.2.2 and Tables A.5 through A.13)
lep_richness_lancaster	Narango et al. (2020)	number of <i>Lepidoptera</i> species supported in larval stage by the plant genus in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania, USA	numeric

Appendix B: Additional Information on BTI Field Data

Figure B.1 reproduces Figure 5 in Jenkins et al. (2010), which contains information on finer grain sizes than those available in Table 4.2. This information was input to the pedotransfer function “Rosetta Lite” from the U.S. Salinity Laboratory, available through the Hydrus 1D graphical user interface, to generate van Genuchten fitting parameters representing the soil moisture characteristic behavior of this soil.

Figure B.1 Particle Size Distributions for BTI Engineered Soil (Reproduced from Figure 5 in Jenkins, 2010)

Table B.2 Availability and Quality of BTI Soil Moisture Field Data

Year	Month	Missing Data?	Reasonable Pattern?	Last Frost Date	Conclusion
2014	4	COMPLETE	YES	4/17/2014	late frost
2014	5	PARTIAL	PARTIAL		incomplete data
2014	6	PARTIAL	YES		incomplete data
2014	7	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2014	8	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2014	9	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2014	10	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2015	4	COMPLETE	YES	4/25/2015	late frost
2015	5	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2015	6	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2015	7	NONE	NO		incomplete data
2015	8	PARTIAL	PARTIAL		incomplete data
2015	9	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2015	10	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	4	COMPLETE	YES	4/10/2016	MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	5	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	6	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	7	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	8	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	9	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2016	10	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	4	COMPLETE	YES	3/24/2017	MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	5	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	6	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	7	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	8	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	9	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2017	10	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	4	COMPLETE	YES	4/11/2018	MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	5	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	6	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	7	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	8	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	9	COMPLETE	YES		MEETS ALL CRITERIA
2018	10	PARTIAL	PARTIAL		incomplete data

Appendix C: Additional Information on Validation Measures

Percent bias describes the degree to which simulated values are larger or smaller than corresponding observed values (Gupta et al., 1999). By convention, a positive value indicates that observed values are greater on average than simulated values and a negative value indicates the opposite. A value of zero would indicate a perfect fit.

$$PBIAS = \frac{\sum(x_{obs} - x_{sim})}{\sum vx_{obs}} \times 100\%$$

where

PBIAS is percent bias,

x_{obs} is an individual observed data point, and

x_{sim} is an individual simulated data point.

Root mean square error is the square root of the mean squared error (difference between observed-simulated pairs) and provides an estimate of error in the same units as the underlying data (Dodson, 2022).

$$RMSE = \frac{\sum_1^n (x_{obs} - x_{sim})^2}{n}$$

where

RMSE is root mean square error (same units as the metric of interest),

n is the number of paired observed-simulated data points,

x_{obs} is an individual observed data point, and

x_{sim} is an individual simulated data point.

Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970) is frequently used to describe the fit between observed data and the results of hydrologic models. It describes the degree of spread about a line of equal fit between the observed and simulated values.

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_1^n (x_{obs} - x_{sim})^2}{\sum_1^n (x_{obs} - \bar{x}_{obs})^2}$$

where

NSE is Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency

x_{obs} is an individual observed data point,

x_{sim} is an individual simulated data point,

\bar{x}_{obs} is the mean of observed data points, and

n is the number of paired observed-simulated data points.

Appendix D: Additional Information on Wet Weather Events Representing Peak Flow Objectives

Table D.1 Historical Extreme Event Depths for Philadelphia International Airport Reported by NOAA Atlas 14

Duration (hr)	Return Period (yr)	Depth (mm)			
		Mean	90% C.I. Lower Bound	90% C.I. Upper Bound	
1	1	30.2	27.9	32.8	
1	2	36.6	33.8	39.9	
1	10	52.1	47.8	56.6	
1	25	60.5	55.1	65.8	
24	1	68.1	63.0	73.7	
24	2	82.0	75.9	88.9	
24	10	122.0	112.0	132.0	
24	25	149.0	136.0	161.0	

Figure D.1 Channel Protection Event 1, April 15, 2014

Figure D.2 Channel Protection Event 2, April 15-16, 2018

Figure D.3 Flooding (Life and Property Protection) Event, September 1, 2021

Appendix E: Additional Details and Discussion of Figure 4.14

This appendix contains raw data for Figure 4.14. Table E.1 lists plant species considered appropriate for ponding and drought conditions created by all 18 design scenarios. Table E.2 lists additional species considered appropriate for design scenarios 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 12, 15, and 18; species listed in Table E.1 are also appropriate for these scenarios. Table E.3 lists additional species considered appropriate for design scenarios 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16; species listed in Tables E.1 and E.2 are also appropriate for these scenarios.

Legend for Tables E.1 through E.2

Scientific Name: standardized genus and species name; see Appendix A

Symbol: USDA symbol; see Appendix A

Type: plant type from USDA PLANTS; no definitions of these terms are provided by USDA

Native Status: native status from USDA PLANTS; no definitions of these terms are provided by USDA, but I have inferred the following definitions:

- L48: continental United States
- CAN: Canada
- GL: Great Lakes region of the United States and Canada
- N: native
- I: introduced
- W: “Western” (meaning ambiguous, no definition available)
- NA: no data

Ponding: ponding tolerance on scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant); see Appendix A

Drought: drought tolerance on scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant); see Appendix A

Salt: salt tolerance on scale of 1 (least tolerant) to 3 (most tolerant); see Appendix A

Lepidoptera: number of native Lepidoptera species supported in the larval stage by this host plant genus in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania (Narango et al., 2020)

Table E.1: Plant Species Appearing in all 18 Design Scenarios

Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	<i>Lepidoptera</i>
<i>Althaea officinalis</i>	ALOF2	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	3.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	AMFR	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	2.50	2.00	25
<i>Schoenoplectus robustus</i>	BORO5	NA	NA	3.00	3.00	3.00	2
<i>Dasiphora fruticosa</i>	DAFR6	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Deschampsia alpina</i>	DEAL6	Graminoid	CAN (N), GL (N)	3.00	3.00	2.50	0
<i>Distichlis spicata</i>	DISP	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Hypericum kalmianum</i>	HYKA	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	20
<i>Iva frutescens</i>	IVFR	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Juncus roemerianus</i>	JURO	Graminoid	L48 (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	9
<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i>	LYLI	Shrub	L48 (N)	3.00	3.00	1.00	11
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	LYSA2	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	3.00	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	PHAR3	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	2.50	4

Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	Lepidoptera
<i>Physocarpus opulifolius</i>	PHOPO	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	2.75	1.75	39
<i>Populus balsamifera</i>	POBAB2	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	329
<i>Pycnanthemum tenuifolium</i>	PYTE	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	2.50	1.00	4
<i>Rudbeckia laciniata</i>	RULA3	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	2.75	1.25	17
<i>Ruppia maritima</i>	RUMA5	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Solidago sempervirens</i>	SOSE	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	2.67	2.00	129
<i>Spartina alterniflora</i>	SPAL	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	11
<i>Spartina cynosuroides</i>	SPCY	Graminoid	L48 (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	11
<i>Spartina patens</i>	SPPA	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	11
<i>Symphotrichum tenuifolium</i>	SYTE6	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	106
<i>Typha x glauca</i>	TYGL	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	15
<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	VACO	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	281
<i>Zostera marina</i>	ZOMA	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	3.00	3.00	3.00	NA

Table E.2: Additional Plant Species Appearing in Design Scenarios 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 12, 15, 18

Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	Lepidoptera
<i>Acer negundo</i>	ACNE2	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.50	287
<i>Agastache foeniculum</i>	AGFO	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	2.00	3
<i>Allium stellatum</i>	ALST	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	2.00	18
<i>Andropogon gerardii</i>	ANGE	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.90	1.33	13
<i>Carex bicknellii</i>	CABI3	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.50	33
<i>Carex hirsutella</i>	CAHI6	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.50	2.50	1.00	33
<i>Coreopsis tripteris</i>	COTR4	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Desmodium canadense</i>	DECA7	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	3.00	18
<i>Diervilla lonicera</i>	DILO	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.50	2.75	1.17	4
<i>Dirca palustris</i>	DIPA9	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	1
<i>Gaylussacia dumosa</i>	GADU	Subshrub, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	45
<i>Gaylussacia frondosa</i>	GAFR2	Shrub	L48 (N)	2.00	3.00	1.00	45
<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i>	GLTR	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.75	1.67	43
<i>Heterotheca camporum</i>	HECAC2	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.50	3.00	1.00	NA
<i>Ilex vomitoria</i>	ILVO	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N)	2.00	3.00	2.50	43
<i>Kosteletzkya virginica</i>	KOVI	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N)	2.00	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Lespedeza virginica</i>	LEVI7	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.50	2.50	1.00	21
<i>Morella pensylvanica</i>	MOPE6	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	2.50	42
<i>Muhlenbergia schreberi</i>	MUSC	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	4
<i>Oenothera fruticosa</i>	OEFR	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	3.00	18
<i>Parthenium integrifolium</i>	PAIN3	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.50	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Packera paupercula</i>	PAPA20	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	2.00	3
<i>Penstemon digitalis</i>	PEDI	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (I)	2.00	2.80	1.70	12
<i>Quercus macrocarpa</i>	QUMA2	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.67	1.50	511
<i>Quercus shumardii</i>	QUSH	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	511
<i>Rhododendron maximum</i>	RHMA4	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	2.67	1.00	63
<i>Rudbeckia fulgida</i>	RUFU2	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (I)	2.00	2.50	1.00	17
<i>Scutellaria incana</i>	SCIN	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.50	2.50	1.00	2
<i>Senna marilandica</i>	SEMA11	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	6
<i>Solidago speciosa</i>	SOSP2	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.50	2.50	2.00	129
<i>Spigelia marilandica</i>	SPMA3	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.50	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Sporobolus virginicus</i>	SPVI3	Graminoid	L48 (N)	2.00	3.00	2.00	1
<i>Vaccinium pallidum</i>	VAPA4	Subshrub, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	NA	281

Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	Lepidoptera
<i>Verbena urticifolia</i>	VEUR	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	2.00	3.00	2.00	13
<i>Viola brittoniana</i>	VIBR	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	2.00	2.50	1.00	30
<i>Sedum x</i>	NA	NA	NA	2.00	3.00	3.00	6

Table E.3: Additional Plant Species Appearing in Design Scenarios 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16

Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	Lepidoptera
<i>Allium cernuum</i>	ALCE2	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	3.00	18
<i>Andropogon ternarius</i>	ANTE2	Graminoid	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	13
<i>Antennaria spp.</i>	ANTEN	NA	NA	NA	3.00	2.00	3
<i>Andropogon virginicus</i>	ANVI2	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.75	1.00	13
<i>Artemisia ludoviciana</i>	ARLU	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	2.00	NA
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	ARUV	Subshrub, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N), GL (N)	1.00	2.83	2.25	NA
<i>Asclepias tuberosa</i>	ASTU	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.80	1.62	13
<i>Avena sativa</i>	AVSA	Graminoid	L48 (I), CAN (W), GL (W)	1.00	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Baptisia alba</i>	BAAL	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	3.00	21
<i>Baptisia australis</i>	BAAU	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	2.83	1.67	21
<i>Baptisia sphaerocarpa</i>	BASP	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	21
<i>Baptisia tinctoria</i>	BATI	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	21
<i>Blephilia ciliata</i>	BLCI	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	0
<i>Carex albicans</i>	CAAL25	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	33
<i>Callicarpa americana</i>	CAAM2	Shrub	L48 (N)	1.00	2.83	1.00	NA
<i>Carya cordiformis</i>	CACO15	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	241
<i>Carex eburnea</i>	CAEB2	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	33
<i>Carya glabra</i>	CAGL8	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	1.00	241
<i>Cercis canadensis</i>	CECA4	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.88	1.00	24
<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	CECY2	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I), GL (I)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Celtis occidentalis</i>	CEOC	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.70	46
<i>Coreopsis palmata</i>	COPA10	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Comptonia peregrina</i>	COPE80	Subshrub, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	59
<i>Coreopsis grandiflora lanceolata verticillata</i>	COVE5	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Crataegus crus-galli</i>	CRCR2	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.33	155
<i>Danthonia spicata</i>	DASP2	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N), GL (N)	1.00	3.00	3.00	2
<i>Dichanthelium aciculare</i>	DIAC	Graminoid	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	3
<i>Elaeagnus commutata</i>	ELCO	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	NA
<i>Erigeron pulchellus</i>	ERPU	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	2.00	25
<i>Eragrostis spectabilis</i>	ERSP	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	3.00	1.00	4
<i>Euonymus atropurpureus</i>	EUAT5	Shrub, Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	13
<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i>	GABA	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	45
<i>Gaultheria procumbens</i>	GAPR2	Subshrub, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	1
<i>Geranium maculatum</i>	GEMA	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	2.00	26
<i>Geum triflorum</i>	GETR	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	1.50	2
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	GIBI2	Tree	L48 (I)	NA	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Helianthus divaricatus</i>	HEDI2	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	3.00	72
<i>Heuchera parviflora</i>	HEPA10	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	0
<i>Helianthus strumosus</i>	HEST	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	2.50	72
<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	HETU	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	2.00	72
<i>Heuchera villosa</i>	HEVI2	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	0
<i>Iris cristata</i>	IRCR	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	14

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Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	Lepidoptera
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	JUCO6	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N), GL (N)	1.00	3.00	1.67	34
<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	JUVI	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.88	1.50	34
<i>Kalmia latifolia</i>	KALA	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	33
<i>Kerria japonica</i>	KEJA	Shrub	L48 (I), CAN (I)	NA	3.00	3.00	NA
<i>Lespedeza capitata</i>	LECA8	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.83	2.00	21
<i>Leucanthemum x superbum</i>	LESU49	Forb/herb	L48 (I)	NA	3.00	2.00	NA
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	LEVU	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Mirabilis nyctaginea</i>	MINY	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Oligoneuron album</i>	OLAL2	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	2.00	NA
<i>Opuntia fragilis</i>	OPFR	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	3.00	4
<i>Ostrya virginiana</i>	OSVI	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	98
<i>Parthenium hispidum</i>	PAHI8	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i>	PAQU2	Vine	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.75	2.00	30
<i>Pennisetum alopecuroides</i>	PEAL	Graminoid	L48 (I)	1.00	2.67	2.00	NA
<i>Penstemon hirsutus</i>	PEHI	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	NA	12
<i>Phedimus hybridus</i>	PHHY3	NA	NA	NA	3.00	2.00	NA
<i>Phedimus spurius</i>	PHSP9	NA	NA	NA	3.00	2.00	NA
<i>Pinus virginiana</i>	PIVI2	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	3.00	1.67	172
<i>Prunus pumila</i>	PRPUP	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	2.00	419
<i>Quercus marilandica</i>	QUMA3	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	511
<i>Quercus muehlenbergii</i>	QUMU	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.75	511
<i>Quercus stellata</i>	QUST	Tree	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	511
<i>Rhus copallinum</i>	RHCO	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	1.50	55
<i>Rhus glabra</i>	RHGL	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.67	55
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i>	RHRO3	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N), GL (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA
<i>Rhus typhina</i>	RHTY	Shrub, Tree	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	2.50	55
<i>Rosa carolina</i>	ROCA4	Subshrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	2.00	119
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	ROPS	Tree	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	2.50	2.00	67
<i>Rubus allegheniensis</i>	RUAL	Subshrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	159
<i>Ruellia humilis</i>	RUHU	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.67	1.00	2
<i>Sassafras albidum</i>	SAAL5	Tree, Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	31
<i>Schizachyrium scoparium</i>	SCSC	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.88	6
<i>Sedum album</i>	SEAL	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	NA	3.00	2.00	6
<i>Sedum reflexum</i>	SERE4	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	NA	3.00	2.00	6
<i>Sedum sexangulare</i>	SESE6	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	NA	3.00	2.00	6
<i>Shepherdia canadensis</i>	SHCA	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	2.33	NA
<i>Sporobolus heterolepis</i>	SPHE	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	1
<i>Sporobolus neglectus</i>	SPNE2	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	3.00	1
<i>Stachys byzantina</i>	STBY	Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I)	NA	2.50	2.00	8
<i>Symphotrichum oblongifolium</i>	SYOB	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	106
<i>Symphotrichum oolentangiense</i>	SYOO	Forb/herb, Subshrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	2.50	2.00	106
<i>Tephrosia virginiana</i>	TEVI	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	4
<i>Thymus praecox</i>	THPRA	Subshrub, Forb/herb	L48 (I), CAN (I), GL (I)	NA	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Tridens flavus</i>	TRFL2	Graminoid	L48 (N), CAN (I)	1.00	3.00	1.00	7
<i>Uniola paniculata</i>	UNPA	Graminoid	L48 (N)	1.00	3.00	1.50	NA
<i>Vaccinium stamineum</i>	VAST	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	3.00	1.00	281
<i>Verbesina helianthoides</i>	VEHE	Forb/herb	L48 (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	18
<i>Verbena stricta</i>	VEST	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	2.50	2.00	13

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Scientific Name	Symbol	Type	Native Status	Ponding	Drought	Salt	<i>Lepidoptera</i>
<i>Viburnum acerifolium</i>	VIAC	Shrub, Subshrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.50	1.00	114
<i>Viburnum rafinesqueanum</i>	VIRA	Shrub	L48 (N), CAN (N)	1.00	2.67	1.50	114
<i>Waldsteinia fragarioides</i>	WAFR	Forb/herb	L48 (N), CAN (N)	NA	3.00	2.50	NA
<i>Yucca filamentosa</i>	YUFI	Subshrub, Shrub, Forb/herb	L48 (N)	NA	2.50	2.00	NA
<i>Sedum turnatum</i>	NA	NA	NA	1.00	2.50	1.00	NA

Appendix F: Larval Host Plants for 100 or More Species of *Lepidoptera*

This appendix presents an example application of the master list of bioretention plant species. Figure 3.6 is reproduced below, illustrating the 26 plant genera serving as larval hosts for 100 or more species of *Lepidoptera* in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania according to Narango et al. (2020). This figure is not limited to genera found in the master bioretention plant data list.

Figure 3.6: Plant genera supporting 100 or more species of butterfly larvae in Lancaster County, Pennsylvania (analysis of data provided by Narango et al., 2020). Includes two genera (*Malus* and *Castanea*) not found in master bioretention plant list.

Table F.1 provides additional information on the 24 plant genera found in the master bioretention plant list that serve as larval host plants for 100 or more species of *Lepidoptera* in Lancaster County. Twenty-two of these are woody genera consisting of tree and shrub species. Whether these species are appropriate for urban sites depends partly on context and available space. Where a genus includes shrub options, these may be appropriate for an urban site where larger trees would not be. The two herbaceous genera appearing in the “top 24” are the *Solidago* or goldenrod genus and the *Symphotrichum* or aster genus. Both of these genera include ponding and drought tolerant species.

Table F.1: Twenty Four Larval Host Plant Genera Supporting 100+ Species of Lepidoptera

Plant Genus	Common Name	Type	Lepidoptera Supported	Plant Species	Ponding Tolerance			Drought Tolerance			Salt Tolerance		
					Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
<i>Quercus</i>	oak	trees, shrubs	511	19	9	5	5	5	9	5	12	7	0
<i>Prunus</i>	cherry	trees, shrubs	419	4	3	0	0	0	3	1	2	2	0
<i>Salix</i>	willow	trees, shrubs	383	11	1	1	9	7	4	0	4	5	0
<i>Betula</i>	birch	trees	373	5	2	2	1	1	4	0	3	2	0
<i>Populus</i>	cottonwood, aspen, poplar	trees	329	5	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1
<i>Acer</i>	maple	trees, shrubs	287	7	3	2	1	1	5	1	5	2	0
<i>Vaccinium</i>	blueberry, cranberry	shrubs	281	12	3	6	3	2	6	3	10	0	1
<i>Carya</i>	hickory	trees	241	6	5	1	0	2	2	2	6	0	0
<i>Alnus</i>	alder	trees, shrubs	226	3	1	0	2	2	1	0	3	0	0
<i>Ulmus</i>	elm	trees	197	2	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	2	0
<i>Pinus</i>	pine	trees	172	7	5	1	1	2	4	1	3	4	0
<i>Rubus</i>	blackberry	shrubs	159	5	2	2	1	1	3	1	3	2	0
<i>Tilia</i>	basswood	tree	159	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
<i>Crataegus</i>	hawthorn	trees, shrubs	155	8	2	5	1	1	5	1	7	0	0
<i>Fraxinus</i>	ash	trees	139	3	1	0	2	2	1	0	1	2	0
<i>Juglans</i>	walnut	trees	137	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
<i>Fagus</i>	beech	tree	133	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
<i>Corylus</i>	hazelnut	shrub	129	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
<i>Solidago</i>	goldenrod	herbaceous	129	14	8	2	4	3	9	2	4	8	0
<i>Cornus</i>	dogwood	trees, shrubs	123	7	1	4	2	1	5	0	7	0	0
<i>Rosa</i>	rose	shrubs	119	4	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	0
<i>Viburnum</i>	arrow-wood, blackhaw	trees, shrubs	114	8	4	2	2	2	4	2	6	2	0
<i>Amelanchier</i>	service-berry	trees, shrubs	113	5	2	3	0	1	4	0	1	4	0
<i>Symphotrichum</i>	aster	herbaceous	106	20	4	4	11	4	8	3	13	5	1

Note: The number of ponding, drought, and salt tolerant species may not add up to the total in the case of missing ratings.

Appendix G: Additional Analysis of Climate Change Bioretention Simulations

This appendix provides further analyses of the finding that plant screening results reported in Section 5 do not change between the historical period (2003-2022) and projected future scenario (SSP5-8.5 2081-2100). In summary, although hydrologic performance decreases between the time periods, the hydraulic configuration of the bioretention design limits changes in ponding duration and 10-day soil moisture deficit. The resulting changes are not sufficient to cause a change in the plant screening result. It is important to note the limitations of this conclusion. First, the methodology followed assesses effects on plants of changes in ponding duration and soil moisture. It does not consider direct physiological effects of heat on the plants, and these effects merit further research to determine whether specific plant species would be able to persist under the conditions present in this scenario. Other factors affecting plants, such as erosive flows in bioretention due to more intense rainfall, are also outside the scope of this analysis.

Table G.1 summarizes mean annual performance of the three simulated bioretention designs for the historical period (2003-2022) and the projected future period. For all three designs, increased inflow volumes and intensities lead to substantially degraded hydrologic performance, with increases in mean annual surface outflow. Increased inflow and outflow occur in all 20 years, with variation shown in Figure G.1. This result is expected because surface storage, soil storage, and overflow elevation are unchanged between the two time periods and the system is therefore unable to manage the increased inflow through infiltration or evapotranspiration.

In spite of the increased volume and intensity of inflow, the mean of annual maximum ponding durations decreases slightly in the projected future time period. For design scenario 1,

maximum ponding durations increase during six years of the 20-year continuous simulation, but they decrease in the remaining 14 years (Table G.2). This result can be explained by the decreased duration and increased intensity of inflows exceeding the system’s storage capacity more frequently, resulting in shorter durations of ponded water in the system.

The maximum (most negative, indicating dryest conditions) soil moisture deficit increases slightly (becomes slightly wetter) on a mean annual basis. Individual years display small increases (14 of 20 years) and decreases (6 of 20 years). This result can be explained by the effect of net inflow being added to the system slightly exceeding the effect of increased potential evapotranspiration caused by higher air temperatures during the critical condition of some years.

Together, the decrease in mean annual ponding duration and slight increase (to a less dry condition) of mean annual soil moisture deficit explain the lack of change in the plant screening exercise discussed in Chapter 5. The number of plants passing the ponding duration screen does not decrease because the overall trend in ponding duration is a decreasing one. Plants that are sensitive to longer ponding durations are therefore not screened out in greater numbers in the projected long-term condition compared to the historical condition. There is very little change (less than 1 cm increase or decrease) in the maximum 10-day soil moisture deficit that occurs during each year. Because of this minimal change, there is no change in the number of plants passing the drought tolerance screen.

Table G.1: Mean Annual Performance under Historical and Projected Conditions

Design Scenario	Inflow (watershed-cm)			Surface Outflow (watershed-cm)			Longest Ponding Event (hr)			Maximum SMD (cm)		
	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change
1	107.24	128.88	21.64	24.05	49.94	25.88	32.85	29.30	-3.55	-5.81	-5.65	0.16
2	107.24	128.88	21.64	18.74	36.18	17.43	119.35	107.10	-12.25	-5.81	-5.65	0.16
3	107.24	128.88	21.64	25.36	46.54	21.18	93.15	80.15	-13.00	-5.81	-5.65	0.16

Figure G.1: Variation in Annual Values of Performance Measures by Design Scenario

Table G.2: Annual Results for Design Scenario 1

Year	Inflow (watershed-cm)			Surface Outflow (watershed-cm)			Longest Ponding Event (hr)			Maximum SMD (cm)		
	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change	2003-2022	2081-2100 SSP5-8.5	Change
1	119.72	132.98	13.26	12.35	28.86	16.51	35	41	6	-6.02	-5.63	0.39
2	133.63	158.46	24.83	50.05	88.52	38.48	31	17	-14	-5.41	-5.49	-0.08
3	109.45	137.14	27.69	38.22	66.55	28.34	40	32	-8	-5.71	-5.59	0.11
4	129.08	151.96	22.88	28.08	62.00	33.93	29	31	2	-5.39	-5.48	-0.09
5	114.65	144.68	30.03	18.85	52.78	33.93	49	35	-14	-5.17	-5.17	0.00
6	80.20	100.87	20.67	14.17	36.27	22.10	28	23	-5	-6.03	-5.70	0.33
7	115.43	137.92	22.49	17.94	44.72	26.78	38	29	-9	-5.29	-5.81	-0.52
8	112.44	135.84	23.40	40.30	80.85	40.56	38	32	-6	-6.06	-5.95	0.11
9	162.62	186.66	24.05	51.35	98.27	46.93	34	29	-5	-6.04	-5.92	0.12
10	88.00	104.77	16.77	17.81	49.27	31.46	44	17	-27	-6.47	-5.81	0.66
11	122.19	138.96	16.77	29.38	55.63	26.26	35	20	-15	-5.53	-5.58	-0.05
12	102.82	135.84	33.02	23.53	46.54	23.01	44	37	-7	-5.74	-5.51	0.23
13	81.11	97.88	16.77	1.95	23.92	21.97	25	21	-4	-5.84	-5.69	0.16
14	70.06	84.23	14.17	7.28	21.97	14.69	20	26	6	-6.19	-6.08	0.11
15	57.45	73.05	15.60	5.46	12.87	7.41	24	23	-1	-6.15	-5.61	0.54
16	136.88	159.24	22.36	25.09	46.93	21.84	28	50	22	-5.85	-5.66	0.19
17	110.62	138.44	27.82	20.80	41.21	20.41	28	39	11	-5.90	-5.27	0.63
18	120.37	145.85	25.48	40.30	69.80	29.51	32	21	-11	-6.09	-5.79	0.31
19	92.55	105.42	12.87	30.81	46.54	15.73	20	16	-4	-5.57	-5.62	-0.05
20	85.53	107.37	21.84	7.41	25.22	17.81	35	47	12	-5.72	-5.67	0.05